

Lectures on Some Types of algebra With Fuzzification

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CHAPTER ONE

SECTION ONE

1.1. Introduction to BCK-algebras

The notion of BCK-algebras was formulated first in 1966 by K. Iseki, Japanese mathematician. This notion is originated from two different ways.

One of the motivations is based on set theory. In set theory, there are three most elementary and fundamental operations including the general analytical operations introduced by L. Cantorovic and E. Livenson to make a new set from old sets. These fundamental operations are to make the union, the intersection and the set difference, then as a generalization of those three operations and properties, we have the notion of Boolean algebras. If we take both of the union and the intersection, then as a general algebra, the notion of distributive lattices is obtained. As a generalization of this notion, for example, there is the notion of semi rings. Moreover, if we consider the notion of the union or the intersection, we have the notion of an upper semi lattice or a lower semi lattice. But the notion of set difference was not considered systematically before K. Iseki. Another motivation is from classical and non-classical propositional calculus. There are some systems which contain the only implication functor among the logical functions. These examples are the system of positive implicational calculus, weak positive implicational calculus by Church, and BCI/ BCK-systems by C. A. Meredith (see A.N. Prior). From these relationships, K. Iseki introduced a new notion called a BCK-algebra.

Definitions and elementary properties of BCK-algebras are studied.

DEFINITION 1.1.1.

Let X be a set with a binary operation $*$ and constant 0 . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a BCK-algebra if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$\text{BCI-1} \quad ((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0,$$

$$\text{BCI-2} \quad (x * (x * y)) * y = 0,$$

$$\text{BCI-3} \quad x * x = 0,$$

BCI-4 $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$,

If a BCI-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies

BCI-5 $0 * x = 0$, for all $x \in X$, then we say that X is a BCK-algebra.

REMARK 1.1.2.

For brevity we also call $(X; *, 0)$ a BCK-algebra. In X we can define a binary relation \leq (by $x \leq y$ if and only if, $x * y = 0$).

DEFINITION 1.1.3.

Let X be a set with a binary operation $*$ and constant 0 . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a BCK-algebra if and only if, it satisfies that : for all $x, y, z \in X$,

BCI-1' $(x * y) * (x * z) \leq z * y$,

BCI-2' $x * (x * y) \leq y$,

BCI-3' $x \leq x$,

BCI-4 $x \leq y$ and $y \leq x$ imply $x = y$,

BCK-5' $0 \leq x$,

BCI-6' $x \leq y$ if and only if, $x * y = 0$.

REMARK 1.1.4.

Now, for any BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, $*$ is called a BCK-operation and \leq is called a BCK-ordering on X respectively.

Next, we consider the independence of the axiomatically system of BCK- algebras.

EXAMPLE 1.1.5.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ and the operation $*$ be defined as follows:

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies BCI-1, BCI-3, BCI-4 and BCK-5, but it does not satisfy BCI- 2.

EXAMPLE 1.1.6.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, w\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ y & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } y \neq 0, \\ x & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } y = 0. \end{cases}$$

where \leq is the natural ordering on X and $x < y$ denotes that $x \leq y$ and $x \neq y$.

Then $((X; *, 0)$ satisfies BCI-2 ,BCI-3, BCI-4 and BCK-5 , but does not satisfy BCI-1.

EXAMPLE 1.1.7.

Let $X = \{0,1\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

$*$	0	1
0	0	0
1	0	0

Then $(X;*, 0)$ satisfies BCI-1, BCI-2, BCI-3 and BCK-5, but it does not satisfy BCI-4.

EXAMPLE 1.1.8.

Let $X = \{0, 1,2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

$*$	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	2	2	0
2	2	2	0

Then $(X;*, 0)$ satisfies BCI-1, BCI-2, BCI-4 and BCK-5, but it does not satisfy BCI-3 .

EXAMPLE 1.1.9.

Let $X = \{0,1,2\}$ in which the operation $(*)$ is given by the table

$*$	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	2	0	0
2	2	2	0

Then $(X;*, 0)$ satisfies BCI-1- BCI-4, but it does not satisfy BCK-2.

The above examples show that BCI-1, BCI-2, BCI-3, BCI-4 and BCK-5 are independent each other.

Now, we give some elementary and fundamental properties of BCK-algebras.

THEOREM 1.1.10.

In a BCK-algebra $(X;*, 0)$, we have the following properties : for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (a) $x \leq y$ implies $z * y \leq z * x$.
- (b) $x \leq y$ and $y \leq z$ imply $x \leq z$.

Proof.

Let $x \leq y$. Then by BCI-1, we have $(z * y) * (z * x) \leq x * y$.
 Since $x \leq y$ implies $x * y = 0$, we obtain $(z * y) * (z * x) \leq 0$.
 Combining BCK-5' and BCI-4' we have $(z * y) * (z * x) = 0$,
 that is, $z * y \leq z * x$, and hence (a) holds.

By (a), $y \leq z$ implies $x * z \leq x * y$. If $x \leq y$ then $x * y = 0$. Hence $x * z \leq 0$, and so $x \leq z$. Therefore, we have (b). ■

Putting BCI-3', BCI-4' and (b) together we know that (X, \leq) is a partially ordered set.

THEOREM 1.1.11.

In a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proof.

By BCI-2', we have $x * (x * z) \leq z$. Making use of (a) and BCI-1', we get
 $(x * y) * z \leq (x * y) * (x * (x * z)) \leq (x * z) * y$.

Since x, y and z are arbitrary, interchanging y and z in the above inequality we obtain
 $(x * z) * y \leq (x * z) * (x * (x * y)) \leq (x * y) * z$. By BCI-4', we have
 $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$. ■

THEOREM 1.1.12.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. Then the following hold: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (a) $x * y \leq z$ implies $x * z \leq y$,
- (b) $(x * z) * (y * z) \leq x * y$,
- (c) $x \leq y$ implies $x * z \leq y * z$,
- (d) $x * y \leq x$,
- (e) $x * 0 = x$.

Proof.

(a) is a directly consequence of Theorem (1.1.11).

(b) follows from BCI-1' and (a) without any difficulty.

(c) Let $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$, and hence by (b), $(x * z) * (y * z) \leq x * y = 0$.

Hence $x * z \leq y * z$, and (c) holds.

(d) By virtue of (a), BCI-3 and BCK-5, we have $(x * y) * x = (x * x) * y = 0 * y = 0$.

Consequently $x * y \leq x$, proving (d).

(e) By BCI-2', we have $x * (x * 0) \leq 0$, that is, $x \leq x * 0$.

Moreover by (d), we get $x * 0 \leq x$. Hence by BCI 4', (e) holds. ■

REMARK 1.1.13.

For any $x, y \in X$ denote $x \wedge y = y * (y * x)$. Obviously, $x \wedge y$ is a lower bound of x and y , and $x \wedge x = x, x \wedge 0 = 0 \wedge x = 0$. But in general, $x \wedge y \neq y \wedge x$.

THEOREM 1.1.14

In any BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have $x * (y \wedge x) = x * y$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof.

For any $x, y \in X$, since $y \wedge x \leq y$, by Theorem (1.1.12(a)) we get $x * y \leq x * (y \wedge x)$.

On the other hand, by BCK-2' we have $x * (y \wedge x) = x * (x * (x * y)) \leq x * y$.

This means $x * y = x * (y \wedge x)$. ■

In the following, we give two equivalent definitions for BCI- algebras.

THEOREM 1.1.15.

An algebra $(X; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra if and only if it satisfies the following conditions:

$$\text{BCI-1 } ((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0,$$

$$(a) \quad x * (0 * y) = x,$$

$$\text{BCI-4 } x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \text{ imply } x = y.$$

Proof.

The part "only if" is obvious and omitted. We give the proof the part "if" as follows.

Putting $x = z = 0$ and using (BCI-1) we have $((0 * y) * (0 * 0)) * (0 * y) = 0$, $(0 * y) * (0 * 0) = 0, \Rightarrow 0 * y = 0$, thus BCK-5 holds.

Combining (a) and BCK-5 we get (1) $x * 0 = x$. Substituting 0 for y and z in BCI-1 and using (1) we easily obtain BCI-3 $x * x = 0$.

Replacing y by 0 in BCI-1 and applying (1) it follows that BCI-2 $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$. Summarizing the above results we have proved that $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK- algebra. ■

REMARK 1.1.16.

In combinatory logic, there are various combinators. The names of combinators are attached to formulas of the algebra in the following way :

If a combinator U has functionality V the corresponding formula is obtained by replacing $F Z W$ in V by $W * Z$ and equating the result with 0. (If a logical system is to be represented each $F Z W$ becomes $Z \supset W$ and the results is preceded by \vdash ; for more details on the combinators, their functionality and their corresponding tautologies, see H. B. Curry and R.

The functionality of the combinators K, B, C, I and W are given by

$$\begin{array}{l} \vdash Fx (Fyx) . \quad K \\ \vdash F(Fxy)(F(Fzx)(Fzy)) . \quad B \\ \vdash F(Fx(Fyz))(Fy(Fxz)) . \quad C \end{array}$$

$$\begin{cases} \vdash Fxx. & \text{I} \\ \vdash F (Fx (Fxy)) (Fxy). & \text{W.} \end{cases}$$

Thus according to the above procedure the corresponding formulas are :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{K} & (x * y) * x = 0, \\ \text{B} & ((y * z) * (x * z)) * (y * x) = 0, \\ \text{C} & ((z * x) * y) * ((z * y) * x) = 0, \\ \text{I} & x * x = 0, \\ \text{W} & (y * x) * ((y * x) * x) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

In 1981, M. W. Bunder, gave the following theorem.

THEOREM 1.1.17.

An algebra $(X;*, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is a BCK- algebra if and only if, it satisfies the axioms B, C and K and the rule BCI-4 .

Proof.

The part "only if" has been proved in Theorems (1.1.12 and 1.1.13). For the part "if", interchanging x and $y \in C$ gives $((z * y) * x) * ((z * x) * y) = 0$.

Applying the rule BCI-4 we have (1) $(z * y) * x = (z * x) * y$. By (1) and B it follows that $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = ((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0$, which says that BCL-1 holds. (1) and K give

$$(2) (x * x) * 0 = (x * 0) * x = 0.$$

$$\text{Using (2) and K we get } 0 * (x * x) = ((x * x) * 0) * (x * x) = 0.$$

The two identities above and the rule BCI-4 give BCI-3. By BCI-3 and K we obtain $0 * x = (x * x) * x = 0$, which is BCK-2. From (1) and BCI-3 it follows that $(x * (x * y)) * y = (x * y) * (x * y) = 0$, namely, BCI-2 holds.

Therefore, $(X;*, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra.

This theorem exhibits a closed relationship between BCK-algebras and combinatory logic, and the name of BCK-algebras is also taken from the BCK-systems of C. A. Meredith.

The following examples are interesting for development of BCK-algebras.

EXAMPLE 1.1.18.

Let A be an arbitrary nonempty set and let X be the set of all real valued functions defined on A . For $f, g \in X$, we define $f * g$ by: $(f * g)(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{iff } f(x) \leq g(x) \\ f(x) - g(x) & \text{iff } g(x) < f(x) \end{cases}$.

By the definition of $(X;*, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra.

EXAMPLE 1.1.19.

Let M be the set of all non-negative integers. For any x, y in M , we put

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ x - y & \text{if } y < x \end{cases} . \text{ Then } M \text{ is a BCK-algebra.}$$

EXAMPLE 1.1.20.

Let M be a partially ordered set with the least element (0). The operation (*) on M is defined by

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ x & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then $(M ; * , 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Hence any partially ordered set is regarded as a BCK-algebra.

As a special case of this example, we have

EXAMPLE 1.1.21.

Let X be a nonempty set. The power set is denoted by $P(X)$, and \emptyset the empty set, the binary operation (*) on $P(X)$ is given by, for any A, B in $P(X)$,

$$A * B = \begin{cases} \emptyset & \text{if } A \subseteq B \\ A - B & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \text{ Then } (P(X); * , \emptyset) \text{ is a BCK-algebra.}$$

EXAMPLE 1.1.22.

Let X be a partially ordered set with the least element 0 and a distinguished element a such that $0 \leq x$ for all x in X and $a \leq x$ for all nonzero x in X . The operation * is defined as follows:

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x < y \\ x & \text{if } y = 0 \\ a & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \text{ Then } (X ; * , 0) \text{ is a BCK-algebra.}$$

This example is due to Y. Seto (see K. Iséki) .

The main materials in this section are from Professor K. Iséki and S . Tanaka. The examples (1-4) were given by H .Jiang and Z .P. Tian.

CHAPTER ONE**SECTION TWO****1.2. Subalgebras of BCI/BCK-algebras**

In this section, we shall discuss the number of subalgebras in a finite BCK-algebra.

DEFINITION 1.2.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let X_0 be a nonempty subset of X . Then X_0 is called to be a subalgebra if X if, for any x, y in X_0 ; $x * y \in X_0$.

i.e., X_0 is closed under the binary operation $*$ of X .

THEOREM 1.2.2.

Suppose that $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra and let X_0 be a subalgebra of X . Then

- (a) $0 \in X_0$,
- (b) $(X_0; *, 0)$ is also a BCK-algebra,
- (c) X_0 is a subalgebra of X ,
- (d) $\{0\}$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proof.

This is immediate from Definition (1.2.1). ■

Routine calculation now leads to the following.

THEOREM 1.2.3.

If we are given a nonzero element x_0 of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then $(\{0, x_0\}; *, 0)$ is a subalgebra of X .

LEMMA 1.2.4.

- In a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, for all $x, y, z \in X$,
- (a) If $x \neq y$, then $y * x \neq 0$, whenever $x * y = 0$,
 - (b) $x * y = z$ implies $z * x = 0$.

Proof: Suppose that $x \neq y$ and $x * y = 0$.

If $y * x = 0$, by BCI-4 we obtain $x = y$, which contradicts to $x \neq y$. Hence (a) holds.

If $x * y = z$, it follows from Theorem (1.1.13(d)) that $z * x = (x * y) * x = (x * x) * y = 0 * y = 0$. This shows that (b) is true. ■

DEFINITION 1.2.5.

For a n -sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ the $(n-1) \times n$ matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * a_2 & a_2 * a_1 & \dots & a_n * a_1 \\ a_1 * a_3 & a_2 * a_3 & \dots & a_n * a_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_1 * a_n & a_2 * a_n & \dots & a_n * a_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

is called **the adjoint matrix relative to the n -sequence** a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n .

THEOREM 1.2.6.

Given a n -sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n ($n \geq 2$) of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if $a_i \neq a_j$, whenever $i \neq j$, ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$), then there exists at least a column in the adjoint matrix A which consists of nonzero elements.

Proof.

We proceed by induction on n . If $n = 2$ then $A = (a_1 * a_2, a_2 * a_1)$.

Suppose $a_1 * a_2 = a_2 * a_1 = 0$. Then we have $a_1 = a_2$ by BCI-4, a contradiction. Hence the assertion holds for $n = 2$.

Now suppose that the assertion holds for $n = k$. For a $k+1$ -sequence $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, a_{k+1}$ of X , let $a_i \neq a_j$ whenever $i \neq j$ ($1 \leq i, j \leq k+1$) and adjoint matrix

$$A_{k+1} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * a_2 & a_2 * a_1 & \dots & a_k * a_1 & a_{k+1} * a_1 \\ a_1 * a_3 & a_2 * a_3 & \dots & a_k * a_2 & a_{k+1} * a_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_1 * a_k & a_2 * a_k & \dots & a_k * a_{k-1} & a_{k+1} * a_{k-1} \\ a_1 * a_{k+1} & a_2 * a_{k+1} & \dots & a_k * a_{k+1} & a_{k+1} * a_k \end{pmatrix}$$

Denote

$$A_k = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * a_2 & a_2 * a_1 \dots & a_k * a_1 \\ a_1 * a_3 & a_2 * a_3 \dots & a_k * a_2 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_1 * a_k & a_2 * a_k \dots & a_k * a_{k-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

Obviously A_k is the adjoint matrix of the k -sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k . By the hypothesis of induction, we know that there is at least a column in A_k , which consists of nonzero elements, without loss of any generality suppose that it is the first column, thus

$$\begin{cases} a_1 * a_2 \neq 0, \\ a_1 * a_3 \neq 0, \\ \vdots \\ a_1 * a_k \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

Now it suffices to discuss the following cases:

If $a_1 * a_{k+1} \neq 0$ then each element in the first column of A_{k+1} is not equal to 0, and consequently the assertion holds for $n = k + 1$.

If $a_1 * a_{k+1} = 0$, then by Lemma (1.2.4), we obtain $a_{k+1} * a_1 \neq 0$ as $a_1 \neq a_{k+1}$.

We can verify $a_{k+1} * a_i \neq 0$ for $2 \leq i \leq k$. In fact, if there is i_0 ($2 \leq i_0 \leq k$) such that $a_{k+1} * a_{i_0} = 0$, in view of Theorem (1.1.12(b)) we get $a_1 * a_{i_0} = 0$ as $a_1 * a_{k+1} = 0$. This is impossible.

This shows that each element in the first column of A_{k+1} is not equal to 0, and so the assertion holds for $n = k + 1$. ■

REMARK 1.2.7.

For a set A denote the cardinal of A by $|A|$. For a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, $|X|$ is called to be the order of this algebra.

If $|X| < \infty$, then X is called to be of finite order.

If $|X| = n$, then X is said to be of order n .

If $|X| = \infty$, then X is said to be of infinite order.

THEOREM 1.2.8.

Any BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ with order $n + 1$ must contain a subalgebra with order $n(n \geq 1)$.

Proof.

Suppose $X = \{0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ is a BCK-algebra with order $n + 1$, in which $a_i \neq a_j$ whenever $i \neq j$ and let

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * a_2 & a_2 * a_1 & \dots & a_n * a_1 \\ a_1 * a_3 & a_2 * a_3 & \dots & a_n * a_2 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_1 * a_n & a_2 * a_n & \dots & a_n * a_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

be the adjoint matrix of the n -sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n . By Theorem (1.2.6) there exists at least a column in A which consists of nonzero elements, without loss of generality, we can suppose it is the n -th column of A that is, $a_n * a^i \neq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$.

We now show that $X_0 = \{0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}\}$ is a subalgebra of X . In fact, if not, then there are i and $j (1 \leq i, j \leq n-1)$ such that $i \neq j$ and $a_i * a_j = a_n$. By means of Lemma (1.2.4(a)), we have $a_n * a_i = 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$, which contradicts to $a_n * a_i \neq 0 (1 \leq i \leq n-1)$. ■

Next we give a theorem of estimating the number of subalgebras in a finite BCK-algebra.

THEOREM 1.2.9.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra with order $n (\geq 1)$. Then $1 \leq N(i) \leq C_{n-1}^{i-1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where $N(i)$ denotes the number of subalgebras with order i in X .

Proof.

We know that any subalgebra with order $i (1 \leq i \leq n)$ consists of 0 and $i-1$ nonzero elements. Since X contain only $n-1$ nonzero elements, it follows that $N(i) \leq C_{n-1}^{i-1}$.

On the other hand, by Theorem (1.2.8), X at least contains a subalgebra X_{n-1} with order $n-1$, X_{n-1} contains a subalgebra X_{n-2} with order $n-2$, repeating this argument we get that $1 \leq N(i)$ for all $i (1 \leq i \leq n)$. This completes the proof.

EXAMPLE 1.2.10. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	a
b	b	a	0	b
c	c	c	c	0

Simple calculations show that $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra and the lattice of subalgebras in X is as follows:

It is not difficult to see that $N(i) = C_{4-1}^{i-1}$, $i=1, 2, 3, 2, 1$. This example shows that in Theorem (1.2.9), $N(i) = C_{n-1}^{i-1}$ may hold.

EXAMPLE 1.2.11.

Let $X = \{0, 1\}$ in which $*$ is defined by $0 * 0 = 0 * 1 = 1 * 1 = 0$ and $1 * 0 = 1$.

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is BCK-algebra and $1 = N(i) = C_{2-1}^{i-1}$, $i=1, 2$.

This example shows that in Theorem (1.2.8), $1 = N(i)$ may hold.

EXAMPLE 1.2.12.

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ with $*$ table be as follows:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	0	a
b	b	b	0	0	0
c	c	c	c	0	c
d	d	d	b	b	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, and in X $1 < N(3) < C_{5-1}^{3-1}$.

This example shows that in Theorem (1.2.9), $1 < N(i)$ and $N(i) < C_{n-1}^{i-1}$.

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION THREE

1.3. Bounded BCI/BCK-algebras

In this section, we study bounded of a BCK-algebra.

DEFINITION 1.3.1.

If there is an element e of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfying $x \leq e$, for all x in X , that mean $(x * e = 0)$ the element e is called **unit of X**. a BCK-algebra with unit is called to be a **bounded**.

In a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we denote $e * x$ by N_x or x^* .

EXAMPLE 1.3.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and $*$ operation be given by the table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded BCK-algebra with unit 4.

EXAMPLE 1.3.3.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, w\}$ with $*$ operation be defined by: for all $x, y, w \in X$

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \leq w \\ 1 & \text{if } y < x < w \text{ and } y \neq 0 \\ w & \text{if } y < x = w \text{ and } y \neq 0 \\ x & \text{if } y < x \leq w \text{ and } y = 0 \end{cases}$$

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded BCK-algebra with unit w .

EXAMPLE 1.3.4.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ with the natural order. Then we define

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y, \\ 1 & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } y \neq 0, \\ x & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } y = 0. \end{cases}$$

Under the definition of $*$, $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, but this is not bounded.

This shows that the class of bounded BCK-algebras is a proper subclass of the class of BCK-algebras.

Next, we give some properties about N_x or x^* .

THEOREM 1.3.5.

In a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have, for all $x, y \in X$

- (a) $e^* = 0$, $0^* = e$,
- (b) $x^{**} \leq x$,
- (c) $x^* * y^* \leq y * x$,
- (d) $y \leq z$ implies $x^* \leq y^*$,
- (e) $(x * y)^* = (y * x)^*$,
- (f) $e \wedge x = x$,
- (g) $x \wedge e = x^{**}$,
- (h) $x^{***} = x^*$.

DEFINITION 1.3.6.

For a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if an element x satisfies $x^{**} = x$, then x is called an **involution**.

The set of all involutions of a bounded BCK-algebra X is denoted by $S(X)$. Since $0^{**} = e^* = 0$ and $e^{**} = 0^* = e$, the elements 0 and e are contained in $S(X)$. Hence $S(X)$ is not empty set.

THEOREM 1.3.7.

In a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have $x * y^* = y * x^*$, for all $x, y \in S(X)$.

THEOREM 1.3.8.

For any bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, $S(X)$ is bounded subalgebra of X , which is called **the involutory subalgebra of X** .

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } x, y \in S(X). \text{ Then by Theorem (1.1.11) and (1.3.5(h)),} \\ (x * y) * (x * y)^{**} &= (x^{**} * y) * (x * y)^{**} \\ &= ((x * y)^{***} * y) * x^* = ((x * y)^* * y) * x^* \\ &= (x^{**} * y) * (x * y) = (x * y) * (x * y) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

But then, $(x * y)^{**} * (x * y) = 0$ follows from BCI-2. Thus applying BCI-4 we obtain

$(x * y)^{**} = x * y$, which says $x * y \in S(X)$, and consequently $S(X)$ is closed with respect to the operation $*$, namely, $S(X)$ is a subalgebra of X . ■

In the Example (1.3.3), $S(X) = \{0, 1, w\}$. The following theorem give a way extending BCK-algebras.

THEOREM 1.3.9.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and $e \notin X$. We define the operation $'$ on $\bar{X} = X \cup \{e\}$ as follows

$$x *' y = \begin{cases} x * y & \text{if } x, y \in X \\ 0 & \text{if } x \in X \text{ and } y = e \\ e & \text{if } x = e \text{ and } y \in X \\ 0 & \text{if } x = y = e \end{cases}$$

Then $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ is a bounded BCK-algebra with unit e .

Proof.

In view of Theorem (1.1.17) it suffices to verify BCK-1. If $x, y, z \in X$, then BCK-1, to prove $((x *' y) *' (x *' z)) *' (z *' y) = 0$, if $x = e$, then

$$((e *' y) *' (e *' z)) *' (z *' y) = (e *' e) *' (z *' y) = 0 *' (z *' y) = 0,$$

$$\text{If } x = e \text{ and } y = e, \text{ then } ((e *' e) *' (e *' z)) *' (z *' e) = (0 *' e) *' 0 = 0 *' 0 = 0,$$

$$\text{If } x = e \text{ and } z = e, \text{ then } ((e *' y) *' (e *' e)) *' (e *' y) = (e *' 0) *' e = e *' e = 0,$$

$$\text{If } x = y = z = e, \text{ then } ((e *' e) *' (e *' e)) *' (e *' e) = (0 *' 0) *' 0 = 0,$$

$$\text{If } x \neq e, z \neq e \text{ and } y = e, \text{ then } ((x *' e) *' (x *' z)) *' (z *' e) = (0 *' (x *' z)) *' 0 = 0,$$

$$\text{If } x \neq e, y \neq e \text{ and } z = e, \text{ then } ((x *' y) *' (x *' e)) *' (e *' y) = ((x *' y) *' 0) *' e = 0,$$

$$\text{If } x \neq e \text{ and } y = z = e, \text{ then } (x *' e) *' (x *' e) *' (e *' e) = (0 *' 0) *' 0 = e.$$

This shows that $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ satisfies BCK-1.

$$\text{BCK-2, to prove } (x *' (x *' y)) *' y = 0, \text{ if } x = e, (e *' (e *' y)) *' y = (e *' e) *' y = 0 *' y = 0$$

$$\text{If } x \neq e \text{ and } y = e, (x *' (x *' e)) *' e = (x *' 0) *' e = x *' e = 0$$

$$\text{If } x \neq e \text{ and } y \neq e, (x *' (x *' y)) *' y = 0$$

This shows that $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ satisfies BCK-2.

BCK-3, to prove $x *' x = 0$, if $x = e$, then $e *' e = 0$, and if $x \neq e$, then $x * x = 0$

BCK-4, to prove $x *' y = 0$ and $y *' x = 0$, then $x = y$.

If $x *' y = 0$, then either $x \in X, y = e$ or $x = y = e$, then $x = y = e$.

If $y *' x = 0$, then either $y \in X, x = e$ or $x = y = e$, then $x = y = e$.

This shows that $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ satisfies BCK-4.

BCK-5, to prove $0 *' x = 0$, if $x = e$, then $0 *' e = 0$. And if $x \neq e$, then $0 * x = 0$ and so it is a BCK-algebra.

Since $e *' x = e$, for all $x \in X$, then $x = e$. And $e *' e = e$. It is clear that e is unit of \bar{X} . ■

It is worth to note that each nonzero element of X is not an involution in \bar{X} . This shows that there is such a BCK-algebra that the set of all involutions consists of 0 and unit. From now on we call $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ the **Iséki's extension** of $(X; *, 0)$.

EXAMPLE 1.3.10.

Let $X = \{0, a, b, 1\}$ and $*$ be given by :

$*$	0	a	b	1
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	0
b	b	b	0	0
1	1	b	a	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded BCK algebra and 1 is unit of X . It is easy to see that $S(X) = X$.

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION FOUR

1.4. Positive implicative BCI/BCK-algebras

In this section, we will discuss an important class of algebras called positive implicative BCK-algebras, which was introduced by K. Iséki in 1975.

DEFINITION 1.4.1.

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called to be **positive implicative** if it satisfies for all $x, y, z \in X$, $(x * z) * (y * z) = (x * y) * z$.

In order to give some equivalent conditions of positive implicativity we need following lemma.

LEMMA 1.4.2.

In any BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) \leq x * (x * (y * (y * x)))$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. To prove it, we enough prove

$((x * (x * y)) * (y * x)) * (x * (x * (y * (y * x)))) = 0$. Because

$$\begin{aligned} & ((x * (x * y)) * (y * x)) * (x * (x * (y * (y * x)))) \\ &= ((x * (x * (x * (y * (y * x)))) * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.11).} \\ &= ((x * (y * (y * x))) * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.16).} \\ &\leq (y * (y * (y * x))) * (y * x), \text{ by BCI-1.} \\ &= (y * x) * (y * x) = 0, \text{ by BCI-2.} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) \leq x * (x * (y * (y * x)))$. ■

THEOREM 1.4.3.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. Then the following conditions are equivalent each other: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (a) X is positive implicative,
- (b) $x * y = (x * y) * y$,
- (c) $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = x * (x * (y * (y * x)))$,
- (d) $x * y = (x * y) * (x * (x * y))$,
- (e) $x * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y)$,
- (f) $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = (y * (y * x)) * (x * y)$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b) By Definition (1.4.1), we have

$$x * y = (x * y) * 0 = (x * y) * (y * y) = (x * y) * y, \text{ which is (b).}$$

(b) \Rightarrow (c) In (b), if we substitute $x * (y * (y * x))$ for y , then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x * (x * (y * (y * x))) &= (x * (x * (y * (y * x)))) * (x * (y * (y * x))), \text{ by (b).} \\ &\leq (y * (y * x)) * (x * (y * (y * x))), \text{ by BCI-1.} \\ &< (y * (y * x)) * (x * y), \text{ by (b).} \\ &= (y * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.11).} \\ &= ((y * (x * y)) * (y * x)) * (y * x), \text{ by (b),} \\ &\leq (x * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by BCI-1.} \end{aligned}$$

in the above proof, we use $x * y \leq x * (y * (y * x))$.

Combining Lemma (1.4.2), we obtain (c).

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Replacing x by $y * x$ in (c) we obtain

$$(y * x) * ((y * x) * y) * (y * (y * x)) = (y * x) * ((y * x) * (y * (y * (y * x)))) \\ = (y * x) * ((y * x) * (y * x)) = (y * x). \text{ Thus (d) holds.}$$

(d) \Rightarrow (e). Substituting $x * y$ for y we get

$$x * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * (x * (x * y))) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y),$$

thus (e) holds.

(e) \Rightarrow (f). Right $*$ multiplying both sides of (e) by $y * x$, we have

$$(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = ((x * (x * y)) * (x * y)) * (y * x) \\ \leq (y * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by BCI-1.} \\ = (y * (y * x)) * (x * y), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.11).}$$

By symmetry, we obtain the converse inequality. Thus (f) holds.

(f) \Rightarrow (b). If we substitute $x * y$ for y in (f), then we obtain

$$x * y = (x * (x * (x * y))) * 0 \\ = (x * (x * (x * y))) * ((x * y) * x), \text{ by} \\ = ((x * y) * ((x * y) * x)) * (x * (x * y)) \\ = (x * y) * (x * (x * y)), \\ = (x * (x * (x * y))) * y, \text{ by Theorem (1.1.11).} \\ = (x * y) * y, \text{ which is (b).}$$

(b) \Rightarrow (a). Suppose (b) holds. Then

$$((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z) \\ = (((x * z) * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z) \\ \leq ((x * z) * y) * ((x * y) * z) \\ = ((x * y) * z) * ((x * y) * z) = 0,$$

thus $(x * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * y) * z$.

The converse inequality is clear, and (a) holds. This finishes the proof of the theorem. ■

The identity (f) motivates us to characterize positive implicative BCK-algebra by a set of identities.

THEOREM 1.4.4.

An algebra $(X; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra if and only if it satisfies BCI-1, BCK-5 and

$$(f) (x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = (y * (y * x)) * (x * y),$$

$$(g) x * 0 = x.$$

Proof.

Necessity being obvious, we only give the proof of the part " if " as follows. By BCK-5 and (g), we obtain

$$x * (0 * y) = x * 0 = x, \text{ which in Theorem (1.1.15(a)).}$$

If $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$, then (f) and (g) give

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (x * 0) * 0 = (x * (x * y)) * (y * x) \\ &= (y * (y * x)) * (x * y) = (y * 0) * 0 = y, \text{ hence BCI-4 holds.} \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem (1.1.15), $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Since it satisfies (f), using Theorem (1.4.3) we know that X is also positive implicative, proving the theorem. ■

THEOREM 1.4.5.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. Then the following conditions are equivalent:

- (a) X is positive implicative,
- (b) $(x * y) * z = 0$ implies $(x * z) * (y * z) = 0$,
- (c) $(x * y) * y = 0$ implies $x * y = 0$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b) is trivial.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). If $(x * y) * y = 0$, then (b) gives $x * y = (x * y) * (y * y) = 0$.

This says that (c) holds.

(c) \Rightarrow (a) Denote $u = (x * y) * y$. Theorem (1.1.11) gives

$$((x * u) * y) * y = ((x * y) * y) * u = ((x * y) * y) * ((x * y) * y) = 0.$$

By (c) we have $(x * u) * y = 0$, that is, $(x * y) * ((x * y) * y) = 0$.

Since $((x * y) * y) * (x * y) = 0$ holds in any BCK-algebra by BCK-5, we have by BCI-4 $x * y = (x * y) * y$, i.e. X is positive implicative. Hence (a) holds. The proof is complete. ■

THEOREM 1.4.6.

The Iséki's extension of a positive implicative BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is still positive implicative.

Proof.

Let $e \notin X$ and denote $\bar{X} = X \cup \{e\}$. Let $*'$ be defined as in Theorem (1.3.9). Then for all x in X , $(e *' x) *' x = e *' x$, $(x *' e) *' e = 0 *' e = 0 = x *' e$, $(e *' e) *' e = 0 *' e = 0 = e *' e$.

Since X is positive implicative, for x, y in X we have $x * y = (x * y) * y$. The above results show that $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ is positive implicative. This completes the proof.

Before concluding this section, we give several examples.

EXAMPLE 1.4.7.

Let $X = \{0, a, b, 1\}$ and $*$ on X be given by the table:

*	0	a	b	1
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	0
b	b	b	0	0

1	1	1	1	0
---	---	---	---	---

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra .

EXAMPLE 1.4.8.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ with the natural order and $*$ be defined as follows

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y, \\ x & \text{if } y < x. \end{cases}$$

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded positive implicative BCK-algebra and $(X; \leq)$ is a totally ordered set where \leq is the BCK-order.

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION FIVE

1.5. Commutative BCK-algebras

In 1975, S. Tanaka introduced and investigated a new class of BCK-algebras, called commutative BCK-algebras.

Now, it have an important aspect.

DEFINITION 1.5.1.

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is said to be commutative if it satisfies for all $x, y \in X$,

$$x * (x * y) = y * (y * x), \text{ i.e., } x \wedge y = y \wedge x.$$

From the symmetry of x and y in the above equality and BCI-4 we have the following theorem.

THEOREM 1.5.2.

For a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following are equivalent:

(a) X is commutative,

(b) $x * (x * y) \leq y * (y * x)$, (c) $(x * (x * y)) * (y * (y * x)) = 0$.

Obviously, any subalgebra of a commutative BCK-algebra is still commutative.

EXAMPLE 1.5.3.

Let $X = \{ 0,1,2,3,4 \}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0	0
3	3	1	1	0	0
4	4	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, but it is not commutative.

EXAMPLE 1.5.4.

Let $X = \cup_{i=1}^m A_i$ where $A_i \cap A_j = \{ 0 \}$ ($i \neq j$) and A_i consists of

$0 = a_{i0} < a_{i1} < \dots < a_{ij} < \dots$. For $x, y \in X$, we define

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y, \\ a_{ik-1} & \text{if } y \leq x \text{ and } x = a_{ik}, y = a_{i1} \\ x & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

of course \leq and $<$ are the order on A_i . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra.

EXAMPLE 1.5.5.

Let $X = \{ 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, a, b, \dots, c \}$ and suppose the order is defined as follows: $0 < 1 < 2 < \dots < n < a, b, \dots, c$,

and every pair of a, b, c is incomparable.

Denote $N = \{ 0, 1, 2, \dots, n \}$ and $A = \{ a, b, \dots, c \}$. In X the binary operation $(*)$ is given by

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y, \\ x - y & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } x \in N, \\ n + 1 - y & \text{if } y < x, y \neq 0, x \in A \text{ and } y \in N, \\ x & \text{if } y = 0 \text{ and } x \in A, \\ 1 & \text{if } x \neq y \text{ and } x, y \in A \end{cases}$$

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra.

EXAMPLE 1.5.6.

Suppose $|X| \geq 2$ and $0 \in X$. if $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, then the Iséki's extension is not commutative.

DEFINITION 1.5.7.

A partially ordered set (L, \leq) is said to be a lower semilattice if every pair of elements in L has a greatest lower bound (meet); it is called to be an upper semilattice if every pair of elements in L has a least upper bound (join); the operations join and meet are denoted by \vee and \wedge respectively. If (L, \leq) is both an upper and a lower semilattice, then it is called to be a lattice. A lattice is said to be distributive if it satisfies either of the distributive laws:

$$(D1) \quad x \wedge (y \vee z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z),$$

$$(D2) \quad x \vee (y \wedge z) = (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z)$$

DEFINITION 1.5.8.

A lattice (L, \leq) is said to be bounded if there are elements 0 and 1 in L such that for any x in L , $0 \leq x \leq 1$, which is equivalent to $x \wedge 0 = 0$ and $x \vee 1 = 1$. Two elements a, b of a bounded lattice are complements if $a \vee b = 1$ and $a \wedge b = 0$. In this case each of a, b is the complement of the other.

A complemented lattice is a bounded lattice in which every element has a complement.

Now we investigate the connection between commutative BCK-algebra and lattices.

THEOREM 1.5.9.

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is commutative if and only if, it is a lower semilattice with respect to BCK-order \leq .

Proof.

Suppose $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra. By BCI-2' and Theorem (1.1.12(d)) we know that $x \wedge y \leq x, y$. Let z be any element of X such that $z < x, y$. Then $z * x = z * y = 0$, so

$$z = z * 0 = z * (z * x) = x * (x * z).$$

By the same reason we have $z = y * (y * z)$, hence

$$z = x * (x * z) = x * (x * (y * (y * z))) \leq x * (x * y) = x \wedge y.$$

This says that for all x, y in X , $x \wedge y$ is the greatest lower bound, and so (X, \leq) is a lower semilattice.

Conversely, if $(X; *, 0)$ is a lower semilattice, then for any x, y in X , $x \wedge y$ is the greatest lower bound of x and y . Since $y \wedge x$ is a common lower bound of x and y , it follows that $y \wedge x \leq x \wedge y$. By Theorem (1.5.2), X is commutative, completing the proof. i.e., $x \leq y$. (C1) holds.

(i) \Leftrightarrow (iii) is obvious. The proof is complete.

The condition (i) is simpler. We wish that the readers verify the commutativity of the examples 2 and 3 in this section by (i). ■

The notion of initial sections in a BCK-algebra is important, by means of which we can give an equivalent condition of commutativity.

DEFINITION 1.5.11.

For a BCK-algebra X , the set $A(x) = \{y \in X : y \leq x\}$ is an initial section of an element x .

THEOREM 1.5.12.

A BCK-algebra X is commutative if and only if, $A(x) \cap A(y) = A(x \wedge y)$,

for all x, y of X

Proof.

Let X be a commutative BCK-algebra. If $z \in A(x) \cap A(y)$, then $z \leq x, y$. Hence $z \leq x \wedge y$, which implies $z \in A(x \wedge y)$. Thus

$$A(x) \cap A(y) \subseteq A(x \wedge y).$$

Conversely, if $z \in A(x \wedge y)$ then $z \leq x \wedge y$. Hence $z \leq x, y$, and so

$$z \in A(x) \cap A(y). \text{ This shows } A(x) \cap A(y) = A(x \wedge y), \text{ proving the necessity.}$$

Now, if we assume that $A(x) \cap A(y) = A(x \wedge y)$, then

$$A(x \wedge y) = A(x) \cap A(y) = A(y) \cap A(x) = A(y \wedge x).$$

Hence $x \wedge y \in A(y \wedge x)$. Therefore $x \wedge y \leq y \wedge x$. By Theorem (1.5.2(b)), X is commutative. This finishes the proof. ■

THEOREM 1.5.13.

A BCK-algebra X is commutative if and only if, $x*(x*y) = y*(y*(x*(x*y)))$

for all x, y in X

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) It is immediate from Theorem (1.5.10(i)).

Conversely if we assume $x*(x*y) = y*(y*(x*(x*y)))$ then $x \leq y$ implies that

$$x = x*0 = x*(x*y) = y*(y*(x*(x*y))) = y*(y*x).$$

By Theorem (1.5.10(i)), X is commutative. This says that the implication (\Leftarrow) holds. The proof is complete. ■

Next, we discuss bounded commutative BCK-algebras, in such algebras denote $x \vee y = N(Nx \wedge Ny)$.

THEOREM 1.5.14.

For a bounded commutative BCK-algebra X , we have

- (a) $NNx = x$ for all $x \in X$,
- (b) $Nx \vee Ny = N(x \wedge y)$, $Nx \wedge Ny = N(x \vee y)$ for all $x, y \in X$,
- (c) $Nx * Ny = y * x$ for all $x, y \in X$.

THEOREM 1.5.15.

Any bounded commutative BCK-algebra X with respect to the BCK-order \leq is a lattice.

Proof.

Since $Nx \wedge Ny \leq Nx, Ny$, from Theorem (1.1.11(a)) we have

$$x = NNx \leq N(Nx \wedge Ny) = x \vee y \text{ and}$$

$$y = NNy \leq N(Nx \wedge Ny) = x \vee y.$$

This shows that $x \vee y$ is a common upper bound of x and y .

Next, if $x, y \leq z$, then $Nz \leq Nx, Ny$. By Theorem (1.5.9) we obtain

$Nz \leq Nx \wedge Ny$, $N(Nx \wedge Ny) \leq Nz$ and $x \vee y \leq z$.

Hence $x \vee y$ is a least upper bound of x and y . Therefore $(X; \leq)$ is an upper semilattice, and so a lattice in view of Theorem (1.5.9) . ■

It is clear that for a bounded commutative BCK-algebra, the operations \vee and \wedge satisfy commutative laws, associative laws, idempotent laws and absorption laws .

THEOREM 1.5.16.

Suppose $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded commutative BCK-algebra. If there exists a complement of each element of X , then it is unique.

Proof.

Suppose y and y' are complements of x , namely $x \wedge y = x \wedge y' = 0$ and $x \vee y = x \vee y' = 1$. Then

$0 = x \wedge y = y * (y * x)$. Hence $y \leq y * x \leq y$, which implies $y = y * x$. Similarly $y' = y' * x$. Thus

$y * y' = (y * x) * (y' * x) = (Nx * Ny) * (Nx * Ny')$ [by Theorem (1.5.14(c))]

$= (Nx * (Nx * Ny')) * Ny$ [by Theorem (1.1.12)]

$= (Ny' \wedge Nx) * Ny = N(x \vee y') * Ny$ [by Theorem (1.5.14(b))]

$= NNy * (x \vee y')$ [by Theorem (1.1.12)]

$= y * (x \vee y')$ [by Theorem (1.5.14(a))] $= y * 1 = 0$.

Likewise we have $y' * y = 0$. By BCI-4 we have $y = y'$, which says that complements of x are unique. ■

We should note that for a bounded commutative BCK-algebra element need not have any complement.

EXAMPLE 1.5.17.

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d, 1\}$ in which $*$ is given by:

*	0	a	b	c	d	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0

a	a	0	a	a	0	0
b	b	b	0	0	0	0
c	c	c	b	0	b	0
d	d	b	a	a	0	0
1	1	c	d	a	b	0

Then $(X ; * , 0)$ is a bounded commutative BCK-algebra with unit 1. The element b have no any complement.

THEOREM 1.5.18.

In a bounded commutative BCK-algebra the following conditions are equivalent:

- (a) $x = x * (y * x)$,
- (b) $x * y = (x * y) * y$,
- (c) $(x * z) * (y * z) = (x * y) * z$,
- (d) $x \wedge Nx = 0$
- (e) $x \vee Nx = 1$,
- (f) $x = x * Nx$,
- (g) $Nx = Nx * x$,
- (h) $x * (x * Ny) = x * y$, i.e., $Ny \wedge x = x * y$,
- (i) $x * (x * y) = x * Ny$, i.e., $y \wedge x = x * Ny$,
- (j) $(x * (y * z)) * (x * y) \leq x * Nz$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Substituting $x * y$ for x in (a) and noticing $y = y * (x * y)$ we obtain

$$x * y = (x * y) * (y * (x * y)) = (x * y) * y.$$

(b) holds.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). See Theorem (1.4.2).

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Suppose(c) holds. Then

$$x \wedge Nx = Nx \wedge x = x * (x * Nx) = NNx * (x * Nx) = (1 * Nx) * (x * Nx) = (1 * x) * Nx = Nx * Nx = 0.$$

(d) holds.

(d) \Rightarrow (e) . $x \vee Nx = NN(x \vee Nx) = N(Nx \wedge NNx) = N0 = 1$. Thus (e) is true.

(e) \Rightarrow (f). Since $x * (x * Nx) = x \wedge Nx = NN(x \wedge Nx) = N(Nx \vee NNx) = N1 = 0$,

it follows $x \leq x * Nx$. The inverse inequality is clear. Hence $x = x * Nx$, which is(f).

(f) \Rightarrow (g). Replacing x by Nx in(f) we have $Nx = Nx * NNx = Nx * z$,

(g) holds.

(g) \Rightarrow (h) $Ny = Ny * y$ follows from(g). Hence $x * (x * Ny) = Ny * (Ny * x) = (Ny * y) * (Ny * x) \leq x * y$.

Noticing $x \leq 1$, we get $x * Ny \leq 1 * Ny = NNy = y$.So $x * y \leq x * (x * Ny)$. Thus $x * y = x * (x * Ny)$, proving(h).

(h) \Rightarrow (i). Substituting Ny for y in(h) we obtain

$$x * (x * y) = x * (x * NNy) = x * Ny, \text{ which is (i).}$$

(i) \Rightarrow (j). Since $(x * (y * z)) * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (y * z) = (x * Ny) * (y * z)$ [by(i)]

$$= (x * Ny) * (Nz * Ny) \leq x * Nz, \text{ (j) holds.}$$

(j) \Rightarrow (a). Noticing $y * x \leq 1 * x = Nx$, and $x * Nx \leq x * (y * x)$.

If(j) holds, then $x = (x * 0) * 0 = (x * (x * x)) * (x * x) \leq x * Nx \leq x * (y * x)$, and so $x \leq x * (y * x)$. The inverse inequality holds for any BCK-algebra Therefore, $x = x * (y * x)$.(a) holds. This completes the proof of the theorem. ■

The equivalence of (a), (b) and(c) does not require to be bounded for X (see the next section)

REMARK 1.5.19.

(d) and(e) show that x and Nx are complements. From the above theorem we know that for a bounded commutative BCK-algebra, in order that the complement of each x is Nx, X must satisfy the condition(a) such algebras will be called implicative(see the next section).

It is an interesting question whether an algebra can be defined by a set of identities. H. Yutani and M. Palasinski and B. Wozniakowska, W. H. Cornish and P. M. Idziak studied this aspect. Next we present a result due to H. Yutani .

THEOREM 1.5.20.

An algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra if and only if it satisfies the following

- (a) $x*(x*y) = y*(y*x)$,
- (b) $(x*y)*z = (x*z)*y$,
- (c) $x*x = 0$,
- (d) $x*0 = x$.

Proof.

It suffices to verify the part "if". Using the first three conditions we obtain

$(x*(x*y))*y = (x*y)*(x*y) = 0$, which is BCI-2. If $x*y = y*x = 0$ then by (a) and (d), $x = x*0 = x*(x*y) = y*(y*x) = y*0 = y$, namely, BCI-4 holds.

(a) and (b) give $(x*y)*(x*z) = (x*(x*z))*y = (z*(z*x))*y = (z*y)*(z*x)$,

hence

(1) $(x*y)*(x*z) = (z*y)*(z*x)$.

In the above equality let $x=y$ and $z=0$, then by (c) we obtain $0*x = (x*x)*(x*0) = (0*x)*(0*x) = 0$,

BCK-5 follows. By (1), (d) and BCK-5 we have $((x*y)*(x*z))*(z*y) = ((z*y)*(z*x))*(z*y)*0$

$= (0*(z*x))*(0*(z*y)) = 0*0 = 0$, which is BCI-1. Putting the above results together we have proved that $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra. ■

CHAPTER ONE**SECTION SIX**

1.6. Implicative BCK-algebras

DEFINITION 1.6.1.

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called implicative if for all $x, y \in X, x = x*(y*x)$.

EXAMPLE 1.6.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1\}$ in which $*$ is given by putting $1*0 = 1$ and $0*0 = 0, 1*1 = 0$.

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an implicative BCK-algebra. For convenience of further discussions this algebra is denoted by $\mathcal{2}$.

The example (1.1.9) in the previous section is not implicative as

$d*(c*d) = d*b = a \neq d$. The example (1.1.21) is an implicative BCK-algebra.

The next theorem exhibits the relationship among implicativity, commutativity and positive implicativity.

THEOREM 1.6.3.

A BCK-algebra is implicative if and only if it is both commutative and positive implicative.

Proof.

Suppose X is implicative. Then $x*y = (x*y)*(y*(x*y)) = (x*y)*y$.

Hence X is positive implicative. By implicativity and BCK-1', the following hold

$$x*(x*y) = (x*(y*x))*(x*y) \leq y*(y*x).$$

Therefore X is commutative. The necessity follows. For the sufficiency we note that

$$\begin{aligned} x*(x*(y*x)) &= (y*x)*((y*x)*x) \text{ [by commutativity]} \\ &= ((y*x)*x) * ((y*x)*x) \text{ [by positive implicativity]} \\ &= 0. \text{ [by BCI-3]} \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, $(x*(y*x))*x = 0$ by Theorem (1.1.12 (d)). By BCI-4, $x = x*(y*x)$. Therefore X is implicative. The proof is complete. ■

In view of the above theorem, for a bounded implicative BCK-algebra, (b) - (j) in Theorem (1.5.18) hold .

LEMMA 1.6.4.

In a bounded implicative BCK-algebra X, the following hold:

(a) $x \vee y = y \vee x = N(Nx * y) = N(Ny * x)$,

(b) $(x \vee y) * x \leq y$,

(c) $x * y \leq z$ implies $x \leq y \vee z$, i.e., $(x * y) * z = 0$ implies $x * (y \vee z) = 0$.

Proof.

By Theorem (1.5.18(i)), $x \vee y = N(Nx \wedge Ny) = N(Nx * NNy) = N(Nx * y) = N(Ny * x)$,

which is (a). By (a) we obtain $(x \vee y) * x = N(Nx * y) * x = Nx * (Nx * y) \leq y$,

so (b) holds. If $x * y \leq z$, by (a), we have $x * (y \vee z) = x * N(Ny * z) = NNx * N(Ny * z) = NN(Ny * z) * Nx$

$= (Ny * z) * Nx = (NNx * y) * z = (x * y) * z = 0$, that is, $x \leq y \vee z$. (c) follows. The proof is complete. ■

THEOREM 1.6.5.

A bounded implicative BCK-algebra X is distributive lattice and each element of X have a unique complement Nx .

Proof.

By Theorem (1.5.18(e) and (f)), for each x in X , Nx is a complement of X. Then, by Theorem (1.5.17) we know that each x of X have a unique complement. In order to prove the remainder, we observe

$$((x \vee y) \wedge z) * (x \wedge z) = ((x \vee y) * Nz) * (x * Nz) \text{ [by Theorem (1.5.18(i))]}$$

$$= ((x \vee y) * x) * Nz \text{ [by positive implicativity]}$$

$$\leq y * Nz \text{ [by Lemma (1.6.4(b))]}$$

$$= y \wedge z \text{ . [by Theorem (1.5.18(i))]}$$

Consequently, $(x \vee y) \wedge z \leq (x \wedge z) \vee (y \wedge z)$ by Lemma (1.6.3(c)). The inverse inequality is trivial. Thus we get $(x \vee y) \wedge z = (x \wedge z) \vee (y \wedge z)$.

This shows that $(X ; \vee, \wedge)$ is a distributive lattice by means of Theorem (1.5.16). This completes the proof. ■

As is well-known, a complemented distributive lattice is a Boolean algebra. Hence the above theorem may be reformulated as follows.

THEOREM 1.6.6.

Any bounded implicative BCK-algebra is a Boolean algebra.

THEOREM 1.6.7.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a nontrivial BCK-algebra. Then the Iséki's extension of it is not implicative.

Proof.

Assume $x \in X$ and $x \neq 0$. Then $x*(1*x) = x*1 = 0 \neq x$, completing the proof. ■

Finally, we give some equivalent conditions of implicativity.

THEOREM 1.6.8.

Suppose $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Then the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is implicative,
- (b) $y*(y*x) = (x*(x*y))*(x*y)$,
- (c) $y*(y*x) = (x*(x*y))*(y*x)$,
- (d) $(x*(x*y))*(x*y) = (y*(y*x))*(y*x)$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Assume (a). Then X is both positive implicative and commutative. Hence by positive implicativity we have $(x*(x*y))*(x*y) = x*(x*y)$. By commutativity the following holds

$x*(x*y) = y*(y*x)$. Combining the above results (b) follows.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). From (b) it follows that $y*(y*x) = (x*(x*y))*(x*y) \leq x*(x*y)$,

so $x*(x*y) = y*(y*x)$. Again applying (b) we obtain

$x*(x*y) = y*(y*x) = (x*(x*y))*(x*y) = (y*(y*x))*(x*y)$, Which is (c).

(c) \Rightarrow (d) By the similar to (b) \Rightarrow (c) we obtain $x*(x*y) = y*(y*x)$.

Thus $(x*(x*y))*(x*y) = (y*(y*x))*(x*y) = x*(x*y) = y*(y*x)$

$= (x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = (y * (y * x)) * (y * x)$, and hence (d) holds.

(d) \Rightarrow (a). Replacing y by $x * y$ in (d) we obtain

$$x * y = ((x * y) * 0) * 0 = ((x * y) * ((x * y) * x)) * ((x * y) * x) = (x * (x * (x * y))) * (x * (x * y)) = (x * y) * (x * (x * y))$$

$= (x * (x * (x * y))) * y = (x * y) * y$. This says that X is positive implicative. Combining (d) we have

$$x * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y) = (y * (y * x)) * (y * x) = y * (y * x),$$

that is, X is also commutative. By virtue of Theorem (1.6.3), X is implicative and (a) holds. The proof is complete. ■

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION SEVEN

1.7. BCK-algebras with condition(S)

BCK-algebras with condition(S) were introduced by K. Iséki and studied extensively by several authors.

DEFINITION 1.7.1.

Given a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and given elements of X , we define

$A(a,b) = \{ x \in X : x * a \leq b \}$.piously, $0, a$ and b are in $A(a, b)$. If, for all x, y in X , $A(x,y)$ has a test element, written $x \circ y$, then the BCK-algebra is called to be with condition(S) .

From the definition it is easy to see that $a \leq a \circ b, b \leq a \circ b$ and $a \circ 0 = 0 \circ a = a$.

EXAMPLE 1.7.2.

Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$, $*$ be given by the table .

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X ; *, 0)$ is BCK-algebra with condition(S), but it is neither positive implicative nor commutative.

EXAMPLE 1.7.3.

Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ in which $*$ is defined as follows :

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X, *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra with condition(S). We should note that this BCK-algebra is positive implicative, but not commutative.

EXAMPLE 1.7.4.

Let $X = \{ 0,1, 2, 3 \}$ and the operation $*$ is as follows :

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra, but not with condition (S), in fact,

$A(1,3) = \{0, 1, 3\}$ has no any greatest element.

LEMMA 1.7.5.

Suppose a, b are any fixed elements of a BCK-algebra. If $a \circ b$ exists then so $b \circ a$, and $a \circ b = b \circ a$.

Proof.

Since $x * a \leq b$ is equivalent to $x * b \leq a$, therefore $A(a, b) = A(b, a)$, which implies the assertion of the lemma. ■

LEMMA 1.7.6.

If X is a BCK- algebra with condition (S) and $a, b, c \in X$, then $(a \circ b) \circ c = a \circ (b \circ c)$.

Proof.

By the definition of the operation \circ we have $((a \circ b) \circ c) * c \leq a \circ b$ and so

$$(((a \circ b) \circ c) * b) * c = (((a \circ b) \circ c) * c) * b \leq (a \circ b) * b \leq a.$$

Hence $((a \circ b) \circ c) * b \leq a \circ c$, and $(a \circ b) \circ c \leq (a \circ c) \circ b$.

symmetry we have the inverse inequality. Thus $(a \circ b) \circ c = (a \circ c) \circ b$. Cabling Lemma (1.7.5) we have $(a \circ b) \circ c = (b \circ a) \circ c = (b \circ c) \circ a = a \circ (b \circ c)$. proof is complete. ■

DEFINITION 1.7.7.

By a semigroup (S, \cdot) we will mean a nonempty set which a binary operation \cdot is defined and satisfies for a, b, c in S , $(a \cdot b) \cdot c = a \cdot (b \cdot c)$.

Using the notion of semigroups, the above results may be reformulated follows

THEOREM 1.7.8.

A BCK-algebra X with condition(S) is a semigroup respect to the operation \circ and 0 is zero element.

COROLLARY 1.7.9.

If X is a bounded BCK-algebra, then for all $x \in X$, the following hold $x \circ 1 = 1 \circ x = 1$ and $x \circ Nx = 1$.

Proof.

Since $u * x \leq 1$ for all u in X , $x \circ 1 = 1$. And $u * x \leq 1 * x$ implies $x \circ (1 * x) = 1$, that is to say $x \circ Nx = 1$. This completes the proof. ■

THEOREM 1.7.9.

A BCK-algebra X with condition(S) is a commutative ordered semigroup with zero 0.

Proof.

By virtue of Theorem (1.7.8), it suffices to show that the operation \circ is order preserving relative to the BCK-ordering \leq . To do this we suppose $x \leq y$, then $(x \circ z) * y \leq (x \circ z) * x \leq z$, so $x \circ z \leq y \circ z$. This finishes the proof. ■

THEOREM 1.7.10.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra with condition(S) Then

- (a) $(x * y) * z = x * (y \circ z)$,
- (b) $x * y \leq (x * z) \circ (z * y)$,
- (c) $(x \circ z) * (y \circ z) \leq x * y \leq x \circ y$

Note that :

the condition(a) is equivalent to the condition(S) in certain sense .

THEOREM 1.7.11.

Suppose $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. If there is a binary operation \vee such that for all x, y, z in X ,

- (a) $(x * y) * z = x * (y \vee z)$, then X is with condition(S) and \vee is exactly the operation \circ .

THEOREM 1.7.12.

Let X be a BCK-algebra with condition(S). Then the least element x satisfying $a \leq b \circ x$ for given $a, b \in X$ is $a * b$.

THEOREM 1.7.13.

Any non-trivial BCK-algebra X with condition(S) is never a group on \circ .

Proof.

Let a' be the inverse of $a (\neq 0)$ in X . Then $a \circ a' = 0$ and $0 \neq a \leq a \circ a' = 0$, a contradiction. Hence X is not a group on \circ . The proof is complete.

In the following we will discuss positive implicative (resp. commutative, implicative) BCK-algebra with condition(S).

THEOREM 1.7.14.

Let X be a BCK-algebra with condition(S). Then the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is positive implicative,
- (b) $x \leq y$ implies $x \circ y = y$,
- (c) $x \circ x = x$,
- (d) $(x \circ y) * z = (x * z) \circ (y * z)$,
- (e) $x \circ y = \text{lub} \{ x, y \}$
- (f) $x \circ y = x \circ (y * x)$.

THEOREM 1.7.15.

Suppose X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra with condition(S) and bounded. Then each element a of X has a right implement Na , that is, $a \circ Na = 1$ and $a \wedge Na = 0$.

Proof

From $b \leq 1$ it follows that $b * a \leq 1 * a = Na$,

so $b \leq a \circ Na$. If we assume $b = 1$, then $1 \leq a \circ Na$. The inverse inequality is obvious, and so $a \circ Na = 1$. On the other hand, by positive implicative of X we have

$$a \wedge Na = Na * (Na * a) = Na * ((1 * a) * a) = Na * (1 * a) = Na * Na = 0.$$

This finishes the proof. ■

THEOREM 1.7.16.

Suppose X is positive implicative BCK-algebra with condition(S) and bounded. Then the involutory subalgebra $S(X)$ is also with condition(S) .

THEOREM 1.7.17.

Let X be a nonempty set, $*$ and \circ two binary operations and let 0 be a constant. Then the algebra $(X; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra with condition(S) on \circ if and only if it satisfies the following

- (a) $(x*y) * z = x* (y \circ z)$,
- (b) $x \circ y = y \circ x$,
- (c) $x * 0 = x$,
- (d) $x * (x * y) = y* (y* x)$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) is clear.

(\Leftarrow) By(a) and(b), we have $(x*y) * z = x*(y \circ z) = x*(z \circ y) = (x*z)*y$.

In view of Theorem (1.5.20), X is a commutative BCK-algebra. By Theorem (1.7.11) , X is also with condition(S) on \circ . This completes the proof . ■

THEOREM 1.7.17.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a bounded commutative BCK-algebra. Then X is with condition(S) and

$a \circ b = N(Na * b)$ for any a, b in X .

Consequently we combine this result theorem (1.7.17) to obtain the following.

THEOREM 1.7.18.

Any bounded implicative BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is condition(S) and

$x \circ y = x \vee y$ for any x, y in X .

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0

1	1	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

X is a bounded commutative BCK-algebra, and $2=N(N1*2)=3*((3*1)*2)=3*(2*2)=3$,

$2=2$. Hence $1 \circ 2 \neq 1 \vee 2$.

THEOREM 1.7.19.

If $(X; *, 0)$ is an implicative BCK-algebra with condition (S), then

- (a) (X, \circ) is an upper semilattice with the least element 0,
- (b) (X, \wedge) is a lower semilattice,
- (c) $c^* (a \circ b) = (c^* a) \circ (c^* b)$,
- (d) $c^* (a \circ b) = (c^* a) \wedge (c^* b)$,
- (e) $(a \circ b) \wedge c = (a \wedge c) \circ (b \wedge c)$.

This theorem says that an implicative BCK-algebra with condition (S) is a generalized Boolean algebra.

DEFINITION 1.7.20.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. It is said to be complete if every nonempty subset of X has a supremum and an infimum belonging to X . A subalgebra of X is said to be complete if every nonempty subset of the subalgebra has a supremum and an infimum

THEOREM 1.7.21.

Any locally complete BCK-algebra is with condition (S).

CHAPTER TWO

SECTION ONE

2.1. The union of two BCK-algebras

DEFINITION 2.1.1.

Let $(X_1; *_1, 0)$ and $(X_2; *_2, 0)$ be two BCK-algebras and $X_1 \cap X_2 = \{0\}$.

Suppose $X = X_1 \cup X_2$, define $*$ on X as

THEOREM 2.1.2.

The union $X = X_1 \oplus X_2$ with $|X_1| \geq 2$ and $|X_2| \geq 2$ does not satisfy the condition (S).

Proof.

Suppose a and b are non-zero elements in X and $a \in X_1, b \in X_2$. Then $a, b \in A(a, b)$, but there is no non-zero c such that $a \leq c$ and $b \leq c$. This means that X does not satisfy the condition (S). The proof is complete. ■

Likewise, for an indexed family of BCK-algebras $\{X_i : i \in I\}$ we may define the union algebra $X = \bigoplus \{X_i : i \in I\}$, and the previous facts also hold.

LEMMA 2.1.3.

Let x and y be any elements of a BCK-algebra X . If $A(x) \cap A(y) = \{0\}$, then

$x * y \neq x$ and $y * x = x$ and $y * x = y$.

Proof.

Note that $x * (x * y) \leq x, y$ hold in X . Hence $x * (x * y) \in A(x) \cap A(y)$,

which implies $x * (x * y) = 0$, i.e., $x \leq x * y$.

The inverse inequality is clear, and so $x = x * y$.

By the same way we obtain $y * x = y$ proving the lemma. ■

THEOREM 2.1.4.

In the union $\bigoplus \{X_i : i \in I\}$, $x \in X_i$ implies $A(x) \subseteq X_i$.

THEOREM 2.1.5.

Let $\{S_i : i \in I\}$ be an indexed family of subsets of BCK-algebra X satisfying the following conditions:

- (a) $X = \bigcup_{i \in I} S_i$,
- (b) $S_i \cap S_j = \{0\}$ for any distinct i and j ,
- (c) $x \in S_i$ implies $A(x) \subseteq S_i$ for any $i \in I$,

Then all S_i are subalgebras of X and X is the union of all BCK-algebras $S_i (i \in I)$.

Proof.

Since $x * y \leq x$, it follows that $x * y \in A(x)$, which means that for any $x, y \in S_i$, $x * y \in A(x) \subseteq S_i$. Hence S_i is a subalgebra of X . The conditions (b) and (c) are clearly equivalent to the one that $x \in S_i$, $y \in S_j$ and $i \neq j$ imply $A(x) \cap A(y) = \{0\}$. Consequently, by Lemma (2.1.5), $x \in S_i$ and $y \in S_j$, for distinct i and j imply $x * y = x$ and $y * x = y$. Hence X is the union of all BCK-algebras $S_i (i \in I)$. This finishes the proof. ■

CHAPTER TWO

SECTION TWO

2.2. Direct product of BCK-algebras

THEOREM 2.2.1.

Let $(X_i; *, 0_i)$ ($i \in I$) be an indexed family of BCK-algebras and let $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ be the set of all mappings $f: I \rightarrow \cup \{X_i; i \in I\}$, and $f(i) \in X_i$ for all $i \in I$.

For $f, g \in \prod_{i \in I} X_i$, we define by $f * g$ by $(f * g)(i) = f(i) * g(i)$ for every $i \in I$ and 0 by $0(i) = 0_i$. Then $(\prod_{i \in I} X_i; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, which is called the direct product X_i ($i \in I$).

THEOREM 2.2.2.

Let $(X_i; *, 0_i)$ be an indexed family of BCK-algebras. Then we have the following :

- (a) $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ is bounded if and only if every X_i is bounded
- (b) $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ is commutative if and only if every X_i is commutative
- (c) $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ is positive implicative if and only if every X_i is positive implicative,
- (d) $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ is implicative if and only if every X_i is implicative,
- (e) $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ is with condition(S) if and only if every X_i is with condition(S) .

Proof.

we only prove (e). The remainder is left to the reader as an exercise.

Let every X_i ($i \in I$) be with condition(s). For any $f, g \in \prod_{i \in I} X_i$, we define $f \circ g$ such that

$(f \circ g)(i) = f(i) \circ g(i)$ for all $i \in I$.

For $h \in \prod_{i \in I} X_i$, if $h * f \leq g$, then $h(i) * f(i) = (h * f)(i) \leq g(i)$ for all $i \in I$.

From this it follows that $h(i) \leq f(i) \circ g(i)$. This says that $h * f \leq g$ implies $h \leq f \circ g$. his Moreover, for $i \in I$ we have

$$((f \circ g) * f)(i) = (f \circ g)(i) * f(i) = (f(i) \circ g(i)) * f(i) \leq g(i) .$$

This shows $(f \circ g) * f \leq g$. Hence $f \circ g$ is the element of $A(f, g)$.

Consequently, $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ is with condition (S).

Conversely, suppose $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ is with condition (s). For any $x_i, y_i \in X_i$, take $f, g \in \prod_{i \in I} X_i$ such that

$$g(j) = \begin{cases} y_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0_j & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases} \quad f(j) = \begin{cases} x_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0_j & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases}$$

Then $(f \circ g)(i) = x_i \circ y_i$. In fact, since $(f \circ g) * f \leq g$,

$$(f \circ g)(i) * x_i = (f \circ g)(i) * f(i) = ((f \circ g) * f)(i) \leq g(i) = y_i.$$

On the other hand, if $z_i * x_i \leq y_i$ and h is such that $h(j) = \begin{cases} z_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0_j & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases}$

$$\text{Then } (h * f)(j) = \begin{cases} z_i * x_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0_j & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases}$$

Hence $h * f \leq g$, and $h \leq f \circ g$. In particular, $z(i) = h(i) \leq (f \circ g)(i)$.

This shows that $z_i * x_i \leq y_i$ implies $z_i \leq (f \circ g)(i)$.

Therefore, $(f \circ g)(i) = x_i \circ y_i$. This finishes the proof. ■

In the following we discuss the close relationship between union algebras and direct products.

DEFINITION 2.2.3.

If $(X_1; *_{1}, 0_1)$ and $(X_2; *_{2}, 0_2)$ are any two BCK-algebras, then we call the mapping $f: X_1 \rightarrow X_2$ to be a homomorphism whenever for any x, y in X_1 we have

$$f(x *_{1} y) = f(x) *_{2} f(y).$$

If f is also onto, then f is said to be an epimorphism.

If a homomorphism f is both onto and one to one, then we call it to be an isomorphism in this case, we say X_1 is isomorphic to X_2 , written $X_1 \cong X_2$.

obviously, an isomorphic relation is an equivalent one.

Given a nonempty indexed family $\{X_i : i \in I\}$, we consider the direct product $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$. For any fixed $i \in I$, assume $a_i \in \prod_{i \in I} X_i$ such that

$$a_i(j) = \begin{cases} a \in X_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0_i & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases}$$

Then $\tilde{X}_i = \{ a_i: a \in X_i \}$ is a subalgebra of $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ and isomorphic to X_i . If $i \neq j$, then $a_i * a_j = a_i$ and

$\tilde{X}_i \cap \tilde{X}_j = \{0\}$. Hence $\cup_{i \in I} \tilde{X}_i = \bigoplus_{i \in I} \tilde{X}_i$. So $\cup_{i \in I} X_i$ is a subalgebra of $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$, and for any projection map p_j we have $p_j(\cup_{i \in I} \tilde{X}_i) = X_j$. Since $\cup_{i \in I} \tilde{X}_i$ is isomorphic to $\bigoplus_{i \in I} X_i$. ■

We have proved the following

THEOREM 2.2.4.

$\bigoplus_{i \in I} X_i$ is a subalgebra of $\prod_{i \in I} X_i$ up to isomorphism.

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CHAPTER THREE

SECTION ONE

3.1. Introduction of ideals and quotient to BCK-algebras

The notion of ideals in BCK-algebras was introduced by K. Iséki in 1975. The ideal theory plays a fundamental role for the general development of BCK-algebras. The concepts of ideals, quotient algebras, and homomorphisms are all closely related. These will be the subject of this and next chapters.

DEFINITION 3.1.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let I be a nonempty subset of X . Then I is called to be an ideal of X if, for all x, y in X ,

(i) $0 \in I$,

(ii) $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$.

$\{0\}$ and X are two ideals of X . We will call X a trivial ideal. An ideal I is proper if $I \neq X$.

EXAMPLE 3.1.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1
2	2	2	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an implicative BCK-algebra, and $\{0\}$, X , $\{0, 1\}$, $\{0, 2\}$ are all ideals of X .

EXAMPLE 3.1.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra, it has only two ideals $\{0\}$ and X .

commutative BCK-algebra, it has only two

EXAMPLE 3.1.3. Let X be any BCK-algebra and let \bar{X} be the Iséki's extension of X . Then X is an ideal of \bar{X} .

THEOREM 3.1.4. Suppose I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra X and $x \in I$. If $y \leq x$ then $y \in I$.

Proof. $y \leq x$ implies $y * x = 0 \in I$. Combining $x \in I$ and using (ii) we obtain $y \in I$, proving the theorem. ■

Next we give an equivalent condition of ideals.

THEOREM 3.1.5. Suppose I is a nonempty subset of a BCK-algebra X . Then I is an ideal of X if and only if, for any x, y in I , $A(x, y) \subseteq I$.

Proof. Let I be an ideal and let $x \in I$ and $y \in I$. If $z \in A(x, y)$,

then $z * x \leq y$. By Theorem (3.1.4) we have $z * x \in I$. Using (ii) we obtain $z \in I$, that is to say $A(x, y) \subseteq I$.

Conversely, suppose $A(x, y) \subseteq I$ for all x, y in I . Since I is a nonempty subset of X , we assume $x \in I$. By BCK-5, $0 * x \leq x$, and so $0 \in A(x, x) \subseteq I$, (i) holds for I . Let $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. By BCI-2, $x * (x * y) \leq y$, This says that $x \in A(x * y, y) \subseteq I$, and so (ii) holds for I . Hence I is an ideal of X . This completes the proof. ■

It is clear that the above theorem is equivalent to the following

COROLLARY 3.1.6. I is an ideal of X if and only if, for all x, y in I , $(z * x) * y = 0$ implies $z \in I$

So far we have looked at some means constructing new algebras from the old algebras, for instance, sub algebras, union algebras, and direct.

$x \in C_0$. Conversely, let $x \in C_0$, then $x = x * 0 \in I$, and so $x \in I$. Hence $I = C_0$.

Denote $X/I = \{ C_x : x \in X \}$ and define that $C_x * C_y = C_{x * y}$. Since \sim is a congruence relation on X , the operation $*$ is well-defined. In what follows, we will prove that $(X/I ; * , C_0)$ is a BCK-algebra.

If $C_x * C_y = C_0$, then we define $C_x \leq C_y$. Since $C_0 * C_x = C_{0 * x} = C_0$, we obtain $C_0 \leq C_x$ for all x in X . Let $C_x * C_y = C_y * C_x = C_0$, then $x * y \sim 0$ and $y * x \sim 0$. If $u \in C_x$, then $x \sim u$, and so $u * y \sim x * y \sim 0$, which shows $u \in C_y$.

Hence $C_x \subseteq C_y$. Similarly, we have $C_y \subseteq C_x$. This $C_x = C_y$. $C_x * C_x = C_{x * x} = C_0$ implies $C_x \leq C_x$. Therefore BCI-3, BCI-4 and BCK-5 hold in X/I . If $x \leq y$, we have $x * y = 0$ and $C_x * C_y = C_{x * y} = C_0$. Hence $x \leq y$ implies $C_x \leq C_y$. By this

$$(C_x * C_y) * (C_x * C_z) = C_{x * y} * C_{x * z} = C_{(x * y) * (x * z)} \leq C_{z * y} = C_z * C_y$$

which is BCI-1. Since $C_x * (C_x * C_y) = C_{x * (x * y)} \leq C_y$,

BCI-2 holds. Hence X/I is a BCK-algebra. ■

THEOREM 3.1.6. Let $(X ; * , 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let I be an ideal of it. Then $(X/I ; * , C_0)$ is also a BCK-algebra, which is called to be the quotient algebra via I , and $C_0 = I$.

There is a close relation between the ideals of X and the one of X/I .

THEOREM 3.1.7 Any ideal of a BCK-algebra X is a sub algebra of X .

Proof. Suppose I is an ideal of X and $x, y \in I$. Since $x * y \leq x$, it follows from Theorem (3.1.4) that $x * y \in I$. Hence I is a sub algebra of X . The proof is complete. ■

THEOREM 3.1.8. If I and J are any ideals of X and $I \subset J$, then

(a) I is also an ideal of the sub algebra,

(b) I/J as the quotient of the sub algebra J via the ideal I is an ideal of X/I .

Proof. (a) is immediate from Definition 1.1. In order to prove (b), first we have to show that each element of J/I is also an element of X/I . To avoid the ambiguity, we denote the element of J/I

containing x by $C_x(J)$. Suppose $y \in X$ and $x \in J$. If $x \sim y$ with respect to I , then $y * x \in I$ and so $y * x \in J$ and $x \in I$. By Definition (3.1.1(ii)) we have $y \in J$, this says $C_x(J) \in X/I$ or each element of J/I is also an element of X/I .

Next we prove that J/I is an ideal of X/I . Since $I \subseteq J$, $C_0 = I \in J/I$. If $C_x * C_y \in J/I$ and $C_y \in J/I$, then $C_x * y \in J/I$. It follows that $x * y \in J$ and $y \in J$. By Definition (3.1.1(ii)) we obtain $x \in J$, and so $C_x \in J/I$. This means that J/I is an ideal of X/I . This finishes the proof. ■

THEOREM 3.1.9. If J^* is ideal of X/I , then $J = \{ C_x : C_x \in J^* \}$ is an ideal of X and $I \subseteq J$.

Proof. Since $I = C_0 \in J^*$, $0 \in J$ and $I \subseteq J$. Let $x * y \in J$ and $y \in J$, then $C_x * C_y = C_{x * y} \in J^*$ and $C_y \in J^*$. By Definition 1.1(ii), we have $C_x \in J^*$ and $x \in J$. This shows that J is an ideal of X , proving the theorem. ■

The set of all ideals on X is denoted by $I(X)$, the set of all ideals containing I on X is denoted by $I(X, I)$. The mapping f from $I(X, I)$ to (X/I) is defined by, for any $J \in I(X, I)$, $f(J) = J/I$. The above Lemmas (3.1.8) and (3.1.9) say that f is onto. We can also prove that f is one- to-one.

In fact, let $A, B \in I(X, I)$ and $A \neq B$. Without loss of any generality, we may suppose that there is $x \in B - A$. If $f(A) = f(B)$ then $C \in f(B)$ and $C_x \in f(A)$. Thus there exists $y \in A$ such that $C_x = C_y$, so $x \sim y$, that is, $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$. By means of $I \subseteq A$, we have $x * y \in A$ and $y \in A$, hence $x \in A$, which contradicts to $x \notin A$. The poof is complete. Summarizing the above facts we obtain

THEOREM 3.1.10. If I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra X , then there is a bisection from $I(X, I)$ to $I(X/I)$.

Suppose I is an ideal of X . The mapping v from X to X/I is defined by $v(x) = C_x$ for all x in X obviously $v(x * y) = v(x) * v(y)$.

This says v is a homomorphism, called to be the natural homomorphism. By means of this terminology, Theorem (3.1.9) can reformulated as follows.

THEOREM 3.1.11. If A is an ideal of a BCK-algebra X/I , then $v^{-1}(A)$ is an ideal of X and

$I \subseteq v^{-1}(A)$.

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CHAPTER THREE**SECTION TWO****3.2.Positive implicative ideals of BCK-algebras**

In 1975, K. Iséki[3] introduced the notion of positive implicative ideals (K. Iséki calls it to be implicative ideals) .

DEFINITION 3.2.1. Given a BCK-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$, a nonempty subset I of X is said to be a positive implicative ideal if it satisfies, for all x, y, z in X ,

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y * z \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

Obviously, X is always a positive implicative ideal of X .

EXAMPLE 3.2.2. Let $X = \{ 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 \}$ in which $*$ is given by

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
2	2	2	0	2	0
3	3	1	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. $\{0,1,3\}$ and $\{0,1,2,3\}$ are positive implicative ideals of X . $\{0\}$, $\{0,2\}$ and $\{0,2,4\}$ are ideals of X , but not positive implicative.

THEOREM 3.2.2. Any positive implicative ideal must be an ideal, but the inverse is not true.

Proof. Suppose I is a positive implicative ideal. If $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$, then $(x * y) * 0 \in I$ and $y * 0 \in I$. By (ii) we have $x = x * 0 \in I$, hence I is an ideal. In the example 1, $\{0,2\}$ is an ideal, but not positive implicative as $(3 * 2) * 0 \in \{0,2\}$, $2 * 0 = 2 \in \{0,2\}$ and $3 * 0 = 3 \notin \{0,2\}$. This shows that an ideal need not be positive implicative. ■

In the following, we give a number of equivalent conditions of positive implicative ideals needed for further discussion.

THEOREM 3.2.3. If we are given an ideal I of a BCK-algebra X , then I is positive implicative if and only if for any $a \in X$, the set $A_a = \{x \in X : x * a \in I\}$ is an ideal of X .

Proof. (\Rightarrow). Suppose that I is positive implicative and $x * y \in A_a$ and $y \in A_a$. Then $(x * y) * a \in I$ and $y * a \in I$. By (ii) we obtain $x * a \in I$ i.e., $x \in A_a$. This says A_a is an ideal.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that for any a in X , A_a is an ideal of X . If $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y * z \in I$, then

$x * y \in A_z$ and $y \in A_z$. Since A_z is an ideal of X , $x \in A_z$, and so $x * z \in I$. This means that I is positive implicative. Then proof is completed. ■

If I is a positive implicative ideal, then A_a is an ideal, as well as then least ideal containing I and a . In fact, if B is any ideal containing I and a , then for all $x \in A_a$ we have $x * a \in I$. It follows that $x * a \in B$ and $a \in B$, hence $x \in B$. This shows that $A_a \subseteq B$. The assertion holds. Thus we have.

COROLLARY 3.2.4. If I is a positive implicative ideal of X then for any $a \in X$,

$A_a = \{x \in X : x * a \in I\}$ is the least ideal containing I and a .

THEOREM 3.2.5. Given a nonempty subset I of a BCK-algebra X , the following are equivalent:

(a) I is a positive implicative ideal

(b) I is an ideal, and for any x, y in X , $(x * y) * y \in I$ implies $x * y \in I$. (c) I is an ideal, and for any x, y, z in X , $(x * y) * z \in I$ implies $(x * z) * (y * z) \in I$,

(d) $0 \in I$, and $((x * y) * y) * z \in I$, imply $x * y \in I$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b). If I is a positive implicative ideal, by Theorem (3.2.2), I is an ideal. Suppose $(x * y) * y \in I$. Since $y * y = 0 \in I$, by(ii) we have $x * y \in I$. (b) holds

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Assume (b) and $(x * y) * z \in I$. Since

$$((x * (y * z)) * z) * z = ((x * z) * (y * z)) * z \leq (x * y) * z \in I,$$

it follows that $((x * (y * z)) * z) * z \in I$. By(b) we have

$$(x * z) * (y * z) = (x * (y * z)) * z \in I \text{ and so(c) holds.}$$

(c) \Rightarrow (d). It is clear that $0 \in I$. If $((x * y) * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$, then $((x * z) * y) * y \in I$. By (c) we get $(x * y) * z = ((x * z) * y) * (y * y) \in I$. Since I is an ideal and $z \in I$, $x * y \in I$ follows. (d) holds.

(d) \Rightarrow (a). First observe that if I satisfies (d) then I is an ideal of X . In fact, suppose $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$, then $((x * 0) * 0) * y \in I$ and $y \in I$.

Using (d) we obtain $x = x * 0 \in I$, i.e., I is an ideal. Next let $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y * z \in I$. As

$$((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * z) * y = (x * y) * z \in I, \text{ it follows that}$$

$((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \in I$. Combining $y * x \in I$ and using (d) we have $x * z \in I$. This have proved that I is a positive implicative ideal. The proof is completed. ■

The next theorem describe a distributive case of all positive implicative ideals in a BCK-algebra, by means of which we will obtain a nice characterization for positive implicative BCK-algebras by ideals.

THEOREM 3.2.6. Suppose I and A are ideals of a BCK-algebra X , and $I \subseteq A$. If I is positive implicative, then so is A .

Proof. Let $(x * y) * z \in A$ and denote $u = (x * y) * z$. Then

$((x * u) * y) * z = ((x * y) * z) * u = 0 \in I$. Making use of positive implicativity of I and Theorem (3.2.5(c)), we have $((x * u) * z) * (y * z) \in I, ((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z) = ((x * z) * (y * z)) * u \in I$. As $I \subset A$ we obtain $((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z) \in A$.

Combining $(x * y) * z \in A$ and A is an ideal, it follows that $(x * z) * (y * z) \in A$. This shows that for the ideal A , $(x * y) * z \in A$ implies $(x * z) * (y * z) \in A$. So A is positive implicative by Theorem (3.2.5(c)). This completes the proof. ■

COROLLARY 3.2.7 In a BCK-algebra X , the following are equivalent :

- (a) X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra
- (b) $\{0\}$ is a positive implicative ideal of X ,
- (c) All ideals of X are positive implicative,
- (d) For any a in X , $A(a) = \{x \in X : x \leq a\}$ is an ideal.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b). We have known that $\{0\}$ is an ideal of X . Assume that (a) holds. Then

$(x * y) * y = x * y$. Hence $(x * y) * y \in \{0\}$ implies $x * y \in \{0\}$. By Theorem (3.2.5(b)), $\{0\}$ is a positive implicative ideal of X , and (b) follows.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). It is immediate from Theorem (3.2.6).

(c) \Rightarrow (d). For $a \in X$ and $x * y, y \in A(a)$ we have $x * y \leq a$ and $y \leq a$. Hence $(x * y) * a = 0 \in \{0\}$. and $y * a = 0 \in \{0\}$. By (c), $\{0\}$ is a positive implicative ideal and so $x * a \in \{0\}$, i.e., $x * a = 0$. Hence $x \in A(a)$. That is to say $A(a)$ is an ideal, (d) holds.

(d) \Rightarrow (a). Suppose (d) and $(x * y) * y = 0$, then $x * y \in A(y)$. Noticing $A(y)$ is an ideal and $y \in A(y)$ we have $x \in A(y)$, i.e., $x * y = 0$. Hence we have proved that for the BCK-algebra X ,

$(x * y) * y = 0$ implies $x * y = 0$. By Theorem (1.4.5), X is positive implicative, and so (a) holds. This finishes the proof. ■

From this corollary we see that in BCK-algebras, zero ideals play important roles.

THEOREM 3.2.8. A BCK-algebra X is positive implicative if and only if for any ideal I of X and any element a of X , $A_a = \{x \in X : x * a \in I\}$ is an ideal of X .

Proof. Suppose that X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra. It follows from Corollary (3.2.7) that I is a positive implicative ideal. Since $I \subset A_a$, by Theorem (3.2.3) we know that A_a is an ideal.

Conversely, suppose that for any ideal I and any element a , A_a is an ideal of X . In order to prove that X is positive implicative, from Corollary (3.2.7) it suffices to show that any ideal A of X is

positive implicative , to do this let $(x * y) * z \in A$ and $y * z \in A$. Denote $B = \{ u : u * z \in A \}$. Thus $x * y \in B$ and $y \in B$. By the hypothesis we know that B is an ideal , and so $x \in B$, equivalently $x * z \in A$. This says A positive implicative . Therefore X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra. The proof is completed. ■

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CHAPTER THREE

SECTION THREE

3.3.Implicative ideals of BCK-algebras

In 1986, Jie Meng introduced the notion of implicative ideals and by means of such ideals implicative BCK-algebra was characterized.

DEFINITION 3.3.1. Suppose $(X; *, 0)$, is a BCK-algebra. A nonempty subset I of X is said to be an implicative ideal if it satisfies the following:

(i) $0 \in I$,

(ii) $(x * (y * x)) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$ imply $x \in I$ for all x, y, z in X .

EXAMPLE 3.3.2. Given a BCK-algebra X , the set X is always an implicative ideal of X , which is called the trivial implicative ideal.

EXAMPLE 3.3.4. Suppose X is an implicative BCK-algebra, then every ideal of X is implicative.

EXAMPLE 3.3.5 .Let $X = \{ 0,1,2,3,4 \}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, but it is neither positive implicative nor commutative . It is easy to verify that $I = \{ 0, 1, 2, 3 \}$ is an implicative ideal of X .

First we discuss the relations of ideals, implicative ideals and positive is implicative ideals.

THEOREM 3.3.2 An implicative ideal must be an ideal, but the inverse does not hold.

Proof . Let I be an implicative ideal and $x * z \in I$, $z \in I$. Putting $y = x$ in(ii) we have $(x * (x * x)) * z = x * z \in I$ and $z \in I$. By(ii) we get $x \in I$, so I is an ideal . ■

The last part is shown by the following example.

EXAMPLE 3.3.6. Suppose $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4 \}$, the operation $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
2	2	2	0	2	0
3	3	1	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. It is easy to verify that $\{0, 2\}$ is an ideal, but not implicative.

THEOREM 3.3.3. An implicative ideal must be positive implicative, but a positive implicative ideal need not be implicative.

Proof. Suppose I is an implicative ideal and $(x * y) * z \in I, y * z \in I$. Since

$$((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * z) * y = (x * y) * z \in I,$$

by Theorem (3.1.2) we get $((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \in I$.

Combining $y * z \in I$ and making use of I being an ideal, we have $(x * z) * z \in I$.

$$\text{As } (x * z) * (x * (x * z)) = (x * (x * (x * z))) * z = (x * z) * z \in I,$$

it follows that $((x * z) * (x * (x * z))) * 0 \in I$. Combining $0 \in I$ we obtain $x * z \in I$. This means that I is a positive implicative ideal.

In the example 4, $\{0, 1, 3\}$ is a positive implicative ideal but not implicative. This finishes the proof. ■

For further relations we have the following.

THEOREM 3.3.4. Suppose I is a positive implicative ideal of X . Then I is imperative if and only if for all x, y in X

(a) $y * (y * x) \in I$ implies $x * (x * y) \in I$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose I is a positive implicative ideal, and let $y * (y * x) \in I$. Since $x * (x * y) \leq x$, it follows that $x * (x * (x * y)) \leq x * (x * y) * (y * x) = (x * (y * x)) * (x * y) \leq y * (y * x)$. Since I is also an ideal by Theorem (3.2.2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & (x * (x * y)) * (y * (x * (x * y))) \leq x * (x * y) * (y * x) = (x * (y * x)) * (x * y) \\ & \leq y * (y * x). \text{ Since } I \text{ is also an ideal by Theorem (3.2.2), we obtain} \\ & ((x * (x * y)) * (y * (x * (x * y)))) * 0 \in I. \end{aligned}$$

Combining $0 \in I$ and using (ii) we have $x * (x * y) \in I$. Thus we have

proved that $y * (y * x) \in I$ implies $x * (x * y) \in I$, namely, I satisfies (a).

Sufficiency. Suppose I satisfies (a) and let $(x * (y * x)) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$. Now we prove that $x \in I$. Since I is an ideal, $x * (y * x) \in I$. Noticing that $(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \leq x * (y * x) \in I$,

We have $(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \in I$. It follows from Theorem 2.5(b) that $y * (y * x) \in I$. By (a) we obtain

$$(1) \ x * (x * y) \in I. \text{ Noticing that } (x * y) * z \leq x * y \leq x * (y * x) \in I,$$

We have $(x * y) * z \in I$. Combining $z \in I$ it follows that $x * y \in I$. From this and (1) $x \in I$ follows. Therefore I is an implicative ideal. This completes the proof. ■

THEOREM 3.3.5 An ideal I is implicative if and only if, for all x, y in X ,

$$(a) \ x * (y * x) \in I \text{ implies } x \in I.$$

Proof. Suppose I is an ideal and satisfies (a). If $(x * (y * x)) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$. By the definition of ideals we have $x * (y * x) \in I$. Then, by (a) it follows that $x \in I$. This proves that the direction.

(\Leftarrow). The Opposite direction is evident. This finishes the proof. ■

The next theorem is similar to Theorem (3.2.6).

THEOREM 3.3.6. If I is an implicative ideal of BCK-algebra X , then every ideal A containing I is implicative

Proof. By means of Theorem (3.3.3), we know that I must be a positive implicative ideal. Using Theorem (3.2.6). A is a positive implicative ideal. In the order to prove that A is implicative, it is sufficient only to verify that A satisfies the condition (a) in Theorem 3.4. To do this suppose

$$x * (x * y) \in A \text{ and denote } u = x * (x * y). \text{ Since } (x * (x * y)) * u = 0 \in I$$

and I is positive implicative, it follows from Theorem (3.2.5(c)), that

$$(x * u) * ((x * y) * u) = (x * u) * ((x * u) * y) \in I$$

Using implicatively of I and Theorem (3.3.4), we have $y * (y * (x * u)) \in I$.

It follows from $I \subseteq A$ that $y * (y * (x * u)) \in A$. Note that

$$\begin{aligned} (y * (y * x)) * (y * (y * (x * u))) &\leq (y * (x * u)) * (y * x) \\ &\leq x * (x * u) = x * (x * (x * (x * y))) = x * (x * y) \in A. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(y * (y * x)) (y * (y * (x * u))) \in A$. Combining $y * (y * (x * u)) \in A$ we have $y * (y * x) \in A$. By Theorem (3.3.4), A is an implicative ideal. ■

Finally we give some characterizations of implicative BCK-algebras ideals

COROLLARY 3.3.7. Given a BCK-algebra X, the following are equivalent :

- (a) The zero ideal $\{0\}$ is implicative,
- (b) Every ideal of X is implicative,
- (c) For all a of X, $A(a) = \{x \in X : x \leq a\}$ is an implicative ideal ,
- (d) X is an implicative BCK-algebra

Proof. (a) \Leftrightarrow (b) \Leftrightarrow (c) is an immediate consequence of Theorem (3.3.6) is clear that (d) implies (a) and (b). For the converse implication, Let $\{0\}$ be an implicative ideal. By Theorem (3.3.3), $\{0\}$ is also a positive implicative ideal. Thus $A(x * (y * x))$ is an ideal by Corollary (3.2.7), and so it is implicative. From $x * (y * x) \in A(x * (y * x))$ it follows that $x \in A(x * (y * x))$, hence

$x \leq x * (y * x)$. The converse inequality is clear. Consequently $x = x * (y * x)$. This shows that X is an implicative BCK-algebra. This completes the proof. ■

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION FOUR

3.4. Commutative ideals of BCK-algebras

Following the idea of implicative and positive implicative ideals, J. Meng [4] introduced the notion of commutative ideals, and discussed the relations of commutative ideals, positive implicative ideals, and implicative ideals.

DEFINITION 3.4.1. A nonempty subset I of a BCK-algebra X is said to be a commutative ideal of X if it satisfies

- (a) $0 \in I$,
- (b) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$ imply $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$ for all x, y, z in X .

Obviously, X is always a commutative ideal of BCK-algebra X , which called the trivial commutative ideal.

In the example (3.3.4), $\{0,2\}$ and $\{0,2,4\}$ are commutative ideals, but not positive implicative ideals. Also $\{0, 1, 3\}$ is a positive implicative ideal but not commutative, and $\{0,1,2,3\}$ is an implicative ideal.

THEOREM 3.4.2. A commutative ideal must be an ideal, but the inverse hold

Proof. Suppose I is a commutative ideal, and let $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. Then $(x * 0) * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. By the definition, we have $x = x * (0 * (0 * x)) \in I$,

and so I is an ideal. The last half part is shown by the previous example. This completes the proof. ■

THEOREM 3. 4.3. An ideal I is commutative if and only if it satisfies

- (a) $x * y \in I$ implies $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$.

Proof. If an ideal I is commutative and $x * y \in I$, then $(x * y) * 0 \in I$ and $0 \in I$. By (ii) we have $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. This says that (a) holds.

Conversely , let an ideal I satisfies (a). If $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$, then by the definition of ideals we obtain $x * y \in I$. It follows from (a) that $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. This means that I is a commutative ideal . This finishes the proof. ■

In the following theorem we will give a relation of commutative ideals , implicative ideas and positive implicative ideals , which is similar to Theorem (1.6.2) .

THEOREM 3.4.4. If we are given a BCK-algebra X , then a nonempty subset I of X is an implicative ideal if and only if it is both a commutative ideal and positive implicative ideal .

Proof . Suppose I is an implicative ideal. By Theorem (3.3.3) I is a positive implicative ideal. Now we prove that I is also commutative. To do this let $x * y \in I$. Since $x * (y * (y * x)) \leq x$, we have $y * x \leq y * (x * (y * (y * x)))$. Denote $u = x * (y * (y * x))$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} u * (y * u) &= (x * (y * (y * x))) * (y * (x * (y * (y * x)))) \\ &\leq (x * (y * (y * x))) * (y * x) = (x * (y * x)) * (y * (y * x)) \leq x * y \in I . \end{aligned}$$

Hence $u * (x * u) \in I$. Making use of Theorem 3.5 we get $u \in I$, i.e., $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. This proves that $x * y \in I$ implies $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. Therefore I is a commutative ideal .

Conversely , suppose I is both a commutative ideal and positive implicative ideal.

Let $x * (y * x) \in I$. Since $(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \leq x * (y * x)$,

$(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \in I$. Making use of Throrem (3.2.5 (b)) we have

$$(1) \quad y * (y * x) \in I .$$

Moreover, since $x * y \leq x * (y * x)$ we obtain $x * y \in I$. By Theorem (3.4.3), $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. Combining (1) we have $x \in I$. This proves that $x * (y * x) \in I$, implies $x \in I$. Therefore I is an implicative ideal. This completes the proof. ■

With respect to the distribution of commutative ideals in a BCK- algebra , we have

THEOREM 3.4.5 Suppose I and A are ideals of X and let $I \subseteq A$. If I is commutative then so is A .

Proof . Let $x * y \in A$ and denote $u = x * y$, then $(x * u) * y = (x * y) * u = 0 \in I$.

Using the commutativity of I and Theorem (3.4.3), we have $(x * u) * (y * (y * (x * u))) \in I$.

The hypothesis $I \subseteq A$ implies $(x * (y * (y * (x * u)))) * u = (x * u) * (y * (y * (x * u))) \in A$.

Combining $u \in A$ we have $x * (y * (y * (x * u))) \in A$. As

$$(x * (y * (y * x))) * (x * (y * (y * (x * u)))) \leq (y * (y * (x * u))) * (y * (y * x))$$

$\leq (y * x) * (y * (x * u)) \leq (x * u) * x = 0 * u \in A$, we obtain $x * (y * (y * x)) \in A$. Hence A is a commutative ideal. finishes the proof. ■

We close this section with the next theorem, in which some characterizations of commutative BCK-algebras are shown.

THEOREM 3.4.6 If we are given a BCK-algebra X , then the following are equivalent :

- (a) Zero $\{0\}$ is commutative,
- (b) Every ideal of X is commutative,
- (c) X is a commutative BCK-algebra.

proof. (a) \Leftrightarrow (b) follows directly from Theorem (3.4.5). It is not difficult to verify (a) \Leftrightarrow (c) by means of Theorem (3.5.6). ■

From (3.3.2), to this section we discussed the three classes of ideals in BCK-algebras-commutative ideals, positive implicative ideals and implicative ideals, and their relationships. It is need to emphasize that in BCK-algebras, zero ideal plays an important role : a BCK-algebra X is commutative (resp. implicative, positive implicative) if and only if the zero ideal of X is commutative (resp. implicative, positive implicative). Hence we think the zero ideal to be not trivial.

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION FIVE

3.5. Maximal ideals of BCK-algebras

DEFINITION 3.5.1. Given a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, an ideal I of X is called to be a maximal ideal if I is a proper ideal of X and not a proper subset of any proper ideal of X .

EXAMPLE 3.5.2.

a) Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let $(\bar{X}; *, 0)$ be the Iséki's extension of X . Then X is a maximal ideal of \bar{X} .

b) Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
---	---	---	---	---	---

0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1	1
3	3	3	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, $\{0,1,2,3\}$ and $\{0,1,2,4\}$ are two maximal ideal of X .

THEOREM3. 5.3 . Suppose $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded BCK-algebra and $|X| \geq 2$. Then X at least have one maximal ideal.

Proof . we proceed on the following steps .

The first step . We prove that an ideal of X is proper if and only if $1 \notin I$. In fact , if $1 \notin I$, then $I \neq X$, and so I is a proper ideal.

Conversely , assume that I is proper . If $1 \in I$ then $x \leq 1$ for all x of X , hence $x \in I$. This means that $I = X$, which contradicts to the hypothesis. Therefore $1 \notin I$.

The second step. We prove that every ideal A is contained in a maximal ideal . The set of all proper ideals containing A is denoted by S .

Obviously $(S; \subseteq)$ is a partially ordered set and $S \neq \emptyset$. Let S_0 be a totally ordered subset of S and denote $B = \cup \{ I : I \in S_0 \}$. Noticing that A is the least element of (S, \subseteq) we have $A \subseteq B$.

Hence $0 \in B$. Let $x * y \in B$ and $y \in B$. Then there are $I_1, I_2 \in S_0$ such that $x * y \in I_1$ and $y \in I_2$. we can suppose $I_2 \subseteq I_1$, without loss of any generality . Thus $x * y \in I_1$, $y \in I_1$ and $x \in I_1$.

It follows that $x \in B$. This means that B is an ideal. Since every ideal of S_0 does not contain the element 1 , we have $1 \notin B$. By the first step B is a proper ideal, hence $B \in S$. This proved that every totally ordered subset of S have an upper bound in S .

By Zorn's lemma S have a maximal element M . Clearly, $A \subseteq M$. Therefore M is indeed a maximal ideal. ■

As an immediate consequence of the above theorem we have

THEOREM 3.5.4. Suppose X is a bounded BCK-algebra and let I be a proper commutative (resp. implicative, positive implicative) ideal, then there is a maximal commutative (resp. implicative, positive implicative) ideal containing I .

In the next theorem some of equivalent conditions of maximal ideals are given .

THEOREM 3.5.5. Suppose I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra X . Then the following are equivalent :

- (a) I is maximal and implicative,
- (b) I is maximal and positive implicative,
- (c) $x, y \notin I$ implies $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$ for all x, y in X .

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b) . See Theorem (3.3.3).

(b) \Rightarrow (c) Let $x \notin I$ and $y \notin I$. Since I is positive implicative , by Corollary (3.2.4),

$A_y = \{ u \in X : u * y \in I \}$ is the least ideal containing I and y . Using maximalist of I we have

$A_y = X$. Hence $x \in A_y$, that is $x * y \in I$. Likewise for $y * x \in I$. (c) holds.

(c) \Rightarrow (a). At first we prove that I is implicative. Suppose I does not implicative, then there are x, y in X such that $x * (y * x) \in I$ but $x \notin I$. We consider $y * x$. If $y * x \in I$, combining $x * (y * x) \in I$ we obtain $x \in I$, which contradicts to $x \notin I$. If $y * x \notin I$ by (c) we have $y \in I$ as $x \notin I$. By means of

$y * x \leq y$, we obtain $y * x \in I$, which contradicts $y * x \notin I$. Summarizing we have $x \in I$. This means that I is implicative .

Next we prove that I is maximal. Note that I is also positive implicative , hence it suffices to verify that for any $a \notin I$ we have $A_a = \{ x \in X : x * a \in I \} = X$. In view of Corollary (3.2.4), A_a is the least ideal containing I and a , and so for all u in X , when $u \in I$, then $u \in A_a$; when $u \notin I$, by $a \notin I$ and (c) we have $u * a \in I$, i.e , $u \in A_a$. This says $A_a = X$. Therefore I is maximal. The proof is completed. ■

THEOREM 3.5.6. Suppose X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra and let I be an ideal of X . Then I is maximal if and only if , for all x, y in X , $x \notin I$ imply $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$.

Proof. It is immediate from Theorem (3.5.5) and Corollary (3.2.7). ■

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CHAPTER THREE

SECTION SIX

3.6.Quotient to BCK-algebras

In (3.1) we established quotient algebras of BCK-algebras via ideals. Now we will give further properties of them, in particular, characterize quotient algebras by means of properties of ideals .

THEOREM 3.6.1. Let I be an ideal of a BCK-algebra X . Then I is commutative if and only if the quotient algebra $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra.

Proof .Necessity. Let I be a commutative ideal. For x, y in X denote $u = y * (y * x)$, then $u * x = 0 \in I$, and so $u * (x * (x * u)) \in I$. Since $C_0 = I$ it follows that

$$C_u * (C_x * (C_x * C_u)) = C_{u * (x * (x * u))} = C_0, \text{Hence}$$

$$C_y * (C_y * C_x) = C_{y * (y * x)} = C_u \leq C_u * (C_x * C_u).$$

The inverse inequality is trivial. Therefore we have

$$C_y * (C_y * C_x) = C_x * (C_x * C_u) = C_x * (C_x * (C_y * (C_y * C_x))).$$

By Theorem (1.5.12), it follows that the quotient algebra $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is commutative .

Sufficiency . Let $(X/I; *, C_0)$ be commutative, then zero ideal $\{C_0\}$ is commutative . If $x * y \in I$ then $C_x * C_y = C_{x * y} = C_0 \in \{C_0\}$.By Theorem (3.4.3), we have

$$C_{x * (y * (y * x))} = C_x * (C_y * (C_y * C_x)) \in \{C_0\},$$

that is , $C_{x * (y * (y * x))} = C_0$, and so $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$ Making use of Theorem (3.4.3), I is a commutative ideal. The proof is complete . ■

THEOREM 3.6.2. Suppose I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra X . Then I is positive implicative if and only if the quotient algebra $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is positive implicative BCK-algebra .

Proof. Suppose I is a positive implicative ideal of X . Denote $u = (x * y) * z$, then

$((x * u) * y) * z = ((x * y) * z) * u = 0 \in I$.By Theorem (3.2.5 (c)) we have

$((x * u) * z) * (y * z) \in I$,that is , $((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z) \in I$.

Hence $((C_x * C_z) * (C_y * C_z)) * ((C_x * C_y) * C_z) = C_{((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z)} = C_0$

It is clear that , $((C_x * C_y) * C_z) * ((C_x * C_z) * (C_y * C_z)) = C_0$.

Applying BCI-4 for X/I , we obtain $(C_x * C_z) * (C_y * C_z) = (C_x * C_y) * C_z$.

This shows that $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is positive implicative.

Conversely, let $(X/I; *, C_0)$ be a positive implicative BCK-algebra By Corollary(3. 2.7), $\{ C_0 \}$ is a positive implicative ideal . If $(x * y) * z \in I$, then $(C_x * C_y) * C_z = C_{(x * y) * z} = C_0 \in \{ C_0 \}$.

By means of Theorem (3.2.5 (c)), we have $(C_x * C_z) * (C_y * C_z) \in \{ C_0 \}$.

This is equivalent to $(x * z) * (y * z) \in I$. Hence I is a positive implicative ideal. The proof is complete. ■

THEOREM 3.6.3. Given an ideal I of a BCK-algebra X , I is implicative if and only if the quotient algebra $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is an implicative BCK-algebra .

Proof. This is immediate from Theorem (1.6.2) and Theorems (3.3.6) , (3.6.1) and (3.6.2). ■

In 1977 J. Ahsan and A. B.Thahaem proved that if $(X; *, 0)$ is commutative (resp. implicative, positive implicative), then the quotient algebra $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is also commutative (resp. implicative, positive implicative)

In the above Theorems (3.6.1), (3.6.2) and (3.6.3), we only require ideal I to be commutative (resp. implicative, positive implicative) instead of the mutability (resp. implicatively, positive implicatively) of X , and the conclusions are strengthen.

THEOREM 3.6.4. If we are given a bounded BCK-algebra X with the greatest element 1 and an ideal I of X , then $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is also a bounded BCK-algebra with the greatest element C_1 .

proof. It is need only to prove that C_1 is the greatest element of X/I . For any x in X ,

$C_x * C_1 = C_{x * 1} = C_0$, this means that C_1 is the greatest element of X/I . The proof is complete. ■

The inverse of the above theorem does not hold.

EXAMPLE 3.6.5. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ and the operation $*$ be defined by the table

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. The ordered relation is as the right figure. It is easy to verify that $\{0,1,2\}$ is an ideal of X and $X/I = \{I, \{3\}\}$, this is a BCK-algebra of order 2 and bounded with the greatest element $\{3\}$.

Before stating other results we need the following.

DEFINITION 3.6.6. A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called to be simple if it has no proper non-zero ideals.

EXAMPLE 3.6.7. Let $X = \{0,1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0	0
3	3	1	1	0	0
4	4	1	1	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a simple BCK-algebra.

The example 7 in Chapter 1§1 is simple.

THEOREM 3.6.8. If we are given an ideal I of a BCK-algebra X , then I is maximal if and only if $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is simple.

Proof. Let v be the natural homomorphism from X to X/I . If I maximal ideal of X , we come to prove that X/I is simple. Suppose there is a proper non-zero ideal B of X/I , $v^{-1}(B)$ is a proper ideal of X and properly contains I , which contradicts to maximalist of I .

Conversely, suppose $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is simple. If I is not maximal the there is a proper ideal A of X such that A properly contains I , and so A is a proper non-zero ideal of X/I by Theorem (3.1.8(b)). This contradiction to simplicity of X/I . The proof is complete. ■

THEOREM 3.6.9. Suppose I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra X . Then I is maximal and implicative if and only if the quotient algebra $(X/I; *, C_0) \cong 2$.

Proof. By Theorems (3.6.3) and (3.6.7), I is maximal and implicative if and only if X/I is a simple and implicative BCK-algebra, obviously, the latter $\cong 2$. This finishes the proof. ■

For Boolean algebras the following fact is well-known.

Tar ski theorem. Suppose I is an ideal of a Boolean algebra X , then I is maximal if and only if, $X/I \cong 2$.

In general a BCK-algebra need not be a Boolean algebra, but it may contain a maximal and implicative ideal. The example 3 in §3 is precisely such an example, in which $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is a maximal and implicative ideal. Consequently Theorem (3.6.9) is a generalization of Tar ski theorem.

THEOREM 3.6.10. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra with condition (S) and I an ideal of X . Then the quotient algebra $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is also with condition (S).

Proof. We define the operation \circ on X/I by $C_x \circ C_y = C_{x \circ y}$. At first we prove that it is well-defined. Let $x \sim v$, by Theorem I.7.8 we have

$$(x \circ y) * (u \circ y) \leq x * u \in I \text{ and } (u \circ y) * (x \circ y) \leq u * x \in I,$$

Hence $(x \circ y) * (u \circ y) \in I$ and $(u \circ y) * (x \circ y) \in I$, that is, $x \circ y \sim u \circ y$. Likewise for $u \circ y \sim u \circ v$. By transitivity of \sim we have $x \circ y \sim u \circ v$, which means that \circ is well-defined.

Next by the definition of \circ we have

$$(1) \quad (C_x \circ C_y) * C_x = C_{(x \circ y) * x} \leq C_y.$$

On the other hand, if $C_z * C_x \leq C_y$ then $C_{(z * x) * y} = (C_z * C_x) * C_y = C_0$. Hence $(z * x) * y \in I$.

Since $(z * ((z * x) * y)) * y = (z * y) * ((z * x) * y) \leq z * (z * x) \leq x$,

We have $z * ((z * x) * y) \leq x \circ y$, Which is equivalent to $z * (x \circ y) \leq (z * x) * y \in I$.

Thus $z * (x \circ y) \in I$. For the quotient algebra X/I we have $C_z * C_{x \circ y} = C_0$,

and so $C_x \leq C_{x \circ y}$. Combining (1) we know that $C_{x \circ y}$ is the greatest element in X/I satisfying

$C_z * C_x \leq C_y$. Therefore X/I is with condition (S) and $C_x \circ C_y = C_{x \circ y}$. The proof is complete. ■

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CHAPTER THREE

SECTION SEVEN

3.7.Finitely generated ideals of BCK-algebras

THEOREM 3.7.1. If $\{ I_\lambda : \lambda \in \Lambda \}$ is an indexed set of ideals of a BCK-algebra X , then

$I = \bigcap \{ I_\lambda : \lambda \in \Lambda \}$ is an ideal of X .

DEFINITION 3.7.2 Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let A be a subset of X . Define the ideal generated by A to be the intersection of all ideals of X which contain A .

Notice that this definition is well as there will always be at least one ideal which contain A , X itself. For convenience the ideal generated by will be denoted by $[A]$.

We follow the convention : $(\emptyset] = \{0\}$, and $(\{ a_1, \dots, a_n \}) = (a_1, \dots, a_n]$ The elements

a_1, \dots, a_n are called to be the generators of $(a_1, \dots, a_n]$.

Naturally one wishes to have a description of the elements of $(A]$. K. Iséki, gave a nice result.

THEOREM 3.7.3. Suppose X is a BCK-algebra and A a nonempty subset of X . Then

$(A] = \{ x \in X : \exists a_1, \dots, a_n \in A \text{ such that}$

$(\dots(x * a_1) * \dots) * a_n = 0 \}$.

Proof. Denote the right side of $(*)$ by B , clearly $0 \in B$. Let $x * y \in B$ and $y \in B$, then there are $a_1, \dots, a_m, b_1, \dots, b_n \in A$ such that $(\dots(y * a_1) * \dots) * a_m = 0$, $(\dots((x * y) * b_1) * \dots) * b_n = 0$.

Hence $(\dots(x * b_1) * \dots) * b_n * y = 0$, $(\dots(x * b_1) * \dots) * b_n \leq y$.

Rightly $*$ multiplying both sides of the above inequality by a_1 we have

$(\dots(x * b_1) * \dots) * b_n * a_1 \leq y * a_1$.

Repeating the above argument m times we obtain

$(\dots(((\dots(x * b_1) * \dots) * b_n) * a_1) * \dots) * a_m \leq (\dots(y * a_1) * \dots) * a_m = 0$,

Consequently, $(\dots(((\dots(x * b_1) * \dots) * b_n) * a_1) * \dots) * a_m = 0$.

This implies that $x \in B$. Summarizing the above facts B is an ideal of X . Obviously, $A \subseteq B$. Let I be an ideal containing A . In order to prove $B \subseteq I$ assume any $x \in B$.

Consequently, there are $c_1, \dots, c_n \in A$ such that $(\dots(x * c_1) * \dots) * c_n = 0$.

Hence $0 \in I$, we have $(\dots(x * c_1) * \dots) * c_n \in I$. Hence I is an ideal and $c_n \in I$, it follows that

$(\dots(x * c_1) * \dots) * c_{n-1} \in I$. Repeating this argument n times we obtain $x \in I$, hence $B \subseteq I$. This shows that $B = (A]$, proving the theorem. ■

DEFINITION 3.7.4. An ideal I of a BCK-algebra X is said to be finitely generated if there is a finite subset A of X such that $I = (A)$.

DEFINITION 3.7.5. Given a BCK-algebra X , we say that X satisfies the maximal condition if each nonempty subset of $I(X)$ contains at least one maximal member with respect to the set theoretic inclusion (\subseteq) . X satisfies the ascending chain condition, abbreviated by ACC, if there does not exist an infinite properly ascending chain $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$ in $I(X)$.

In an entirely analogous way the minimal condition and the descending chain condition (abbreviated by DCC) are defined.

THEOREM 3.7.6. Let X be a BCK-algebra. Then

- (a) X satisfies the maximal condition if and only if X satisfies ACC,
- (b) X satisfies the minimal condition if and only if X satisfies DCC .

proof . Suppose X satisfies the maximal condition and $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$ is an ascending chain in $I(X)$. Then the set $\{I_i : i = 1, 2, \dots\}$ has a maximal member I_n .

Consequently, $I_i = I_n$ for all $i \geq n$, this says X satisfies ACC . Conversely, suppose X satisfies ACC and E is any nonempty subset of $I(X)$. If E has no maximal member, each member of E precedes another member of E , which permits the construction of an infinite chain $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$ in E , where $I_i \neq I_j$, whenever $i \neq j$, a contradiction . Hence X satisfies the maximal condition . The proof of (a) is complete .

Likewise for (b), the reader should supply the details. This completes the proof of the theorem.

THEOREM 3.7.7. Suppose A is an ideal of a BCK-algebra X . Then the quotient algebra X/I satisfies ACC if and only if I and X satisfies ACC.

proof. Let $v : X \rightarrow X/A$ be the natural homomorphism.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$ is any ascending chain in $I(X)$, then $I_1 \cap A \subseteq I_2 \cap A \subseteq \dots$ and

$v(I_1) \subseteq v(I_2) \subseteq \dots$ are ascending chains in $I(X)$ and $I(X/A)$, respectively, hence there exist natural numbers m_1 and m_2 such that $I_{m_1} \cap A = I_i \cap A$ and $v(I_{m_2}) = v(I_j)$ Whenever $m_1 \leq i$ and $m_2 \leq j$ by Theorem (3.7.6(a)), for I and X/I .

Assume $m_0 = \max \{ m_1, m_2 \}$. For $i \geq m_0$ and $x \in I_i$ we have so there is $y \in I_{m_0}$ such that $C_x = C_y$, it follows that $C_x * C_y = C_0$, i.e ., $x * y \in A$. Since $x \in I_i$ and $x * y \leq x$, we have $x * y \in I_i$.

Hence $x * y \in I_i \cap A$, and so $x * y \in I_{m_0}$. Combining $y \in I_{m_0}$ we obtain $x \in I_{m_0}$.

This implies $I_i \subseteq I_{m_0}$. The opposite inclusion is trivial, consequently $I_i = I_{m_0}$. This says that X satisfies ACC .

(\Rightarrow) If $A_1 \subseteq A_2 \subseteq \dots$ is an ascending chain in $I(X/I)$, then $v^{-1}(A_1) \subseteq v^{-1}(A_2) \subseteq \dots$ is an ascending chain in $I(X)$. Since X satisfies ACC, there is a natural number n_0 such that $v^{-1}(A_{n_0}) = v^{-1}(A_i)$ whenever $i \geq n_0$. Hence when $i \geq n_0$ we have $A_{n_0} = A_i$. This means that X/I satisfies ACC. It is easy to check that I satisfies ACC and mitted. The proof is complete. ■

DEFINITION 3.7.8. A BCK-algebra X is said to be Noetherian if each ideal of X is finitely generated .

In the following theorem we give some characterizations of Noetherian algebras .

THEOREM 3.7.9 In a algebra X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is Noetherian ,
- (b) X satisfies ACC,
- (c) X satisfies the maximal condition.

proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b). Assume (a) and any ascending chain $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$ in $I(X)$.

Obviously $I = \cup \{ I_i : i = 1, 2, \dots \}$ is an ideal of X , and so I is finitely generated.

Let $I = (a_1, \dots, a_n]$, then there are natural numbers $m_i (i = 1, \dots, n)$ such that $a_i \in I_{m_i} (i = 1, \dots, n)$. Denote $m = \max \{ m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n \}$, we have $a_i \in I_m (i = 1, \dots, n)$, hence $I \subseteq I_m$, it flows that

$I_m = I_{m+1} = \dots$. Therefore (b) follows .

(b) \Leftrightarrow (c). See Theorem (3.7.6(a)) .

(c) \Rightarrow (a) Suppose X satisfies the maximal condition and I is any ideal of X which cannot be finitely generated. Let $a_1 \in I$, then $I_1 = I_n \neq I$ and there exists $a_2 \in I - I_1$. Thus $I_1 \subseteq I_2 = (a_1, a_2]$ and Choose $a_3 \in I - I_2$ then $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq I_3 = (a_1, a_2, a_3]$, and so on. This process cannot terminate , so it yields an infinite ascending chain $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq I_3 \subseteq \dots$ in $I(X)$, which contradicts to(c). This means that X

Noetherian, completing the proof of the theorem. ■

THEOREM 3.7.10. A BCK-algebra X is positive implicative if and only if for any $a_1, \dots, a_n \in X$,

$$(a_1, \dots, a_n] = \{ x \in X : (\dots (x * a_1) * \dots) * a_n = 0 \} .$$

Proof. Suppose that X is positive implicative , then

$$(a_1] = \{ x \in X : x \leq a_1 \} = \{ x \in X : x * a_1 = 0 \} \text{ in view of Theorem (3. 2.5). If } a_1, \dots, a_m \in X ,$$

$$(a_1, \dots, a_m] = \{ x \in X : (\dots (x * a_1) * \dots) * a_m = 0 \} , \text{ Then by Corollary (3.2.4) and Theorem (3.2.5), we have } ((a_1, \dots, a_m] \cup \{ a_{m+1} \}) = \{ x \in X : x * a_{m+1} \in (a_1, \dots, a_m] \}$$

$$= \{ x \in X : (\dots ((x * a_{m+1}) * a_1) * \dots) * a_m = 0 \} = \{ x \in X : ((\dots (x * a_1) * \dots) * a_m) * a_{m+1} = 0 \} .$$

Therefore any $a_1, \dots, a_n \in X. (a_1, \dots, a_n] = \{ x \in X : (\dots (x * a_1) * \dots) * a_n = 0 \} .$

inductive argument. The necessity holds.

Conversely, suppose that for any $a_1, \dots, a_n \in X$, $(a_1, \dots, a_n] = \{x \in X : (\dots(x * a_1) * \dots) * a_n = 0\}$.

Particular, for $a \in X$ we have $(a] = \{x \in X : x * a = 0\} = A(a)$, That is to say that each initial section of X is an ideal, and so X is positive implicative by Theorem (3.2.5). ■

THEOREM 3.7.11. Suppose that X is a BCK-algebra with condition (S). Then for any $a_1, \dots, a_n \in X$, there exist natural numbers m_1, \dots, m_n such that

$$(a_1, \dots, a_n] = \{x \in X : x \leq \underbrace{(a_1 \circ \dots \circ a_1)}_{m_1 \text{ times}} \circ \dots \circ \underbrace{(a_n \circ \dots \circ a_n)}_{m_n \text{ times}}\}.$$

Proof. Let $x \in (a_1, \dots, a_n]$, then there exist $a_{k1}, \dots, a_{ki} \in \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ such that

$$(\dots (x * a_{k1}) * \dots) * a_{ki} = 0, \text{ hence } (\dots (x * a_{k1}) * \dots) * a_{k-1} \leq a_{ki}.$$

In view of the condition(S) we obtain $(\dots (x * a_{k1}) * \dots) * a_{ki} \leq a_{k-1} \circ a_{ki}$.

Repeating the above argument i times we have

$$x \leq a_{k1} \circ \dots \circ a_{ki} \leq \underbrace{(a_1 \circ \dots \circ a_1)}_{m_1 \text{ times}} \circ \dots \circ \underbrace{(a_n \circ \dots \circ a_n)}_{m_n \text{ times}}$$

This means that $(a_1, \dots, a_n] \subseteq \{x \in X : x \leq \underbrace{(a_1 \circ \dots \circ a_1)}_{m_1 \text{ times}} \circ \dots \circ \underbrace{(a_n \circ \dots \circ a_n)}_{m_n \text{ times}}\}$.

Conversely, let $x \leq \underbrace{(a_1 \circ \dots \circ a_1)}_{m_1 \text{ times}} \circ \dots \circ \underbrace{(a_n \circ \dots \circ a_n)}_{m_n \text{ times}}$, then by the definition of \circ we have

$$x * a_1 \leq \underbrace{a_1 \circ \dots \circ a_1}_{m_1 - 1 \text{ times}} \circ \dots \circ \underbrace{a_n \circ \dots \circ a_n}_{m_n \text{ times}}.$$

If $m_1 = 1$, the right side of the above inequality does not contain a_1 . Repeating this process we obtain $(\dots (x *^{m_1} a_1) *^{m_2} \dots) *^{m_n} a_n = 0$.

This says that $\{x \in X : x \leq \underbrace{(a_1 \circ \dots \circ a_1)}_{m_1 \text{ times}} \circ \dots \circ \underbrace{(a_n \circ \dots \circ a_n)}_{m_n \text{ times}}\} \subseteq (a_1, \dots, a_n]$.

The proof is complete. ■

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION EIBHT

3.8.Prime ideals and irreducible ideals of BCK-algebras

The notion of prime ideals was introduced by K. Iséki [14]. M. Palasinski [3] discussed relationships among prime ideals, maximal ideals, and irreducible ideals .

DEFINITION 3.8.1. A BCK-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$ is said to be a lower BCK-semilattice if X is a lower semilattice with respect to BCK-order \leq , and denote $x \wedge y = \text{glb} \{ x, y \}$.

Any commutative BCK-algebra X is a lower BCK-semilattice, in which $y * (y * x) = \text{glb} \{ x, y \}$. In general , the inverse is false. The following example shows that the class of lower BCK-semilattices is a...

EXAMPLE 3.8.2.

a) Assume $X = \{ 1, 2, 3, 4 \}$ in which $*$ is defined by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1	0
3	3	1	1	0	0
4	4	1	1	1	0

Then $(X ; * , 0)$ is a BCK- algebra, but not commutative as

$$4 * (4 * 2) = 1 \neq 2 = 2 * (2 * 4).$$

The right side is the ordered relation, it follows that X is a lower BCK-semilattice.

b) Let $X = \{ 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 \}$ in which $*$ is defined by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	0
2	2	2	0	0	0
3	3	3	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra, the right figure is the ordered relation. Obviously, X is not a lower BCK-semilattice.

DEFINITION 3.8.3. Let X be a lower BCK-semilattice and I a proper ideal of X. Then I is said to be prime if $a \wedge b \in I$ implies $a \in I$ or $b \in I$ for any a, b in X.

DEFINITION 3.8.4. A proper ideal I of a BCK-algebra X is called to be irreducible if $I = A \cap B$ implies $I = A$ or $I = B$ for any $A, B \in \mathcal{I}(X)$.

The following lemma is a base of this section, and due to M. Palasinski .

LEMMA 3.8.5. Given a lower BCK-semilattice X , if $a *^n x = 0$ and $a *^m y = 0$ for natural number n and m then there exists a natural number p such that $a *^p (x \wedge y) = 0$.

COROLLARY 3.8.6. Suppose X is a lower BCK-semilattice and I an ideal. Then $x \wedge y \in I$ implies $(I \cup \{x\}) \cap (I \cup \{y\}) = I$.

As an immediate consequence of Corollary (3.8.5), we have

COROLLARY 3.8.7. For a lower BCK-semilattice X, we have $(x] \cap (y] = (x \wedge y]$.

DEFINITION 3.8.8. In a lower BCK-semilattice X, a nonempty subset S of X is said to be \wedge -closed if $x \wedge y \in S$ whenever $x, y \in S$.

COROLLARY 3.8.9. Suppose that X is a lower BCK-semilattice and S a nonempty subset of X, if S is \wedge -closed and $0 \notin S$ then $Z = \{ I \in \mathcal{I}(X) : I \cap S = \emptyset \}$ have a maximal ideal P such that $P \cap S = \emptyset$, moreover P is a prime ideal.

proof. The existence of an ideal P easily follows from Zorn's lemma. We will prove that P is a prime ideal. Let us suppose it is not the case, i.e., there exist $x, y \in X$ such that $x \wedge y \in P$, $x \notin P$ and $y \notin P$. Then P is properly contained in both $(P \cup \{x\}) = P_1$ and $(P \cup \{y\}) = P_2$. Because of maximality of P , $P_1 \cap P_2 \neq \emptyset$ and $P_2 \cap P_1 \neq \emptyset$. Let $s_i \in P_1 \cap P_2$, $i = 1, 2$. Then $s_1 \wedge s_2 \leq s_i$, $i = 1, 2$ implies $s_1 \wedge s_2 \in P_1 \cap P_2 = P$, by Lemma (3.8.4). On the other hand $s_1 \wedge s_2 \in S$. This is a contradiction. The proof is complete. ■

THEOREM 3.8.10. In a lower BCK-semilattice X , any maximal ideal must be prime, but the inverse is false.

Proof. In the face of Corollary 8.8 it suffices to show that for a maximal ideal I , $X-I$ is \wedge -closed. If it is not the case, then there exist $x, y \in X-I$

such that $x \wedge y \in I$. Because of maximality of I we have $(I \cup \{x\}) = (I \cup \{y\}) = X$. So I is properly contained in $(I \cup \{x\}) \cap (I \cup \{y\})$, which contradicts to Corollary 8.5. Hence I is a prime ideal. The last half part is shown by the following example.

EXAMPLE 3.8. 11. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1	0
3	3	3	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a lower BCK-semilattice. It is easy to verify that $\{0, 1, 2\}$ is a prime ideal of X , but not maximal. In fact, $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is an ideal and properly contain $\{0, 1, 2\}$.

THEOREM 3.8.12. In a lower BCK-semilattice X , the following are equivalent:

- I is an irreducible ideal,
- I is a prime ideal,
- I is an ideal and satisfies that for any $A, B \in \mathcal{I}(X)$, $A \subseteq I$ or $B \subseteq I$ whenever $A \cap B \subseteq I$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b). Let us suppose that I is not prime. Then for some $x, y \in X-I$, $x \wedge y \in I$. It is obvious that I is properly contained in $(I \cup \{x\}) = I_1$ and $(I \cup \{y\}) = I_2$. By Corollary (3.8.5), $I = I_1 \cap I_2$. So I is not irreducible, a contradiction.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). If (c) does not hold then for some $A, B \in I(X)$, $A \cap B \subseteq I$, $A \not\subseteq I$ and $B \not\subseteq I$. Thus there exist a and b such that $a \in A-I$ and $b \in B-I$. From $a \wedge b \leq a$ and $a \wedge b \leq b$ it follows that $a \wedge b \in A, B$, and so $a \wedge b \in A \cap B \subseteq I$, which contradicts to primness of I . Hence (c) holds.

(c) \Rightarrow (a). Let us suppose that there exist $A, B \in I(X)$ such that $I = A \cap B$. So $A \subseteq I$ or $B \subseteq I$ which imply $I = A$ or $I = B$. Thus I is irreducible. This finishes the proof. ■

In a stronger condition the inverse of Theorem (3.8.12) holds

THEOREM 3.8.13. If X is an implicative BCK-algebra, then each prime ideal of X is maximal

Proof. Let us suppose that I is a prime ideal and $a, b \notin I$. By implicativity of X , $(a * b) \wedge b = b * (b * (a * b)) = b * b = 0 \in I$. Noticing $b \notin I$ we have $a * b \in I$. By the same way we obtain $b * a \in I$. Hence I is maximal by Theorem 5.4. The proof is complete.

Summarizing the preceding facts we know that in an implicative BCK-algebra, the notions of maximal ideals, prime ideals and irreducible ideals coincide

DEFINITION 3.8.14. A BCK-algebra X is called to be a BCK-chain if $(X; \leq)$ is a totally ordered set, i.e., for any $x, y \in X$, $x \leq y$ or $y \leq x$.

Now we give some relationships between prime ideals and quotient algebras.

THEOREM 3.8.5. If and only if for any $x, y \in X$, $(x * y) \wedge (y * x) = 0$, then the quotient algebra $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is a BCK-chain.

(b) if $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is a BCK-chain, then I is prime.

DEFINITION 3.8.16. A lower BCK-semilattice X is said to be cancellative if $x \wedge y = 0$ implies $x = 0$ or $y = 0$ for all $x, y \in X$.

THEOREM 3.8.17. In a commutative BCK-algebra X , an ideal I of X is prime if and only if X/I is cancellative

In the setting of bounded implicative BCK-algebras there is a simpler criticism of primness for ideals.

THEOREM 3.8.16. Let X be a bounded implicative BCK-algebra and Let I be an ideal of X . Then I is prime (maximal, irreducible) if and only if for any $x \in X$, exactly one of x, N_x belongs to I .

Proof. Suppose that I is prime. If $x \notin I$ and $N_x \notin I$ for some $x \in X$ then

$x \wedge N_x = x * (x * (1 * x)) = x * x = 0 \in I$, Which implies $x \in I$ or $N_x \in I$, a contradiction . If $x \in I$ and $N_x \in I$ for some $x \in X$, then $1 \in I$ as I is an ideal, this is impossible. Summarizing the above facts we obtain that exactly one of x , N_x belongs to I .

Conversely, assume that exactly one of x , N_x belongs to I for any $x \in X$. If $x \wedge y \in I$, we will prove $x \in I$ or $y \in I$. Suppose $x \notin I$, then $N_x \in I$. Since $y * N_x = y * (1 * x) \leq y * (y * x) = x \wedge y \in I$,

It follows that $y \in I$. This says that I is prime. The proof is complete . ■

Prof. Dr. Areej Tawfeeq Hameed

CHAPTER FOUR

SECTION ONE

4.1. Some Types of Algebras with one operation

This chapter is devoted to the basic definitions and results concerning several types of algebras and its Fuzzy sets, which are required in the succeeding sections. All results here are quoted from existing literature.

In this section, the notions of several classes of algebras were introduced. Here we give a brief review of some algebras such as BCH, BCC, d, BH, Q, QS, KU, etc..

We collected some types of algebra in the period from 1966 to 2015, including subalgebra, ideal, fuzzy subalgebra, fuzzy ideal and some laws achieved by this species that take them and that the link between certain types of algebra, which we took a brief by example α -algebra \leftrightarrow β -algebra $+(x + y) - (x + z) = y - z$.

There are kinds of other types of generalization He reminded us that before we begin to type, there are kinds where ideal \rightarrow subalgebra and not vice versa. We have proven that in the example of some species.

4.1.1.BCH-algebras

The concept of a BCH-algebra is a generalization of the concept of a BCI-algebra. BCH-subalgebra has been found in 1990. Jun Y.B., applied the concept of fuzzy subset to BCH-algebras and he considered the fuzzification of ideals in BCH-algebras . BCH-ideal has been found .

Definition 4.1.1.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BCH-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$,
- (3) $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$.

Definition 4.1.1.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCH-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X .Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$

Definition 4.1.1.3:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCH-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called an **ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.1.4:

Let X be a BCH-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies: $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$

Definition 4.1.1.5:

Let X be a BCH-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy ideal** of X if it satisfies the following conditions :

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.2. BCC-algebras:

In 1983, Komori Y., introduced a new concept of BCC-algebras. Dudek W.A. and Zhang X.H and Jun Y.B, introduced the notion of BCC-ideals in BCC-algebras and described connections between such ideal and congruences and considered the fuzzification of BCC-ideals in BCC-algebras.

Definition 4.1.2.1:

Let $(X; \cdot, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation (\cdot) and a constant (0) . then $(X; \cdot, 0)$ is called a **BCC-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $((x \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot y))(x \cdot z) = 0$,
2. $x \cdot x = 0$,
3. $0 \cdot x = 0$,
4. $x \cdot 0 = x$,
5. $x \cdot y = 0$ and $y \cdot x = 0$ imply $x = y$,

Definition 4.1.2.2:

For brevity we also call X a BCK-algebra. We can define a binary relation (\leq) in by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x \cdot y = 0$

Example 4.1.2.3:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which (\cdot) is defined by the following table:

\cdot	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	0
2	2	2	0	0	0
3	3	3	1	0	0
4	4	3	4	3	0

Then $(X; \cdot, 0)$ is a BCC-algebra.

Definition 4.1.2.4:

Let $(X; \cdot, 0)$ be a BCC-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x \cdot y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.2.5:

Let $(X; \cdot, 0)$ be a BCC-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **BCC-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $(x \cdot y) \cdot z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \cdot z \in I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.2.6:

- (C_1) In a BCC-algebra, any BCC-ideal is a BCK-ideal.
- (C_2) In a BCK-algebra, any BCK-ideal is a BCC-ideal.
- (C_3) In a BCC-algebra, any BCK-ideal is a BCK-subalgebra.
- (C_4) In a BCC-algebra, any BCC-ideal is a BCC-subalgebra.

Definition 4.1.2.7:

Let X be a BCC-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies: $\mu(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$

Definition 4.1.2.8:

Let X be a BCC-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy BCC-ideal** of X if it satisfies the following conditions :

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x \cdot z) \geq \min\{\mu((x \cdot y) \cdot z), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

4.1.3. Hilbert algebras:

In 1985, Busneag D., introduced the class of Hilbert algebras . Kim J., Kim Y. and Roh E.H. and Kim K.H, View what is subalgebra and ideal for Hilbert algebras and View what is fuzzy subalgebra and fuzzy ideal for Hilbert algebras.

Definition 4.1.3.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **Hilbert-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (I) $x * (y * x) = 0$,
- (II) $(x * (y * z))((x * y) (x * z)) = 0$,
- (III) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$.

For brevity we also call X a Hilbert-algebra. We can define a binary relation (\leq) in X by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.3.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a Hilbert algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $0 * x = x$,
- (3) $x * 0 = 0$,
- (4) $x * (y * z) = y * (x * z)$,
- (5) $x * (y * z) = (x * y) (x * z)$
- (6) $x * ((x * y) * y) = 0$.

Definition 4.1.3.3:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a Hilbert algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.3.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a Hilbert algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called an **ideal** of X if it satisfies: for all $x, y \in X$.

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $x * y \in I$ for $x \in X, y \in I$,
- (iii) $(y * (z * x)) * x \in I$ for $y, z \in I, x \in X$.

Definition 4.1.3.5:

Let X be a Hilbert algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy sub-algebra** of X if it satisfies: $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.3.6

Let X be a Hilbert algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy ideal** of X if it satisfies the following conditions :

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$,

2. $\mu(x * y) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x, y \in X$,
3. $\mu((y * (z * x)) * x) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$

4.1.4. BG-algebras:

The concept of a BG-algebra is a generalization of the concept of a B-algebra. BG-subalgebra has been found in 1992, Ahn S.S. and Lee D. , new subalgebra and fuzzy subalgebra BG-ideal and fuzzy BG-ideal has been found see.

Definition 4.1.4.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BG - algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $x * 0 = x$,
- (3) $(x * y) * (0 * y) = x$.

For brevity we also call **XaBG-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) in by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.4.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BG-algebra , then the following hold :for any $x, y \in X$,

- (BG_1) $0 * (0 * x) = x$,
- (BG_2) $x * y = 0$, then $x = y$,
- (BG_3) $0 * x = 0 * y$, then $x = y$,

$$(BG_4) (x * (0 * x)) * x = 0.$$

Example 4.1.4.3:

Let $X = \{0,1,2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	1	2
1	1	0	1
2	2	2	0

Then $(X;*, 0)$ is a BG-algebra.

Definition 4.1.4.4:

Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a BG -algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.4.5:

Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a BG-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **BG-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$,
- iii. $x \in I$ and $y \in X$ imply $x * y \in I$, i.e., $I * X \subseteq I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.4.6:

Let X be a BG-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if,

$$\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

Definition 4.1.4.7:

Let X be a BG-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy BG-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$,
3. $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.5. BH-algebra:

In 1998, Jun Y. B., Roh E. H. and Kim H. S., introduced the notion of BH-algebras and investigated several properties. Zhang Q., Jun Y.B. and Roh E.H, introduced definition of BH-subalgebra and BH-ideal and introduced definition of fuzzy BH-ideal. Baik H.G. and Park C.H, introduced definition of fuzzy subalgebra .

Definition 4.1.5.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BH-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $x * 0 = x$,
- (3) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ implies $x = y$.

Proposition 4.1.5.2:

(BH_1) Every BCH-algebra is a BH-algebra.

(BH_2) Every BH-algebra satisfying the condition

$(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$, for all $x, y, z \in X$, is a BCH-algebra

(BH_3) Every BH-algebra satisfying the condition

$(x * y) * (x * z) * (z * y) = 0$, for all $x, y, z \in X$, is BCI-algebra.

(BH_4) Every BH-algebra satisfying the condition, for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$, and $(x * y) * x = 0$, is a BCK-algebra.

Example 4.1.5.3:

Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	3	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BH-algebra.

Definition 4.1.5.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BH-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.5.5:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BH-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **BH-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

$$\text{i. } 0 \in I,$$

$$\text{ii. } x * y \in I \text{ and } y \in I \text{ imply } x \in I, \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

Definition 4.1.5.6:

Let X be a BH-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies:
 $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.5.7:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BH-algebra. and A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy BH-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

$$1. \mu(0) \geq \mu(x), \text{ for all } x \in X,$$

$$2. \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in X,$$

4.1.6.d-algebras:

In 1999, Neggers J. and Kim H.S. and introduced the class of d-algebras which is a generalization of BCK(BCI)-algebras . Akram M .and Dar K.H. Showing what is fuzzy subalgebra fuzzy ideal for d-algebras.

Definition 4.1.6.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **d-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $0 * x = 0$,
- (3) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ implies $x = y$.

Example 4.1.6.2:

Let $X = \{0,1,2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	2	0	2
2	1	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a d-algebra.

Definition 4.1.6. 3:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a d-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.6.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a d-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **d-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ implies $x \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$.
- iii. $x \in I$ and $y \in X$ implies $x * y \in I$, i.e., $I * X \subseteq I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.6.5:

Let X be a d-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies:
 $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.6.6:

Let X be a d-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy d-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$,
3. $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$,

Proposition 4.1.6.7:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a d-algebra, then the following hold :

(C_1) Every fuzzy d-ideal is a fuzzy BCK-ideal and every fuzzy BCK-ideal is a fuzzy d-subalgebra.

(C_2) Every fuzzy d-ideal of d-algebra is a fuzzy d-subalgebra.

Any BCK-algebra is a d-algebra but there are d-algebras which are not BCK-algebras.

Example 4.1.6.8: Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	2	0	2
2	1	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a d-algebra, but not a BCK-algebra, since

$(2 * (2 * 2)) * 2 = (2 * 0) * 2 = 1 * 2 = 2 \neq 0$. we define a fuzzy set $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.7, \mu(x) = 0.02$, where for all $x \neq 0$. It is easy to see that μ is a fuzzy sub algebra of X.

4.1.7. QS-algebras:

In 1999, Ahn and Kim introduced the notion of algebras QS- which is a generalization of Q-algebras. Saeid A.B. , Showing what is subalgebras and fuzzy subalgebra for QS-algebras.

Definition 4.1.7.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **QS-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(I) x * x = 0,$$

$$(II) x * 0 = x,$$

$$(III) (x * y) * z = (x * z) * y,$$

$$(IV) (x * y) * (x * z) = z * y,$$

Proposition 4.1.7.2:

Let X be a QS-algebra. Then for any x, y and z in X, the following relations hold:

$$(1) x \leq y \text{ implies } z * y \leq z * x,$$

$$(2) x \leq y \text{ and } y \leq z \text{ implies } x \leq z,$$

$$(3) x * y \leq z \text{ implies } x * z \leq y,$$

$$(4) (x * z) * (y * z) \leq x * y,$$

$$(5) x \leq y \text{ implies } x * z \leq y * z,$$

$$(6) 0 * (0 * (0 * x)) = 0 * x.$$

Definition 4.1.7.3:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a QS-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X. Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.7.4:

Let X be a QS-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies:
 $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.8. B-algebras:

In 2001, J.R Cho and H.S. Kim, introduced the notion of B-algebras which are related to several classes of algebras of interest such as BCH, BCK, BCI-algebras. Senapati T. Bhowmik M. and Pal M., Showing what is subalgebras, fuzzy subalgebra for B-algebras and showing what is ideal, fuzzy ideal for B-algebras.

Definition 4.1.8.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **B - algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(1) x * x = 0$$

$$(2) x * 0 = x$$

$$(3) (x * y) * z = x * (z * (0 * y)).$$

For brevity we also call X a **B-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$,

Proposition 4.1.8.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a B-algebra, then the following hold: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(B_1) (x * y) * (0 * y) = x,$$

$$(B_2) x * (y * z) = (x * (0 * z)) * y,$$

$$(B_3) x * y = 0 \text{ implies } x = y,$$

$$(B_4) 0 * (0 * x) = x,$$

$$(B_5) (x * z) * (y * z) = x * y,$$

$$(B_6) y * z = y * (0 * (0 * z)),$$

$$(B_7) x * z = y * z \text{ implies } x = y,$$

$(B_8) 0 * x = 0 * y \text{ implies } x = y.$

Example 4.1.8.3:

Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	2	1	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	1	2	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a B-algebra.

Definition 4.1.8.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a B-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.8.5

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a B-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **B-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$,
- iii. $x \in I$ and $y \in X$ imply $x * y \in I$, i.e., $I * X \subseteq I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.8.6:

Let X be a B-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies:
 $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.8.7:

Let X be a B-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy B-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$,

4.1.9.Q-algebras:

In 2001, Neggers J., Ahn S. S. and Kim H. S. , introduced a new notion, called Q-algebra, which is a generalization of BCH / BCI / BCK-algebras and find subalgebra, ideal. found fuzzy Q-subalgebra and fuzzy Q-ideal by Mostafa S.M. Abd-Elanaby M.A. and Elgendy O.R.M..

Definition 4.1.9.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **Q-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(1) x * x = 0,$$

$$(2) 0 * x = 0,$$

$$(3) (x * y) * z = (x * z) * y.$$

For brevity we also call X a **Q-algebra**, We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.9.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a Q-algebra, then the following hold : for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(Q_1) (x * (x * y)) * y = 0$$

$$(Q_2) ((x * z) * ((x * z) * y)) * y = 0.$$

Example 4.1.9.3:

Let $X = \{0,1,2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	2	1
1	1	0	2
2	2	1	0

Then $(X;*, 0)$ is a Q-algebra.

Definition 4.1.9.4:

Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a Q-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **Q-subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.9.5:

Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a Q-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **Q-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Definition 4.1.9.6:

Let X be a Q-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy Q-subalgebra** of X if it satisfies:
 $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.9.7:

Let X be a Q-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy Q-ideal** of X if it satisfies: 1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$,

2. $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$,

Proposition 4.1.9.8:

Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a Q-algebra, then every fuzzy Q-ideal of Q-algebra is a fuzzy Q-subalgebra.

4.1.10. BZ-algebras:

In 2003, Zhang X., Wang Y. and Dudek W.A. , introduced the class of BZ-algebras which is a generalization of BCH, BCK (BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.10.1.:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BZ-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(1) ((x * z) * (y * z)) * (x * y) = 0,$$

$$(2) x * 0 = x,$$

$$(3) x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \text{ implies } x = y.$$

For brevity we also call X a **BZ-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.10.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BZ-algebra, then the following hold: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(1) x * x = 0,$$

$$(2) x \leq y \text{ then } x * z \leq y * z \text{ and } z * y \leq z * x,$$

$$(3) 0 * (x * y) \leq y * x,$$

$$(4) 0 * (0 * x) \leq x,$$

$$(5) (0 * x) * (y * x) = 0 * y.$$

Definition 4.1.10.3:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BZ-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.10.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BZ-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called an **ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

4.1.11. Subtraction algebras:

In 2005, Jun Y. B., Kim Y. H. and Roh E. H., introduced the class of subtraction algebras which is a generalization of BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.11.1:

By a **Subtraction algebra** we mean an algebra $(X; -, 0)$ with a single binary operation $(-)$ that satisfies the following identities: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(S_1) \quad x - (y - x) = x,$$

$$(S_2) \quad x - (x - y) = y - (y - x),$$

$$(S_3) \quad (x - y) - z = (x - z) - y.$$

The last identity permits us to omit parentheses in expressions of the form

$$(x - y) - z.$$

The **Subtraction** determines an order relation on X : $x \leq y$ if and only if $x - y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.11.2:

In a Subtraction algebra, the following are true. For all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(a_1) \quad (x - y) - y = x - y,$$

$$(a_2) \quad x - 0 = x \text{ and } 0 - x = 0,$$

$$(a_3) \quad (x - y) - x = 0,$$

$$(a_4) \quad x - (x - y) \leq y,$$

$$(a_5) \quad (x - y) - (y - x) = x - y,$$

$$(a_6) \quad x - (x - (x - y)) = x - y,$$

$$(a_7) \quad (x - y) - (z - y) \leq x - z,$$

$$(a_6) (x - y) - z = (x - z) - (y - z).$$

Definition 4.1.11.3:

Let $(X; -, 0)$ be a Subtraction algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x - y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.11.4:

Let $(X; -, 0)$ be a Subtraction algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called an **ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $a - x \in I$, for all $a \in I, x \in X$,
- ii. For all $x, y \in I$, whenever $x \vee y$ exists in X , then $x \vee y \in I$.

Definition 4.1.11.5:

Let X be a Subtraction algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies: $\mu(x - y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.11.6:

Let X be a Subtraction algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy ideal** of X if it satisfies: for all $x, y \in X$,

1. $\mu(x - y) \geq \mu(x)$,
2. For some $x \vee y$, imply $\mu(x \vee y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

4.1.12. BM-algebras:

In 2006, Kim C. B. and Kim H.S, introduced the notion of a BM-algebra which is a specialization of B-algebra. Saad A.B., introduced the notion of BM-subalgebra. and introduced the notion of fuzzy subalgebra of BM-algebras.

Definition 4.1.12.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BM - algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * 0 = x$,
- (2) $(z * x) * (z * y) = y * x$.

They defined a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.12.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BM-algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(BM_1) x * x = 0,$$

$$(BM_2) 0 * (0 * x) = x,$$

$$(BM_3) 0 * (x * y) = y * x,$$

$$(BM_4) (x * z) * (y * z) = x * y,$$

$$(BM_5) x * y = 0 \text{ if and only if } y * x = 0,$$

$$(BM_6) (x * y) * z = (x * z) * y.$$

Example 4.1.12.3:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	2	1
1	1	0	2
2	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BM-algebra.

Definition 4.1.12.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BM-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.12.5:

Let X be a BM-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies:
 $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.13.J-algebras:

In 2006, Is'eki K., Kim H.S. and Neggers J. , introduced the class of J-algebras which is a generalization of BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.13.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **J-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y \in X$,

$$x * (x * (y * (y * x))) = y * (y * (x * (x * y))).$$

Example 4.1.13.2:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	3
3	2	3	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a J-algebra.

Definition 4.1.13.3:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a J-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

4.1.14.BF-algebras:

In 2007, A. Walendziak ,introduced the class of BF-algebras which is related to several classes of algebras of interest such as BCH/ BCI/ BCK-algebras. Hadipour A.R, introduced the notion of fuzzy subalgebra of BF-algebras and introduced the notion of subalgebra of BF-algebras

Definition 4.1.14.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BF-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y \in X$,

1. $x * x = 0$,
2. $x * 0 = x$,
3. $0 * (x * y) = y * x$.

Proposition 4.1.14.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BF-algebra , then the following hold :for any $x, y \in X$,

$$(BF_1) 0 * (0 * x) = x$$

$$(BF_2) 0 * x = 0 * y, \text{ then } x = y$$

$$(BF_3) x * y = 0, \text{ then } y * x = 0$$

Example 4.1.14.3:

Let $X = \{0,1,2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	1	2
1	1	0	0
2	2	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BF-algebra, but is not BCH/BCI/BCK-algebra

Definition 4.1.14.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BF-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.14.5:

Let X be a BF-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies:
 $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.15. BE-algebras:

In 2007, H.S. Kim and Y.H. Kim, introduced the notion of BE-algebras and investigated several properties. Song S.Z., Jun Y.B. and Lee K.J., introduced the notion of ideal and fuzzy ideal of BE-algebras

Definition 4.1.15.1.:

Let $(X; *, 1)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (1) . Then $(X; *, 1)$ is called a **BE-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $x * x = 1$,
2. $x * 1 = 1$,
3. $1 * x = x$,
4. $x * (y * z) = y * (x * z)$.

For brevity we also call X a **BE-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 1$.

Proposition 4.1.15.2:

Let $(X; *, 1)$ be a BE-algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y, z \in X$,

- $$(BE_1) \quad (y * z) \leq (x * y) * (x * z),$$
- $$(BE_2) \quad x * (y * z) = (x * y) * (x * z),$$
- $$(BE_3) \quad 1 * (x * y) = (1 * x) * (1 * y).$$

Example 4.1.15.3:

Let $X = \{1, a, b, c, d, 0\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	1	a	b	c	d	0
1	1	a	b	c	d	0
a	1	1	a	c	c	d
b	1	1	1	d	c	c
c	1	a	b	1	a	b
d	1	1	a	1	1	a
0	1	1	1	1	1	1

Then $(X; *, 1)$ is a BE-algebra.

Definition 4.1.15.4:

Let $(X; *, 1)$ be a BE-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **BE-ideal** of X if it satisfies: *forall* $x, y, \in X$

- i. $y \in I$, and $x \in X$ imply $x * y \in I$
- ii. $x, y \in I$ and $z \in X$ imply $(x * (y * z)) * z \in I$.

Definition 4.1.15.5:

Let X be a BE-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy BE-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(x * y) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$,
2. $\mu((x * (y * z)) * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

4.1.16. WS-algebras:

In 2008, C.H. Park, Y.B. Jun and M.A. Öztürk introduced the class of WS-algebras which is a generalization of BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.16.1:

By a weak subtraction algebra (**WS-algebra**), we mean a triplet $(X; -, 0)$, where X is a nonempty set, $-$ is a binary operation on X and $0 \in X$ is a nullary operation, called zero element, such that : for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(W_1) (x - y) - z = (x - z) - y,$$

$$(W_2) x - 0 = x,$$

$$(W_3) x - x = 0,$$

$$(W_4) (x - y) - z = (x - z) - (y - z).$$

Note that every subtraction algebra is a WS-algebra, but the converse is not true in general

Example 4.1.16.2:

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ be a set with the following table.

Then $(X; -, 0)$ is a WS-algebra but it is not a subtraction algebra, since $b = b - (b - c) \neq c - (c - b) = c$.

-	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	a
b	b	b	0	0
c	c	c	0	0

subtraction algebra, since

Definition 4.1.16.3:

Let $(X; -, 0)$ be a WS-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X if $x - y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if $x - y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.16.4:

Let $(X; -, 0)$ be a WS-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called an **ideal** of X if it satisfies:

nonempty subset of X . I is

i. $0 \in I$,

ii. $x \in X$ and $y \in I$ if $x - y \in I$, then $x \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.17. TL-algebras:

In 2009, Sun S. and He F., introduced the class of TL-algebras which are a generalization of Q/BCH/BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.17.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra, a L-subset μ of X is said to be a **TL-algebra** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.17.2:

Let X be a BCK-algebra and μ be a L-subset of X , then a necessary and sufficient condition for μ is that every μ_t is a subalgebra of X , where $\mu_t = U(\mu, t) = \{x \in X : \mu(x) \geq t\}$, $t \in L = [0, 1]$.

Definition 4.1.17.3:

Let X be a BCK-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **TL-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(0) = 1$ for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.17.4:

Let X be a BCK-algebra, a L-subset μ of X is said to be a **TL-implicative ideal** of X if it satisfies

1. $\mu(0) = 1$ for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * x)) * z, \mu(z)\}$ for all $x, y, z \in X$.

4.1.18. CI-algebras:

In 2009, Meng B.L. and elat, introduced the notion of CI-algebras as a generation of BE-algebras. Gave the concept of ideal of CI-algebra and investigated some related properties of CI-algebras see.

Definition 4.1.18.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **CI-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $x * x = 0$,
2. $0 * x = x$,
3. $x * (y * z) = y * (x * z)$.

For brevity we also call X a **CI-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.18.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a **CI-algebra**, then the following hold: for any $x, y \in X$,

$$(CI_1) y * ((y * x) * x) = 0,$$

$$(CI_2) (x * 0) * (y * 0) = (x * y) * 0.$$

Example 4.1.18.3:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	1	3
2	0	0	0	3
3	0	1	2	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a CI-algebra.

Definition 4.1.18.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a CI-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.18.5:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a CI-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **CI-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. If $x \in X$ and $y \in I$, then $x * y \in I$, i.e., $X * I \subseteq I$,
- ii. If $x \in X$ and $y, z \in I$, then $(y * (z * x)) * x \in I$.

Definition 4.1.18.6:

Let X be a CI-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies:
 $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.18.7:

Let X be a CI-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy CI-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(x * y) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$,
2. $\mu((y * (z * x)) * x) \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(z)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

4.1.19.KU-algebras:

In 2009, C. Prabpayak and U. Leerawat, introduced the concept of KU-algebra and investigated some related properties. S.M. Mostafa, and et al. they introduced the concepts of fuzzy KU-subalgebra and fuzzy KU-ideal in KU-algebra and investigated some related properties.

Definition 4.1.19.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **KU-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $(x * y) * ((y * z) * (x * z)) = 0$,
- (2) $x * 0 = 0$,
- (3) $0 * x = x$,
- (4) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$.

In a KU-algebra X , We define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $y * x = 0$.

Lemma 4.1.19.2:

Every KU-algebra X satisfies the following conditions:

- (1) $x * (y * z) = y * (x * z)$, for arbitrary $x, y, z \in X$.

(2) $x * x = 0$, for arbitrary $x \in X$.

Example 4.1.19.3:

Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ in which the operation ($*$) be defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	0	3	4
2	0	1	0	3	4
3	0	0	0	0	4
4	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X;*,0)$ is a KU-algebra.

Proposition 4.1.19.4:

Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a KU-algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $z * (x * z) = 0$.
2. $x \leq y$ implies $y * z \leq x * z$ and $z * y \leq z * x$.
3. $z * (y * x) = y * (z * x)$.
4. $y * ((y * x) * x) = 0$.

Definition 4.1.19.5:

Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a KU-algebra X and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **KU-subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$, i.e., S is closed under the binary operation ($*$) of X .

Definition 4.1.19.6:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a KU-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **KU-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.19.7:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a KU-algebra. Then any KU-ideal of X is a KU-subalgebra of X .

Definition 4.1.19.8:

Let X be a KU-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies: $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.19.9:

Let X be a KU-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy KU-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.19.10:

Let μ be a fuzzy KU-ideal of a KU-algebra X , for all $x, y, z \in X$

1. If $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$.
2. If the inequality $x * y \leq z$ hold in X , then $\mu(y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(z)\}$.
3. $\mu(x * (x * y)) \geq \mu(y)$.

Proposition 4.1.19.11. :

A fuzzy subset μ in a KU-algebra X is a fuzzy sub-algebra of X , if and only if, for any

$t \in [0, 1]$, $\mu_t \in U(\mu, t)$ is a sub-algebra of X when $U(\mu, t) \neq \phi$.

Proposition 4.1.19.12:

A fuzzy subset μ in a KU-algebra X is a fuzzy KU-ideal of X , if and only if, it satisfies, for any $t \in [0, 1]$, $U(\mu, t) \neq \phi$ implies $U(\mu, t)$ is a KU-ideal of X .

4.1.20.AC-algebras:

In 2009, J. Soontharanon and U. Leerawat, introduced the notion of AC-algebras which are a generalization of /QS/BCH/BM/BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.20.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called an **AC-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * (y * z) = (x * y) * z$,
- (2) $x * y = y * x$,
- (3) $x * y = 0$ if and only if $x = y$.

Now, we give some fundamental properties of **AC-algebras**.

Proposition 4.1.20.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an AC -algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$,
2. $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$
3. $x * 0 = x$,
4. $0 * (x * y) = (0 * x) * (0 * y)$,
5. $((x * z) * (y * z)) * (x * y) = 0$,
6. $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$,
7. $x * y = 0$ if and only if $(x * z) * (y * z) = 0$,
8. $x * y = 0$ if and only if $(z * x) * (z * y) = 0$.

Example 4.1.20.3:

Let $X = \{(0,0), (0, 1), (1,0), (1,1)\}$ in which $(*)$ be defined by the following table:

*	(0,0)	(0,1)	(1,0)	(1,1)
(0,0)	(0,0)	(0,1)	(1,0)	(1,1)
(0,1)	(0,1)	(0,0)	(1,1)	(1,0)
(1,0)	(1,0)	(1,1)	(0,0)	(0,1)
(1,1)	(1,1)	(1,0)	(0,1)	(0,0)

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a AC-algebra.

Definition 4.1.20.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an AC-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.20.5:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an AC-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called an **ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.20.6:

S is a subalgebra of an AC-algebra X if and only if S is an ideal of X .

4.1.21. GT-algebras:

In 2009, Kim J. Kim, Y. and E.H. Roh, introduced the class of GT-algebras which are a generalization of Q/QS/BCH/BM/BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.21.1:

A Generalized Tarski algebra (**GT-algebra**, for short) is an algebra $(X; \rightarrow, 1)$ with a binary operation (\rightarrow) and a constant (1) such that: for that: , for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(T_1) 1 \rightarrow x = x,$$

$$(T_2) x \rightarrow x = 1,$$

$$(T_3) x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z) = (x \rightarrow y) \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z).$$

Given a **GT-algebra** A , if it satisfies the condition

$$(T_4) (x \rightarrow y) \rightarrow y = (y \rightarrow x) \rightarrow x.$$

Proposition 4.1.21.2:

We call the algebra a Tarski algebra. In a Tarski algebra A we can define an order relation (\leq) by setting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 1$. It is well known that $(X; \rightarrow)$ is an ordered set.

Proposition 4.1.21.3:

Let $(X; \rightarrow, 1)$ be a GT-algebra, then for all $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $x \leq 1$,
2. $x \leq y \rightarrow z$,
3. $x \rightarrow (x \rightarrow y) = x \rightarrow y$,
4. $x \leq (x \rightarrow y) \rightarrow y$,
5. $x \leq y$ if and only if $z \rightarrow x \leq z \rightarrow y$.

4.1.22. TM-algebras:

The notion of TM-algebras was formulated first in 2010 by Megalai and Tamilarasi, introduced the notion of TM-algebras, which is a generalization of BCH /BCI/BCK/Q-algebras and investigated several properties and found ideal, subalgebra, found fuzzy subalgebra and found fuzzy ideal.

Definition 4.1.22.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **TM-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * 0 = x$,
- (2) $(x * y) * (x * z) = z * y$.

For brevity we also call X a **TM-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.22.2 :

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an TM-algebra, then the following hold: for any $x, y \in X$,

$$(L_1) \quad x * x = 0,$$

$$(L_2) \quad (x * y) * x = 0 * y$$

$$(L_3) \quad x * (x * y) = y.$$

Example 4.1.22.3: Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
---	---	---	---	---

0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a TM-algebra.

Definition 4.1.22.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an TM-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.22.5:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an TM-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **TM-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * z \in I$ and $z * y \in I$ imply $x * y \in I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Definition 4.1.22.6:

Let X be a TM-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies: $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.22.7:

Let X be a TM-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is said to be a **fuzzy TM-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x * z), \mu(z * y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.22.8:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a TM-algebra, then the following hold :

(TM_1) Every fuzzy TM-ideal of TM-algebra X is a fuzzy BCK-ideal.

(TM_2) The intersection of any set of TM-ideal in TM-algebra is also a fuzzy TM-ideal.

4.1.23.SU-algebras:

In 2011, KeawrahunS. and LeerawatU., introduced the class of SU-algebras which are a generalization of Q/ BCH/BCK (BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.23.1:

ASU-algebra is a non-empty set X with a constant 0 and a single binary operation $(*)$ satisfying the following for any $x, y, z \in X$

- $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (y * z) = 0$;
- $x * 0 = x$;
- if $x * y = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$.

Example 4.1.23.2: Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X, *, 0)$ is a SU-algebra.

Definition 4.1.23.3:

A binary relation " \leq " on X can be defined as $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.23.4:

Let $(X, *, 0)$ be a SU-algebra, then the following hold: for any $x, y \in X$,

- $x * x = 0$,
- $x * y = y * x$,
- $((x * y) * x) * y = 0$.

Definition 4.1.23.5:

A non-empty subset S of a SU-algebra X is said to be a **subalgebra** if $x * y \in S \forall x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.23.6:

A fuzzy subset μ in a SU-algebra X is said to be a **FuzzySU-subalgebra** of X if

$$\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

Example 4.1.23.7:

Consider the SU-algebra $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in (Example 4.1.23.2) and μ is the fuzzy subset of X defined by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.1 & ; x = 1, 2 \\ 0.3 & ; x = 0, 3 \end{cases}$. Then μ is fuzzy SU-subalgebra of X .

4.1.24. BCL-algebras:

In 2011, Liu Y. , introduced the class of BCL-algebras which are a generalization of BCH/BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.24.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BCL-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ implies $x = y$
- (3) $\left(((x * y) * z) * ((x * z) * y) \right) * ((z * y) * x) = 0$.

For brevity we also call X a **BCL-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.24.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an BCL-algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y \in X$,

(BCL_1) If $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$, then the BCL-algebra is a BCH-algebra.

(BCL_2) Any a (BCH/BCK(BCL))-algebra is a BCL-algebra .

(BCL_3) BCK-algebraic class \subset BCI-algebraic class \subset BCH-algebraic class \subset BCL-algebraic class.

Example 4.1.24.3:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	1
2	2	3	0	2
3	3	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCL-algebra.

4.1.25. BCL⁺-algebras:

In 2012, Liu Y. , introduced the class of BCL⁺-algebras which are a generalization of BCH/BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.25.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BCL⁺-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ implies $x = y$
- (3) $((x * y) * z) * ((x * z) * y) = (z * y) * x$.

For brevity we also call X a **BCL⁺-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Such definition ,clearly ,the BCL⁺-algebra is a generalization of the BCL-algebra, imple a BCL-algebra is BCL⁺-algebra ,however the converse is not true.

Proposition 4.1.25.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCL^+ -algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y \in X$,

(BCL_1) If $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$, then the BCL^+ -algebra is a BCH-algebra.

(BCL_2) Any a (BCH/BCK(BCL))-algebra is a BCL^+ -algebra .

(BCL_3) BCK-algebraic class \subset BCI-algebraic class \subset BCH-algebraic class \subset BCL^+ -algebraic class.

Example 4.1.25.3:

Let $X=\{0,1,2,3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	1	0	0	0
1	0	1	3	3
2	3	1	1	1
3	1	3	3	1

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCL^+ -algebra .

4.1.26. Coxeter algebras:

In 2012, Kim H. S., Kim Y. H. and NeggersJ., introduced the class of Coxeteralgebras which are a generalization of Q /QS/BCH/BM /BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.26.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a generalized **Coxeter-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $x * 0 = x$,
- (3) $(x * y) * z = x * (y * z)$.

Proposition 4.1.26.2:

If $(X; *, 0)$ is a Coxeter-algebra, then it is a B-algebra.

4.1.27. G-algebras:

In 2012 Bandru and Rafi, introduced a new notion, called G-algebras, which is a generalization of QS-algebras and some properties and subalgebra.

Definition 4.1.27.1:

A non-empty set X with a constant 0 and a binary operation $(*)$ is said to be **G-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms:

$$G_1: x * x = 0$$

$$G_2: x * (x * y) = y, \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

A G-algebra is denoted by $(X, *, 0)$

Example 4.1.27.2:

Let $X = \{R - \{-n\}, 0 \neq n \in Z^+\}$ where R is the set of real numbers and Z^+ be the set of all positive integers. Define a binary operation $(*)$ on X by $x * y = \frac{n(x-y)}{n+y}$ then $(X, *, 0)$ is a G-algebra.

Proposition 4.1.27.3:

every QS-algebra is a G-algebra but converse need not be true.

Example 4.1.27.4:

Let $A = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $*$ is defined by:

*	0	1	2
0	0	1	2
1	1	0	2
2	2	1	0

Then $(A, *, 0)$ is a G-algebra but not a QS-algebra because

$$(0 * 1) * 2 = 1 * 2 = 2 \neq 1 = 2 * 1 = (0 * 2) * 1.$$

Proposition 4.1.33.5:

Let $(X, *, 0)$ be an G-algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y, z \in X$,

- (i) $x * 0 = x$,
- (ii) $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- (iii) $0 * (0 * x) = x$,
- (iv) $x * y = 0$ implies $x = y$,
- (v) $0 * x = 0 * y$ implies $x = y$.

Theorem 4.1.27.6:

Let $(A, *, 0)$ be a G-algebra. Then the following are equivalent:

- (i) $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$ for all $x, y, z \in A$.
- (ii) $(x * y) * (x * z) = z * y$ for all $x, y, z \in A$.

Theorem 4.1.27.7:

If $(A, *, 0)$ be a G-algebra satisfying $(x * y) * (0 * y) = x$ for any $x, y \in A$ then $x * z = y * z$ implies $x = y$.

Definition 4.1.27.8:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a G-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.27.9:

Let $A = \{ \langle x, \alpha_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be a fuzzy set in X , where X is a G-subalgebra. Then the set A is a fuzzy subalgebra over the binary operator $*$ if it satisfies the condition $\alpha_A(x * y) \geq \min \{ \alpha_A(x), \alpha_A(y) \}$ for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.28. BO-algebras:

In 2012, Kim C.B. and Kim H.S. , introduced the notion of BO-algebras

Definition 4.1.28.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BO-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $x * 0 = x$,
- (3) $x * (x * y) = (x * y) * (x * y)$.

4.1.29. KK-algebras:

In 2012, S. Asawasamrit and Sudprasert A., introduced the notion of KK-algebras and investigate its properties.

Definition 4.1.29.1[16]:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **KK-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $(x * y) * ((y * z) * (x * z)) = 0$,
- (2) $0 * x = x$,
- (3) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ implies $x = y$.

For brevity we also call X a **KK-algebra**. We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting

$$x \leq y \text{ if and only if } y * x = 0.$$

Proposition 4.1.29.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an BCL-algebra, then the following hold: for any $x, y \in X$,

- (KK_1) $x * ((x * y) * y) = 0$,
- (KK_2) $x * x = 0$,
- (KK_3) $x * (y * z) = y * (x * z)$,
- (KK_4) $((x * y) * y) * y = x * y$,
- (KK_5) $(x * y) * 0 = (x * 0) * (y * 0)$.
- (KK_6) $(x * y) * ((z * x) * (z * y)) = 0$

Example 4.1.29.3:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a

KK-algebra.

Definition 4.1.29.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a
is called a

*	0	1	2
0	0	1	2
1	0	0	2
2	2	2	0

KK-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.29.5:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an
called a **KK-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

KK-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * y \in I$ and $x \in I$ imply $y \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.30. BRK-algebras:

The notion of BRK-algebra is introduced which is a generalization of BCK /BCI /BCH / Q / QS/ BM-algebras. In 2012 Bandar R.K. and Mukherjee N.P. Also found in the same year subalgebra and ideal to BRK-algebras .

Definition 4.1.30.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BRK-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $x * 0 = x$,
- (2) $(x * y) * x = 0 * y$.

For brevity we also call **XaBRK-algebra**, We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.30.2:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BRK-algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(R_1) \quad x * x = 0$$

$$(R_2) \quad x * y = 0 \text{ implies } 0 * x = 0 * y,$$

$$(R_3) \quad 0 * (x * y) = (0 * x) * (0 * y),$$

$$(R_4) \quad x * (x * y) = x * y,$$

$$(R_5) \quad (x * y) * (x * z) = z * y.$$

Example 4.1.30.3:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	2	2
1	1	0	0
2	2	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BRK-algebra.

Definition 4.1.30.4:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BRK-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.30.5:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BRK-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **BRK-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. $0 \in I$,
- ii. $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.1.31. I-algebras:

In 2012, Tanaka S. , introduced the class of I-algebras which are a generalization of Q/QS/BCH/BM/BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.1.31.1:

Let $(X; \succ, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation (\succ) and a constant (0) . Then $(X; \succ, 0)$ is a generalized **I-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $1 \succ x = x$,
- (2) $x \succ 1 = 1$,
- (3) $(x \succ y) \succ y = (y \succ x) \succ x$,
- (4) $x \succ (y \succ z) = 1$ implies $y \succ (x \succ z) = 1$.

Proposition 4.1.31.2 :

Let $(X; \succ, 0)$ be an I-algebra, then the following hold :for any $x, y \in X$,

- (G_1) $x \succ x = 1$,
- (G_2) $x \succ y = 1$ and $y \succ x = 0$ implies $x = y$,
- (G_3) $x \succ (y \succ x) = 1$,
- (G_4) $x \succ ((x \succ y) \succ y) = 1$,
- (G_5) $x \succ (z \succ ((x \succ y) \succ y)) = 1$,
- (G_6) $x \succ y = 1, y \succ z = 1$ imply $x \succ z = 1$,
- (G_7) $x \leq (x \succ y) \succ y$,
- (G_8) $y \leq (x \succ y) \succ y$,
- (G_9) $x \leq y$ imply $y \succ z \leq x \succ z$,
- (G_{10}) $x \leq z, y \leq z$ imply $(x \succ y) \succ y \leq z$.

4.1.32. BP-algebras:

In 2013, The concept of a BP-algebra introduced by Ahn S. S. and Han J. S. , which is another generalization of B-algebra.

Definition 4.1.32.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **BP-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x * x = 0$,
- (2) $x * (x * y) = y$,
- (3) $(z * x) * (z * y) = y * x$.

Example 4.1.32.2:

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	a	0	c	b
b	b	c	0	a
c	c	b	a	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BP-algebra.

Theorem 4.1.32.3:

If $(X; *, 0)$ is a BP-algebra, then the following hold: for any $x, y \in X$,

- (i). $0 * (0 * x) = x$,
- (ii). $0 * (y * x) = x * y$,
- (iii). $x * 0 = x$,
- (iv). $x * y = 0$ implies $y * x = 0$,
- (v). $0 * x = 0 * y$ implies $x = y$,
- (vi). $0 * x = y$ implies $0 * y = x$,

(vii). $0 * x = x$ implies $x * y = y * x$.

4.1.33. KUS-algebras:

In 2013, Mostafa S.M., Abdel Naby M.A., Abdel Halim F. and Hameed A.T., introduce and study new algebraic structure, called KUS-algebra and investigate some of its properties.

Definition 4.1.33.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a nonempty set with a single binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) of X . Then

$(X; *, 0)$ is called a **KUS-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(KUS_1) : (z * y) * (z * x) = y * x,$$

$$(KUS_2) : 0 * x = x,$$

$$(KUS_3) : x * x = 0,$$

$$(KUS_4) : x * (y * z) = y * (x * z).$$

In X we can define a binary relation (\leq) by $x \leq y$ if and only if $y * x = 0$.

Example 4.1.33.2:

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	a	b	c	d
a	d	0	a	b	c
b	c	d	0	a	b
c	b	c	d	0	a
d	a	b	c	d	0

It is easy to show that $(X; *, 0)$ is KUS-algebra.

Example 4.1.33.3:

Let $(Z; *, 0)$ be the set of all integers in which $(*)$ be given by $x * y = y - x$, for all $x, y \in Z$.

$(Z; *, 0)$ is a KUS-algebra.

A KU-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called KUS-algebra if it satisfies:

$$(7) (z * y) * (z * x) = (y * x).$$

Now, we give some properties and theorems of KUS-algebras.

Proposition 4.1.33.4:

Let X be a KUS-algebra. Then the following holds: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

a) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$,

b) $x * (y * x) = y * 0$,

c) $(x * y) = 0$ implies that $x * 0 = y * 0$,

d) $(x * y) * 0 = y * x$,

e) $x * 0 = 0$ implies that $x = 0$,

f) $x = 0 * (0 * x)$,

g) $0 * (x * y) = (0 * x) * (0 * y)$,

h) $x * z = y * z$ implies that $x * 0 = y * 0$.

Proposition 4.1.33.5:

Let X be a KUS-algebra. A relation (\leq) on X defined by $x \leq y$ if $y * x = 0$. Then (X, \leq) is a partially ordered set.

Proposition 4.1.33.6:

Let X be a KUS-algebra. Then the following holds: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $x * y \leq z$ imply $z * y \leq x$,

2. $x \leq y$ implies that $z * x \leq z * y$,

$$3. y * [(y * z) * z] = 0,$$

$$4. (x * z) * (y * z) \leq (y * x),$$

$$5. x \leq y \text{ and } y \leq z \text{ imply } x \leq z,$$

$$6. x \leq y \text{ implies } x * z \leq y * z.$$

Proposition 4.1.33.7 :

Every KUS-algebra X satisfying $x * (x * y) = x * y$ for all $x, y \in X$ is a trivial algebra.

Definition 4.1.33.8:

Let I be a nonempty subset of X, I is called an **ideal** of X if, for all $x, y \in X$

$$(I_1) 0 \in I,$$

$$(I_2) x \in I \text{ and } y * x \in I \text{ imply } y \in I.$$

Definition 4.1.35.9:

Let X be a KUS-algebra and let S be a nonempty subset of X. S is called a **KUS-subalgebra** of X if $x * y \in S$ whenever $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.35.10:

A nonempty subset I of a KUS-algebra X is called a **KUS-ideal** of X if it satisfies: for $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(I_{kus_1}) (0 \in I),$$

$$(I_{kus_2}) (z * y) \in I \text{ and } (y * x) \in I \text{ imply } (z * x) \in I.$$

Example 4.1.33.11:

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ in which (*) is defined by the following table:

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	a	0	c	b
b	b	0	0	a
c	c	b	a	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is KUS-algebra . It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, a\}$, $I_2 = \{0, b\}$, $I_3 = \{0, c\}$, and $I_4 = \{0, a, b, c\}$ are KUS-ideals of X

Proposition 4.1.33.12:

Let X be a KUS-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X containing 0 . Then I is a KUS-ideal of X if and only if : $(z * y) \in I, (z * x) \notin I \implies (y * x) \notin I, \text{ for all } x, y, z \in X$.

Corollary 4.1.33.13:

Let X be a KUS-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X containing 0 . Then :

(C_1) I is a KUS-ideal of X if and only if $(z * y) \in I, (y * x) \notin I \implies (z * x) \notin I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

(C_2) I is a KUS-ideal of X if and only if $(z * y) \in I, (z * x) \in I \implies (y * x) \in I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

(C_3) I is a KUS-ideal of X if and only if $(z * x) \in I, (y * x) \in I \implies (z * y) \in I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.33.14:

Every KUS-ideal of KUS-algebra X is a KUS-sub-algebra.

Proposition 4.1.33.15 :

Every KUS-ideal of X is an ideal of X .

In general, the converse of proposition (4.1.33.14) is not true . For example:

Example 4.1.33.16:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a KUS-algebra with the following Cayley table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	3	0	1	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	1	2	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is KUS-algebra . It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 3\}$ is an ideal of X , which is not a KUS-ideal of X , since $3 * 2 = 3 \in I, 2 * 1 = 3 \in I$ and $3 * 1 = 2 \notin I$.

Proposition 4.1.33.17:

Every KUS-ideal of KUS-algebra X is a KU-ideal of X .

In general, the converse of proposition (4.1.33.17) is not true .

For example 4.1.33.18:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a KUS-algebra with the following Cayley table:

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is KUS-algebra . It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 3\}$ is a KU-ideal of X , which is not a KUS-ideal of X ,since $3 * 2 = 3 \in I, 2 * 1 = 3 \in I$ and $3 * 1 = 2 \notin I$.

Proposition 4.1.33.19 :

Let $\{ I_i \mid i \in \Lambda \}$ be a family of KUS-ideals on KUS-algebra X . Then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is a KUS-ideal of X .

Proposition 4.1.33.20:

Let $\{ I_i \mid i \in \Lambda \}$ be a family of KUS-ideals of X , then $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is a KUS-ideal of X ,

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	3	0	1	2
2	4	3	0	1
3	1	2	3	0

KUS-ideals of KUS-algebra X , where $I_i \subseteq I_{i+1}$, for all $i \in \Lambda$.

Definition 4.1.33.21:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a KUS-algebra, A fuzzy subset μ of X be called a **fuzzy KUS-subalgebra** of X if, for all $x, y \in X$, $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

Definition 4.1.33.22 :

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a KUS-algebra, A fuzzy subset μ of X be called a **fuzzy KUS-ideal** of X if it satisfies the following conditions :

$$(Fkus_1) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x),$$

$$(Fkus_2) \mu(z * x) \geq \min\{\mu(z * y), \mu(y * x)\}.$$

Example 4.1.33.23:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ be given by:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	2	2	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a KUS-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.7 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$I = \{0, 1\}$ is a KUS-ideal of X . Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy KUS-ideal of KUS-algebra X .

Lemma 4.1.33.24:

Let μ be a fuzzy KUS-ideal of KUS-algebra X . If $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \leq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.33.25:

The intersection of any set of fuzzy KUS ideals of KUS-algebra X is also a fuzzy KUS-ideal of X .

Proposition 4.1.33.26:

The union of set $\{\mu_i: i \in \Lambda\}$ of fuzzy KUS-ideals of KUS-algebra X is also a fuzzy KUS-ideal of X , where $\mu_i \subseteq \mu_{i+1}$, for all $i \in \Lambda$.

4.1.34. BN-algebras:

In 2013, they define a *BN*-algebra and investigate some relations between *BN*-algebras and other algebras by Kim C. B. and Kim H. S. in 2013 as well as some properties of *BN*-algebras see, . Found both ideal and subalgebras to *BN*-algebras see .

Definition 4.1.34.1:

An algebra $(A; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is called a **BN-algebra** if

$$(B_1) \quad x * x = 0,$$

$$(B_2) \quad x * 0 = x,$$

$$(BN) \quad (x * y) * z = (0 * z) * (y * x)$$

hold for all $x, y, z \in A$.

Let $(A; *, 0)$ be a *BN*-algebra. We define a binary relation (\leq) on A by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$. It is easy to see that, for any $x \in A$, if $x \leq 0$, then $x = 0$.

Example 4.1.34.2:

Let \mathbb{R} be the set of real numbers and let $\mathfrak{R} = (\mathbb{R}; *, 0)$ be the algebra with the operation $*$ defined by:

$$x * y = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } y = 0 \\ y, & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then \mathfrak{R} is a *BN*-algebra.

Example 4.1.36.3:

Let $A = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and $(*)$ be defined by the following:

Then $(A; *, 0)$ is

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	1	1	0

a BN-algebra.

Let $(G; +, 0)$ be an abelian group. If we define $x * y = x - y$, for all $x, y \in G$, then $(G; *, 0)$ is a BN-algebra.

Example 4.1.34.4:

abelian group. If we define $x * y = x - y$, for all $x, y \in G$, then $(G; *, 0)$ is a BN-algebra.

Theorem

4.1.34.5:

If $(X, *, 0)$ is a BN-algebra, then $(X, *, 0)$ is a BF-algebra.

Remark 4.1.34.6:

The converse of Theorem above does not hold in general.

Example 4.1.34.7:

Let $X := \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	2	1	3
1	1	0	1	2
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	1	1	0

Then $(X, *, 0)$ is a BF-algebra, but not a BN-algebra, since

$$(3 * 1) * 3 = 2 \neq (0 * 3) * (1 * 3) = 1.$$

Proposition 4.1.34.8:

If $(A; *, 0)$ is a BN-algebra, then, for all $x, y \in A$,

- (i) $0 * (0 * x) = x$,
- (ii) $0 * (x * y) = y * x$,
- (iii) $y * x = (0 * x) * (0 * y)$,
- (iv) $x * y = 0 \Rightarrow y * x = 0$,
- (v) $0 * x = 0 * y \Rightarrow x = y$.

From, we obtain the following relation: $\mathbf{BM} \subset \mathbf{BN} \subset \mathbf{BF}$.

From now on, A always denotes a BN-algebra $(A; *, 0)$. We introduce the notion of an ideal in BN-algebras.

Definition 4.1.34.9:

A subset I of A is called an **ideal** of A if it satisfies

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$ for any $x, y \in A$.

We will denote by $\text{Id}(A)$ the set of all ideals of a BN-algebra A .

Example 4.1.34.10:

Let $\mathfrak{R} = (\mathbb{R}; *, 0)$ be the BN-algebra given in Example 1.50.2. Observe that $\text{Id}(\mathfrak{R}) = \{\{0\}, \mathbb{R}\}$. Indeed, let I be an ideal of \mathfrak{R} and suppose that $I \neq \{0\}$. Then $a \in I$ for some $a \in \mathbb{R} - \{0\}$.

Let $b \in \mathbb{R}$. Obviously, $b * a \in I$ and hence $b \in I$. Therefore, $I = \mathbb{R}$.

Proposition 4.1.34.11:

Let $I \in \text{Id}(\mathcal{A})$ and $x, y \in A$. If $x \leq y$ and $y \in I$, then $x \in I$.

A nonempty subset S of A is called a **subalgebra** of \mathcal{A} if $x * y \in S$ for any $x, y \in S$. It is easy to see that if S is a subalgebra of \mathcal{A} , then $0 \in S$,

Example 4.1.34.12:

Let $Z = (\mathbb{Z}; -, 0)$, where \mathbb{Z} is the set of all integers. We know that Z is a BN-algebra (see Example 1.50.4). Obviously, a nonempty subset $S \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$ is a subalgebra of Z if and only if

$a - b \in S$ for all $a, b \in S$.

Remark 4.1.34.13:

Consider the BN-algebra $\mathcal{A} = (A; *, 0)$ given in Example 1.50.3. We have $Id(\mathcal{A}) = \{\{0\}, \{0, 2\}, \{0, 3\}, \{0, 2, 3\}, A\}$. Observe that the ideal $I = \{0, 2, 3\}$ is not a subalgebra of \mathcal{A} and $S = \{0, 1\}$ is a subalgebra of \mathcal{A} but it is not an ideal.

Remark 4.1.34.14:

It is easy to prove that the intersection of an arbitrary number of ideals of a BN-algebra A is an ideal of A . It is also not hard to show that the union of an ascending sequence of ideals of A is an ideal of A .

4.1.35. PS-algebras:

In 2014, Priya T. and Ramachandran T, introduced the class of PS-algebras, which is a generalization of BCI / BCK / Q / KU / d- algebras.

Definition 4.1.35.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **PS-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $x * x = 0$
2. $x * 0 = 0$
3. $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y, \forall x, y \in X$.

In **PS-algebras**, where $x \leq y$ is defined by $y * x = 0$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proposition 4.1.35.2:

In any PS-algebra $(X, *, 0)$, with $x \leq y$, the following holds good for all $x, y \in X$.

1. $x * (y * x) = y * (x * x)$
2. $y * (x * (y * x)) = 0$
3. $y * (y * (y * x)) = y * x$
4. $y * (x * (x * y)) = 0$.

$$5. (x * y) * 0 = (x * 0) * (y * 0)$$

$$6. (x * y) * x = (x * x) * y$$

Example 4.1.35.3:

Let $X = \{ 0,1,2 \}$ be the set with the following Cayley table.

*	0	1	2
0	0	1	2
1	0	0	1
2	0	2	0

Then $(X, *, 0)$ is a PS-algebra.

Definition 4.1.35.4:

Let S be a nonempty subset of a PS-algebra X , then S is called a **PS-subalgebra** of X if $x * y \in S$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.35.5: Let X be a PS-algebra and I be a subset of X , then I is called a **PS-ideal** of X if it satisfies following conditions:

$$1. 0 \in I$$

$$2. y * x \in I \text{ and } y \in I \Rightarrow x \in I.$$

Definition 4.1.35.6:

Let X be a non-empty set. A fuzzy subset μ of the set X is a **mapping** $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 4.1.35.7: Let X be a PS-algebra. A fuzzy set m in X is called a fuzzy PS-ideal of X if it satisfies the following conditions.

$$i) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$$

$$ii) \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(y * x), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

Definition 4.1.35.8:

A fuzzy set μ in a PS-algebra X is called a fuzzy PS-sub algebra of X if

$$\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

4.1.36. RG-algebras:

The notion of RG-algebras was formulated first in 2014 by Omar R.A.K . introduce the notion of RG-algebra which is a good generalization of some algebraic structures such as the medial (BCI\BCH-algebras), the BM and BF-algebras see,.

Definition 4.1.36.1: An algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **RG-algebra** if the following axioms are satisfied:

- (i) $x * 0 = x$.
- (ii) $x * y = (x * z) * (y * z) \forall x, y, z \in X$
- (iii) $x * y = y * x = 0 \text{ imply } x = y$.

Example 4.1.36.2:

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ and $(X, *)$ be the pair given by the table:

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	a	0	c	b
b	b	c	0	a
c	c	b	a	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an RG-algebra.

Proposition 4.1.36.3: In any RG-algebra the following hold:

- i) $0 * (y * x) = x * y$.
- ii) $0 * (0 * x) = x$.
- iii) $x * (x * y) = y$.
- iv) $x * y = (z * y) * (z * x) \forall x, y, z \in X$.

v) $x * y = 0$ if and only if $y * x = 0$.

Proposition 4.1.36.4: Every RG -algebra is a BCI-algebra.

The converse of this proposition may be not true.

Example 4.1.36.5:

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ in which $*$ is defined by:

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	b	b
a	a	0	b	b
b	b	b	0	0
c	c	b	a	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCI-algebra but it is not an RG-algebra because

$$0 * (b * c) = 0, c * b = a, \text{ then } 0 * (b * c) \neq c * b.$$

Proposition 4.1.36.6: In any RG-algebra X the following hold:

i) $(x * y) * (0 * y) = (x * (0 * y)) * y = x.$

ii) $x * (x * (x * y)) = x * y.$

iii) $(x * y) * z = (x * y) * ((z * y) * (0 * y))$

$$= ((x * z) * z) * (y * z) = ((x * y) * y) * (z * y)$$

$$= (x * z) * y.$$

Proposition 4.1.36.7:

Let (G, λ) be an abelian group then $(G, *, e)$ is an RG-algebra where e is the identity for the operation λ do as the zero of the operation $*$ and $x * y = x\lambda y^{-1}, \forall x, y \in G$.

Corollary 4.1.36.8:

Every $(Z_n; *, [0])$ is an RG-algebra.

Definition 4.1.36.9:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a RG -algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **RG-subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.36.10:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an RG-algebra, a non empty subset A of X is called an **ideal** of X if:

- i) $0 \in A$.
- ii) $x * y \in A$ and $0 * x \in A$ imply $0 * y \in A, \forall x, y \in X$.

Lemma 4.1.36.11: In an RG-algebra X every RG-ideal is a BCK-ideal.

Lemma 4.1.36.12: In a BCK-algebra any BCK-ideal is an RG-ideal.

Lemma 4.1.36.13: In any RG-algebra any BCK-ideal is an RG-sub algebra.

Corollary 4.1.36.14: Any RG-ideal in an RG-algebra X is an RG-sub algebra of X .

4.1.37. AT-algebras:

The notion of AT-algebras was formulated first in 2016 by Areej Tawfeeq Hameed. introduce the notion of AT-algebra which is a good generalization of some algebraic structures such as the medial (BCI/BCH-algebras),

Definition 4.1.37.1: An **AT-algebra** is a nonempty set X with a constant (0) and a binary operation $(*)$ satisfying the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (i) $(x * y) * ((y * z) * (x * z)) = 0$,
- (ii) $0 * x = x$,
- (iii) $x * 0 = 0$.

In what follows, let $(X; *, 0)$ denote an AT-algebra unless otherwise specified .

For brevity we also call X an AT-algebra. In X we can define a binary relation (\leq)

by: $x \leq y$ if and only if, $y * x = 0$.

Remark 4.1.37.2: $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra if and only if, it satisfies that: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

(i') : $(y * z) * (x * z) \leq x * y$,

(ii') : $x \leq y$ and $y \leq x$ imply $x = y$,

(iii') : $x \leq y$ if and only if, $y * x = 0$.

Example 4.1.37.3: Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

It is easy to show that $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra.

Proposition 4.1.37.4:

In any AT-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$;

- 1) $z * z = 0$,
- 2) $z * (x * z) = 0$,
- 3) $x * y = y * x = 0$ implies $x = y$,
- 4) $y * ((y * z) * z) = 0$,
- 5) $x * y = 0$ implies that $x * 0 = y * 0$,
- 6) $0 * x = 0 * y$ implies that $x = y$.

Proposition 4.1.37.5: In any AT-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$;

- a) $x \leq y$ implies that $y * z \leq x * z$,
- b) $x \leq y$ implies that $z * x \leq z * y$

c) $z * x \leq z * y$ implies that $x \leq y$ (left cancellation law).

Proof.

a) Since by (i), $(y * x) * ((x * z) * (y * z)) = 0$, but $x \leq y$ implies $(y * x) = 0$, then $0 * ((x * z) * (y * z)) = 0$. By (ii), we get $(x * z) * (y * z) = 0$, i.e; $y * z \leq x * z$.

b) Since $x \leq y$ implies $(y * x) = 0$, by (i), we obtain $(z * y) * ((y * x) * (z * x)) = 0$, but $(y * x) = 0$, then $(z * y) * (0 * (z * x)) = 0$. By (ii), we get $(z * y) * (z * x) = 0$, i.e; $z * x \leq z * y$

c) $x = 0 * x = (z * z) * x = z * (z * x) \leq z * (z * y) = (z * z) * y = 0 * y = y$. Δ

Proposition 4.1.37.6:

In any AT-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$;

a) $x * (y * z) = y * (x * z)$,

b) $(0 * x) * (y * x) = y * 0$,

c) $x = 0 * (0 * x)$,

d) $x * y \leq z$ imply $z * y \leq x$.

Proof.

a) By (i'), $(x * z) * z = (x * z) * (0 * z) \leq 0 * x = x$, and by proposition (2.6(a)), and (i'), it follows that $[(x * z) * z] * (y * z) \leq x * (y * z)$. By the transitivity of (\leq) gives $x * (y * z) \leq y * (x * z)$. And we replacing x by y and y by x , we obtain $y * (x * z) \leq x * (y * z)$. By the anti-symmetry of (\leq) , thus $y * (x * z) = x * (y * z)$.

b) $(0 * x) * (y * x) = (0 * y) * ((0 * x) * x) = (0 * y) * 0 = y * 0$.

c) $0 * x = 0 * (0 * x) = (0 * 0) * (0 * x) = 0 * (0 * (0 * x))$, then by proposition (2.5(6)), $x = 0 * (0 * x)$.

d) We know that $x * y \leq z$ imply $z * (x * y) = 0$, but $x * (y * z) = y * (x * z)$ by (a), we obtain $x * (z * y) = 0$, i.e; $z * y \leq x$. Δ

Example 4.1.37.7. :Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a set with the following table:

Then $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra.

Proposition 4.1.37.8. :

Let x be any element in AT-algebra X . Then $((x*0)*0)*x$ is a positive element of X for every $x \in X$, where $(x$ is a positive element of X if $x \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow x*0=0)$.

Proof. Since $((x*0)*0)*x*0 = (((x*0)*0)*0)*(x*0) = (x*0)*(x*0) = 0$. Therefore, $((x*0)*0)*x$ is a positive element of X . Δ

Definition 4.1.37.9: A nonempty subset S of an AT-algebra X is called an **AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X** if $x*y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.1.37.10: A nonempty subset I of an AT-algebra X is called an **AT-ideal of AT-algebra X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$.

AT₁) $0 \in I$;

AT₂) $x*(y*z) \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x*z \in I$.

Example 4.1.37.11. :

(a) Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d, e\}$ be a set with the following table:

*					

Then $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, a\}$ and $I_2 = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ are AT-ideals of X .

(b) Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

Then $(X, *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, 1\}$ and $I_2 = \{0, 3\}$ are AT-ideals of X .

Proposition 4.1.37.12. :

Every AT-ideal of AT-algebra X is an AT-subalgebra.

Proof. Let I be an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X , for all $x, y \in X$ and let $x, y \in I$, then $x * (0 * y) \in I$ and $0 \in I$ Hence by (ii), $x * y \in I$ Therefore I is an AT-subalgebra. \triangle

Proposition 4.1.37.13. :

Let I be AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X . Then I is an AT-ideal of X if and only if $y \in I$ and $x * z \notin I$ imply $x * (y * z) \notin I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proof. Let I be an AT-ideal of X and let $y \in I$ whereas $x * z \notin I$. Suppose that $x * (y * z) \in I$. By proposition (2.7(a)), we see that $y * (x * z) \in I$. Since I is an AT-subalgebra of X and $y \in I$, $x * (y * z) \in I$, a contradiction. So $x * (y * z) \notin I$.

Conversely, assume that if $y \in I$ and $x * z \notin I$ imply $x * (y * z) \notin I$ for all $x, y, z \in X$. Since I is an AT-subalgebra of X , then there is $y \in I$ which $0 = y * y \in I$. That is, $0 \in I$. Now, let $x * z \in I$ and $y \in I$. Assume that $(x * (y * z)) \in I$. Hence $x * z \in I$, contradiction. Therefore I is an AT-ideal of X . This completes the proof. \triangle

Proposition 4.1.37.14. :

Let I be an AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X . Then I is an AT-ideal of X if and only if, $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $x * z \notin I$ imply $y \notin I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proof. Let I be an AT-ideal of X and let $x * (y * z) \in I$, $x * z \notin I$. Suppose that $y \in I$. By proposition (2.7(a)), we have $y * (x * z) \in I$. Since I is an AT-subalgebra of X , thus $x * z \in I$, contradiction, this shows that $y \notin I$.

Conversely, assume that $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $x * z \notin I$ imply $y \notin I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$. Since I is an AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X , then there is $y \in I$ which $0 = y * y \in I$. Then $0 \in I$. Let $x * (y * z) \in I, y \in I$ and suppose that $x * z \notin I$. But $y * (x * z) = x * (y * z) \in I$ by proposition (2.7(a)), and $y \in I$, then $x * (y * z) \notin I$ by assumption, a contradiction. This proves that I is an AT-ideal of X . \triangle

Now, we introduce the concept of fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X and we give examples and results of it .

Definition 4.1.37.15: Let X be a nonempty set , a fuzzy subset μ of X is $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

Definition 4.1.39.16: Let X be an AT-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of AT-algebra X is called a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X if it satisfies : $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{ \mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.1.37.17: Let X be an AT-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of AT-algebra X is called a fuzzy AT-ideal of X if it satisfies :

$$FAT_1) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x) ;$$

$$FAT_2) \mu(x * z) \geq \min\{ \mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y, z \in X$$

Example 4.1.37.18. :

Consider $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with $*$ defined by the table

Then $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\mu(0) = t_0, \mu(1) = \mu(2) = t_1 \text{ and } \mu(3) = \mu(4) = t_2, \text{ where } t_0, t_1, t_2 \in [0, 1] \text{ and } t_0 > t_1 > t_2.$$

Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X .

Proposition 4.1.37.19. :

Let μ be a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X . μ_t is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X if and only if , for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is either empty or an AT-ideal of X .

Proposition 4.1.37.20.:

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of AT- algebra X . If μ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X if and only if , for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is either empty or an AT-subalgebra of X .

Proposition 4.1.37.21.:Every fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X .

Prof. Dr. Areej Tawfeeq Hameed

CHAPTER FOUR

SECTION TWO

4.2. Some Types of Algebras with some operation

In this section, the notions of several classes of algebras were introduced. Here we give a brief review of some algebras with more of operations such as MV, IS, C, K, etc..

4.2.1. MV-algebras:

In 1992, L.P. Belluce, introduced the class of MV-algebras which is a generalization of BCK-algebras. applied the concept of fuzzy subset to MV-algebras .

Definition 4.2.1.1:

Let $(X; \oplus, ', 0)$ be a set with a binary operation (\oplus) , $(')$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; \oplus, ', 0)$ is a **MV-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x \oplus (y \oplus z) = (x \oplus y) \oplus z$,
- (2) $x \oplus y = y \oplus x$,
- (3) $x \oplus 0 = x$,
- (4) $x' = x$,
- (5) $x \oplus 0' = 0'$,
- (6) $(x' \oplus y)' \oplus y = (y' \oplus x)' \oplus x$.

Example 4.2.1.2:

The set $[0,1]$ equipped with operations: $x \oplus y = \min\{1, x + y\}$, $x \otimes y = \max\{0, x + y - 1\}$. Then $(X; \oplus, \otimes, 1)$ is a MV-algebra.

Definition 4.2.1.3: Let X be a MV-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ in X is said to be a **fuzzy MV-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

1. $\mu(x \oplus y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.
2. $y \leq x$ implies $\mu(x) \leq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

4.2.2. IS-algebras:

In 1998, Y.B. Jun, E.H. Roh and X.L. Xin, , and , introduced the notion of IS-algebras and studied further properties of this algebra. applied the concept of fuzzy subset to IS-algebras see,

Definition 4.2.2.1:

Let $(X; \cdot, *, 0)$ be a set with two binary operation (\cdot) , $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; \cdot, *, 0)$ is a **IS-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (i) $(X; \cdot)$ is a semigroup,
- (ii) $(X; *)$ is a BCI-algebra ,
- (iii) $x \cdot (y * z) = (x \cdot y) * (x \cdot z)$ and $(x * y) \cdot z = (x \cdot z) * (y \cdot z)$.

Remark 4.2.2.2:

Note that, the IS-algebra is a generalization of the ring.

Example 4.2.2.3 :

Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ in which $(*)$ and (\cdot) are defined by the following tables:

\cdot	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	0	1	0	1

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	2
1	1	0	2	3
2	2	2	0	0
3	0	1	2	3

2	0	0	2	2
3	0	1	2	3

Then $(X, *, \cdot, 0)$ is a IS-algebra.

Definition 4.2.2.4:

Let $(X; *, \cdot, 0)$ be a IS-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if, $x * y \in S$, for any $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.2.2.5:

Let $(X; *, \cdot, 0)$ be a IS-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . I is called a **IS-ideal** of X if it satisfies:

- i. I is an ideal of a BCI-algebra X ,
- ii. $a \in X$ and $x \in I$ imply $a \cdot x, x \cdot a \in I$.

4.2.3. Heyting algebras:

In 1998, Yon Y. H. and Choi E. A. ,introduced the notion of Heyting algebras and some properties of Heyting algebras. Heyting algebras generalize the well-known idea of Boolean algebras and most simply defined as a certain type of lattice.

Definition 4.2.3.1:

A partially ordered set (L, \leq) is said to be a **lower semilattice** if every pair of elements in L has a greatest lower bound (meet); it is called to be an **upper semilattice** if every pair of elements in L has a least upper bound (join); the operations join and meet are denoted by \vee and \wedge respectively. If (L, \leq) is both an upper and a lower semilattice, then it is called to be a **lattice** .

Definition 4.2.3.2:

A lattice (L, \leq) is said to be **bounded** if there are element 0 and 1 in L such that for any x in L , $0 \leq x \leq 1$, which is equivalent to $x \wedge 0 = 0$ and $x \vee 1 = 1$. Two elements a, b of a **bounded lattice** are complements if $a \vee b = 1$, and $a \wedge b = 0$. In this case each a, b is the complement of the other.

Definition 4.2.3.3:

A bounded lattice $(L; \leq)$ is said to be a **Heyting algebra** if for any $a, b \in L$, there is an element $a \rightarrow b \in L$ satisfying $c \wedge a \leq b$ if and only if $c \leq a \rightarrow b$, for some $c \in L$.

Theorem 4.2.3.4:

Let $(L; \leq)$ be a bounded lattice. Then L is a Heyting algebra if and only if there is a map $\rightarrow: L \times L \rightarrow L ((a, b) \rightarrow (a \rightarrow b))$ satisfying the following:

- (i) $a \rightarrow a = 1$,
- (ii) $a \wedge (a \rightarrow b) = a \wedge b$,
- (iii) $b \wedge (a \rightarrow b) = b$,
- (iv) $a \rightarrow (b \wedge c) = (a \rightarrow b) \wedge (a \rightarrow c)$, for all $a, b, c \in L$.

Proposition 4.2.3.5:

Let $(L; \leq)$ be a Heyting algebra. Then

- (i) $a \leq b$ if and only if $a \rightarrow b = 1$,
- (ii) $b \leq a \rightarrow b$,
- (iii) $b \leq c$ implies $a \rightarrow b \leq a \rightarrow c$ and $c \rightarrow a \leq b \rightarrow a$,

- (iv) $a \rightarrow (b \rightarrow c) = (a \wedge b) \rightarrow c,$
- (v) $a \wedge (b \rightarrow c) = a \wedge ((a \wedge b) \rightarrow (a \wedge c)),$
- (vi) $(a \vee b) \rightarrow c = (a \rightarrow c) \wedge (b \rightarrow c),$
- (vii) $a \rightarrow (b \rightarrow c) = b \rightarrow (a \rightarrow c), \text{ for all } a, b, c \in L.$

4.2.4. BL-algebras:

In 1999, Turunen E., and Di Nola A., Georegescu G and Iorgulescu A. , introduced the notion of BL-algebras

Definition 4.2.4.1:

A BL-algebra is an algebra $A=(A; \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ with four binary operations $\wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow$ and two constant $0, 1$ such that $(A; \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ is a bounded lattice $(A; \otimes, 1)$ is commutative monoid and for all $a, b, c \in A,$

1. $c \leq a$ if and only if $a \otimes c \leq b,$
2. $a \wedge b = a \otimes (a \rightarrow b),$
3. $(a \rightarrow b) \vee (a \rightarrow b) = 1.$

Example 4.2.4.2:

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, 1\}$ in which $(\wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow)$ is defined by the following table:

\wedge	0	c	a	b	1	0	c	a	b	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	c	a	b	1
c	0	c	c	c	c	c	c	a	b	1
a	0	c	a	c	a	a	a	a	1	1
b	0	c	c	b	b	b	b	1	b	1
1	0	c	a	b	1	1	1	1	1	1

\otimes	0	c	a	b	1	0	c	a	b	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
c	0	c	c	c	c	0	1	1	1	1
a	0	c	a	c	a	0	b	1	b	1
b	0	c	c	b	b	0	a	a	1	1
1	0	c	a	b	1	0	c	a	b	1

is a

Then $(A; \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ BL-algebra.

4.2.5. pseudo effect algebras:

In 2001, Dvurečenskij A, Vetterlein T [37] introduced the notion of pseudo effect algebras .

Definition 4.2.5.1:

A structure $(E; +, 0, 1)$, where $+$ is a partial binary operation and $0, 1$ are constants, is called a **pseudoeffect algebra** if for all $a, b, c \in E$, the following hold

(P_1) : $a + b$ and $(a + b) + c$ exist if and only if $b + c$ and $a + (b + c)$ exist, and in this case, $(a + b) + c = a + (b + c)$.

(P_2) : There is exactly one $d \in E$ and exactly one $e \in E$, such that $a + d = e + a = 1$.

(P_3) : If $a + b$ exists, there are elements $d, e \in E$, such that $a + b = d + a = b + e$.

(P_4) : If $1 + a$ or $a + 1$ exists, then $a = 0$.

A pseudoeffect algebra is said to be commutative if for all $a, b \in E$, $a \perp b$ if and only if $b \perp a$, in which case $a + b = b + a$.

we may define two unary operations \sim and $-$ on E by requiring $a + a^\sim = a^- + a = 1$ for any $a \in E$.

Lemma 4.2.5.2:

Let $(E; +, 0, 1)$ be a pseudoeffect algebra. Then, the following hold in E for all $a, b, c \in E$:

(1) $a + 0 = 0 + a = a$.

(2) $a + b = 0$ implies $a = b = 0$.

(3) $0^\sim = 0^- = 1, 1^\sim = 1^- = 0$.

(4) $a^{\sim-} = a^{-\sim} = a$.

(5) $a + b = a + c$ implies $b = c$, and $b + a = c + a$ implies $b = c$.

(6) $a + b = c$ iff $a = (b + c^\sim)^-$ iff $b = (c^- + a)^\sim$.

In any pseudoeffect algebra E , one can define a binary relation \leq_N on E by $a \leq_N b$ $(\exists c \in E) a + c = b$. For all $a, b \in E$.

Lemma 4.2.5.3:

Let $(E; +, 0, 1)$ be a pseudoeffect algebra. Then, the following hold in E for all $a, a_1, b, b_1, c \in E$

(1) \leq_N is a partial order on E .

(2) $a \leq_N b$ iff $b^- \leq_N a^-$ iff $b^\sim \leq_N a^\sim$.

(3) If $a \perp b, a_1 \leq_N a$ and $b_1 \leq_N b$, then $a_1 + b_1$ exists.

(4) $a \perp b$ iff $a \leq_N b^-$ iff $b \leq_N a^\sim$.

(5) If $b \perp c$, then $a \leq_N b$ iff $a \perp c$ and $a + c \leq_N b + c$. If $c \perp b$, then $a \leq_N b$ iff $c \perp a$ and $c + a \leq_N c + b$.

4.2.6. β -algebras:

In 2002, Neggers J. and Kim H.S., introduced the notion of β -algebras also in the same year he found a subalgebra. found fuzzy subalgebra by Abu Ayub Ansari M see, found ideal and fuzzy ideal by Abu Ayub Ansari M see,

Definition 4.2.6.1:

A β -algebra is a non-empty set X with a constant (0) and two binary operations $(+)$ and $(-)$ satisfying the following axioms:

1. $x - 0 = x$.

2. $(0 - x) + x = 0$.

3. $(x - y) - z = x - (z + y) \forall x, y, z \in X$.

Example 4.2.6.2:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with constant 0 and two binary operations $+$ and $-$ are defined on X with the Cayley's table:

4.2.7.C-algebras:

In 2003, Swamy U.M. and et al, and , introduced the class of C-algebras satisfying certain identities and proved that .

Definition 4.2.7.1:

Let X be a set with three binary operations ($\wedge, \vee,$ and $'$) and a constant (0). Then $(X; \wedge, \vee, ', 0)$ is called a **C-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $x'' = x$,
- (2) $(x \wedge y)' = x' \vee y'$,
- (3) $(x \wedge y) \wedge z = x \wedge (y \wedge z)$,
- (4) $x \wedge (y \wedge z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z)$,
- (5) $(x \vee y) \wedge z = (x \wedge z) \vee (x' \wedge y \wedge z)$,
- (6) $x \vee (x \wedge y) = x$
- (7) $(x \wedge y) \vee (y \vee x) = (y \wedge x) \vee (x \wedge y)$.

Proposition 4.2.7.2:

Let $(X; \wedge, \vee, ', 0)$ be a C-algebra, then the following hold: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

- (D₁) $x \wedge x = x$,
- (D₂) $x \wedge y = x \wedge (x' \vee y) = (x' \vee y) \wedge x$,
- (D₃) $x \vee (x' \wedge x) = (x' \wedge x) \wedge x = x$,
- (D₄) $(x \vee x') \wedge y = (x \wedge y) \vee (x' \wedge y)$,
- (D₅) $x \vee x' = x' \vee x$,
- (D₆) $x \vee y \vee x = x \vee y$,
- (D₇) $x \wedge x' \wedge y = x \wedge x'$.

–	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2

2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Prof. Dr. Areej Tawfeeq Hameed

+	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2

2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; +, -, 0)$ is a β -algebra.

Henceforth by a β -algebra X , we mean a β -algebra $(X; +, -, 0)$ derived from a group or a β -algebra $(X; +, -, 0)$ derived from a B-algebra $(X, -, 0)$.

Definition 4.2.6.3:

A non-empty subset A of a β -algebra $(X, +, -, 0)$ is called a β -subalgebra of X , if

1. $x + y \in A, \forall x, y \in A$ and
2. $x - y \in A, \forall x, y \in A$.

Example 4.2.6.4:

Consider the β -algebra $(X, +, -, 0)$ in example 1.16.2. The subsets $\{0, 1\}$, $\{0, 2\}$ and $\{0, 3\}$ are β -subalgebras of X . But the subset $A = \{0, 1, 2\}$ is not a β -sub algebra of X , since $1 + 2 = 3 \notin A$.

Definition 4.2.6.5:

Let μ be a fuzzy set in a β -algebra X . Then μ is called a fuzzy β -subalgebra of X if

1. $\mu(x + y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \forall x, y \in X$.
2. $\mu(x - y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \forall x, y \in X$.

Definition 4.2.6.6:

A non-empty subset I of a β -algebra $(X, +, -, 0)$ is called a β -ideal of X , if

1. $0 \in I$,
2. $x + y \in I, \forall x, y \in I$, and
3. if $x - y$ and $y \in I$ then $x \in I \forall x, y \in X$.

Example 4.2.6.7:

In example (4.2.5.2). of β -algebra X , the subset $I_1 = \{0, 1\}$ is a β -ideal of X . But $I_2 = \{0, 1, 3\}$ is not a β -ideal of X (since $1 + 3 = 2 \notin I_2$.)

Definition 4.2.6.8:

Let μ be a fuzzy set in a β -algebra X . Then μ is called a fuzzy β -ideal of X if

1. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X$,
2. $\mu(x + y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \forall x, y \in X$, and
3. $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x - y), \mu(y)\} \forall x, y \in X$.

Example 4.2.6.9:

Consider the β -algebra $(X, +, -, 0)$ in example (4.2.6.2)

4.2.7. C-algebras:

In 2003, Swamy U.M. and et al, and, introduced the class of C-algebras satisfying certain identities and proved that .

Definition 4.2.7.1.:

Let X be a set with three binary operations (\wedge, \vee , and $'$) and a constant (0) . Then $(X; \wedge, \vee, ', 0)$ is called a **C-algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (8) $x'' = x$,
- (9) $(x \wedge y)' = x' \vee y'$,

- (10) $(x \wedge y) \wedge z = x \wedge (y \wedge z),$
- (11) $x \wedge (y \wedge z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z),$
- (12) $(x \vee y) \wedge z = (x \wedge z) \vee (x' \wedge y \wedge z),$
- (13) $x \vee (x \wedge y) = x$
- (14) $(x \wedge y) \vee (y \vee x) = (y \wedge x) \vee (x \wedge y).$

Proposition 4.2.7.2:

Let $(X; \wedge, \vee, ', 0)$ be a C-algebra, then the following hold: for any $x, y, z \in X,$

- $(D_1) x \wedge x = x,$
- $(D_2) x \wedge y = x \wedge (x' \vee y) = (x' \vee y) \wedge x,$
- $(D_3) x \vee (x' \wedge x) = (x' \wedge x) \wedge x = x,$
- $(D_4) (x \vee x') \wedge y = (x \wedge y) \vee (x' \wedge y),$
- $(D_5) x \vee x' = x' \vee x,$
- $(D_6) x \vee y \vee x = x \vee y,$
- $(D_7) x \wedge x' \wedge y = x \wedge x'.$

4.2.8.K-algebras:

In 2005, K.H. Dar , M. Akram and et al , introduced the notion of K-algebras and studied further properties of this algebra. Zhang Q. and Li S., find fuzzy ideal and fuzzy subalgebra of K-algebras.

Definition 4.2.8.1:

Let $(X; \cdot, *, 0)$ be a group in which each non-identity element is not of order 2. Then a **K-algebra** is a structure $K = (X; \cdot, *, 0)$ on a group X in which induced binary operation

$*$: $X \times X \rightarrow X$ is defined by $(x * y) = x \cdot y^{-1}$, and satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X,$

- (1) $(x * y) * (x * z) = (x * ((0 * z) * (0 * y) * x),$
- (2) $x * (x * y) = (x * (0 * y)) * x,$
- (3) $x * x = 0,$
- (4) $x * 0 = x,$
- (5) $0 * x = x^{-1}.$

\cdot	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	0	1	0	1
2	0	0	2	2
3	0	1	2	3

defined by :

Example 4.2.8.2 :

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ and (\cdot) be

	\cdot	0	1	2	3
0	\cdot	0	1	2	3
1	\cdot	0	1	2	3
2	\cdot	0	1	2	3
3	\cdot	0	1	2	3

Then $(X; *, \cdot, 0)$ is a K-algebra .

Definition 4.2.8.3:

Let $(X; *, \cdot, 0)$ be a K-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of $X.$ Then S is called a **subalgebra** of X if $x * y \in S,$ for any $x, y \in S.$

Definition 4.2.8.4:

A nonempty subset I of a K-algebra K is called an **ideal** of K if it satisfies:

- (i) $0 \in I,$
- (ii) $x * y \in I, y * (y * x) \in I \Rightarrow x \in I$ for all $x, y \in X.$

Definition 4.2.8.5:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a K-algebra and μ be a fuzzy subset of X . Then μ is called a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y \in X, a, b \in N$,

1. $\mu(x) = 1$,
2. $\mu(a \cdot x * b \cdot y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$,
3. $\mu(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

Proposition 4.2.8.6:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a K-algebra and μ be a fuzzy subset of X . Then μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X if and only if μ_t is a subalgebra of X , for all $t \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 4.2.8.7: Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a K-algebra and μ be a fuzzy subalgebra of X . Then μ is called a **fuzzy ideal** of X if for all $x, y \in X, \mu(x \cdot y) \geq \max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

The fuzzy set $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.8 & \text{if } x = 0, 2 \\ 0.5 & \text{if } x = 1, 3 \end{cases}$$

is a fuzzy β -ideal of X .

4.2.9. KS-algebras:

In 2006, Kim H.S. introduced the class of KS-algebras which is a generalization of BCK(BCI)-algebras. Prince Williams D.R. and el at. , applied the concept of fuzzy subset to KS-algebras.

Definition 4.2.9.1:

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a set with a binary operation $(*)$. Then $(X; \cdot, 0)$ is called a **semigroup** if (\cdot) is an associative binary operation .

Definition 4.2.9.2:

An algebraic system $(X, *, \cdot, 0)$ is called a **KS-semigroup** if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (1) $(X, *, 0)$ is a BCK algebra ,
- (2) (X, \cdot) is a semigroup ,
- (3) The operation (\cdot) is distributive (on both sides) over $(*)$, that is, for all $x, y, z \in X$,
 - (a) $x \cdot (y * z) = (x \cdot y) * (y \cdot z)$
 - (b) $(x * y) \cdot z = (x \cdot z) * (y \cdot z)$

Definition 4.2.9.3:

A nonempty subset Y of a KS-semigroup X with binary operations “ $*$ ” and “ \cdot ” is called a **sub KS-semigroup** if Y is closed under “ $*$ ” and “ \cdot ”, that is,

- (1) $x * y \in Y$ for all $x, y \in Y$, and
- (2) $x \cdot y \in Y$ for all $x, y \in Y$.

Definition 4.2.9.4:

Let X be a KS-semigroup and μ a fuzzy set in X such that for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $\mu(x \cdot y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, and
- (2) $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

Then μ is called a **fuzzy sub KS-semigroup** of X .

4.2.10. R₀-algebras:

In 2006, Y.B. Jun and L. Lianzhen, introduced the class of R_0 -algebras which are a generalization of Q/QS/BCH/BM/BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.2.10.1:

Let L is a bounded distributive lattice With order-reversing involution (\neg) and a binary operation (\rightarrow).

Then $(L; \wedge, \vee, \neg, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ containing the least element (0) and the largest element ($1 \neq 0$), is called a **R_0 -algebra** if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $a, b, c \in L$,

$$(R_1) \neg a \rightarrow \neg b = b \rightarrow a,$$

$$(R_2) 1 \rightarrow a = a,$$

$$(R_3) (b \rightarrow c) \wedge ((a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow (a \rightarrow c)) = b \rightarrow c,$$

$$(R_4) a \rightarrow (b \rightarrow c) = b \rightarrow (a \rightarrow c),$$

$$(R_5) a \rightarrow (b \vee c) = (a \rightarrow b) \vee (a \rightarrow c),$$

$$(R_6) (a \rightarrow b) \vee ((a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow (\neg a \vee b)) = 1.$$

Let L be a R_0 -algebra. For any $a, b \in L$, We define $a \otimes b = \neg(a \rightarrow \neg b)$ and $a \oplus b = \neg a \rightarrow b$. It is proved that (\otimes) and (\oplus) are commutative, associative, and $a \oplus b = \neg(\neg a \otimes \neg b)$, and

$(L; \wedge, \vee, \neg, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ is a residuated lattice.

Proposition 4.2.10.2:

For any elements x, y , and z of an R_0 -algebra L there exist the following properties :

$$(a_1) x \leq y \text{ if and only if } x \rightarrow y = 1,$$

$$(a_2) x \leq y \rightarrow x,$$

$$(a_3) \neg x = x \rightarrow 0,$$

$$(a_4) (x \rightarrow y) \vee (y \rightarrow x) = 1, (x \rightarrow y) \vee (y \rightarrow x) = 1,$$

$$(a_5) x \leq y \text{ implies } y \rightarrow z \leq x \rightarrow z \text{ and } z \rightarrow x \leq z \rightarrow y,$$

$$(a_6) ((x \rightarrow y) \rightarrow y) \rightarrow y = x \rightarrow y,$$

$$(a_7) x \vee y = ((x \rightarrow y) \rightarrow y) \wedge ((y \rightarrow x) \rightarrow x),$$

$$(a_8) x \otimes \square x = 0 \text{ and } x \oplus \square x = 1,$$

$$(a_9) x \otimes y \leq x \wedge y \text{ and } x \otimes (x \rightarrow y) = x \wedge y.$$

4.2.11. Algebras based on \mathcal{N} -function :

In 2012, Lee K.J. and Jun Y B., introduced the class of algebras based on \mathcal{N} -function which are a generalization of Q/QS/BCH/BM/BCK

Definition 4.2.11.1:

Denote by $F(X, [-1, 0])$ the collection of functions from a set X to $[-1, 0]$. We say that an element of $F(X, [-1, 0])$ is a negative-valued function from X to $[-1, 0]$ (briefly, \mathcal{N} -function on X).

By an \mathcal{N} -structure we mean an ordered pair (X, f) of X and an \mathcal{N} -function f on X .

Definition 4.2.11.2:

By a subalgebra of a BCK/BCI-algebra X based on \mathcal{N} -function f , we mean an \mathcal{N} -structure (X, f) in which f satisfies the following condition: for any $x, y \in X, f(x * y) = \vee \{f(x), f(y)\}$.

Definition 4.2.11.3:

By an ideal of a BCK/BCI-algebra X based on \mathcal{N} -function f (briefly, \mathcal{N} -ideal of X), we mean an \mathcal{N} -structure (X, f) in which f satisfies the following condition: for any $x, y \in X$,

$$f(0) \leq f(x) \leq \vee \{f(x * y), f(y)\}.$$

Proposition 4.2.11.4:

An \mathcal{N} -structure (X, f) is an \mathcal{N} -subalgebra (resp. ideal) of a BCK/BCI-algebra X if and only if every closed support of (X, f) related to α is a subalgebra (resp. ideal) of X for all $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$.

For our convenience, the empty set \emptyset is regarded as a subalgebra (resp. ideal) of X .

4.2.12. A^* -algebras :

In 2012, V. A. Babu, P. K. Rao and K. Moses., introduced the class of A^* -algebras which are a generalization of Q/QS/BCH/BM/BCK(BCI)-algebras.

Definition 4.2.12.1:

Denote by $F(X, [-1, 0])$ the collection of functions from a set X to $[-1, 0]$. We say that an element of $F(X, [-1, 0])$ is a negative-valued function from X to $[-1, 0]$ (briefly, \mathcal{N} -function on X).

By an \mathcal{N} -structure we mean an ordered pair (X, f) of X and an \mathcal{N} -function f on X .

Definition 4.2.12.2:

An algebra $(X, \wedge, *, (-)^\sim, (-)_\pi, 1)$ is an A^* -algebra if it satisfies: for $x, y, z \in X$,

- (i) $x_\pi \vee (x_\pi)^\sim = 1, (x_\pi)_\pi = x_\pi, \text{ where } x \vee y = (x^\sim \wedge y^\sim)^\sim,$
- (ii) $x_\pi \vee y_\pi = y_\pi \vee x_\pi,$
- (iii) $(x_\pi \vee y_\pi) \vee z_\pi = x_\pi \vee (y_\pi \vee z_\pi),$
- (iv) $(x_\pi \wedge y_\pi) \vee (x_\pi \vee (y_\pi)^\sim) = x_\pi,$
- (v) $(x \wedge y)_\pi = x_\pi \wedge y_\pi, (x \wedge y)^\# = (x^\# \vee y^\#), \text{ where } x^\# = (x_\pi \vee x^\sim_\pi)^\sim,$
- (vi) $x^\sim_\pi = (x_\pi \vee x^\#)^\sim, x^\sim^\# = x^\#,$
- (vii) $(x * y)_\pi = x_\pi, (x * y)^\# = (x_\pi)^\sim \wedge (y^\sim_\pi)^\sim$
- (viii) $x = y$ if and only if $x_\pi = y_\pi, x^\# = y^\#.$

4.2.13. CS-Algebras:

In 2012, Kim K.H., introduced the notion of CS-algebras .

Definition 4.2.13.1: By an CS-algebra $(X, \cdot, *, 1)$ with two binary operations “ \cdot ” and “ $*$ ” that satisfies the following axioms:

(CS₁) $S(X) = (X, \cdot)$ is a semigroup,

(CS₂) $C(X) = (X, *)$ is a CI-algebra,

(CS₃) $x \cdot (y * z) = x \cdot y * x \cdot z$ and $(x * y) \cdot z = x \cdot z * y \cdot z$ for any $x, y, z \in X$.

Example 4.2.13.2:

Let $X = \{1, a, b, c\}$ in which “ $*$ ” and “ \cdot ” are defined by:

$*$	1	a	b	c
1	1	a	b	c
a	1	1	b	c
b	1	a	1	c
c	1	1	1	1

\cdot	1	a	B	C
1	1	1	1	1
a	1	1	1	1
b	1	1	1	1
c	1	a	B	C

Then it is easy to check that $(X, \cdot, *)$ is an CS-algebra.

Proposition 4.2.13.3:

Let X be an CS-algebra. Then the following identities hold.

- (1) $x \cdot 1 = 1$ and $1 \cdot x = 1$ for all $x \in X$,
- (2) $x \leq y$ implies $a \cdot x \leq a \cdot y$ and $x \cdot a \leq y \cdot a$ for all $x, y, a \in X$,
- (3) $x \cdot (y \vee z) = x \cdot z \vee y \cdot z$ for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Definition 4.2.13.4:

Let X be an CS-algebra. A non-empty subset S of X is called a **subalgebra** of X if $x * y \in S$ and $x \cdot y \in S$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Let us define the center of a CS-algebra X , denoted by $\text{cent}(X)$, to be the set

$$\text{cent}(X) = \{x \in X \mid a \cdot x = x \cdot a \text{ for all } a \in X\}.$$
Theorem 4.2.13.5:

For any CS-algebra X , $\text{cent}(X)$ is a subalgebra of X .

Theorem 4.2.13.6:

Let X be a CS-algebra X and $a \in X$. Then the set $C(a) = \{x \in X \mid a \cdot x = x \cdot a\}$ is a subalgebra, and

$$\text{cent}(X) = \bigcap_{a \in X} C(a).$$
Definition 4.2.13.7:

A deductive system F of an CS-algebra X is said to be **closed** if $x \in F$ implies $x * 1 \in F$.

Theorem 4.2.13.8:

A deductive system of an CS-algebra X is closed if and only if it is a subalgebra of CS-algebra X .

4.2.14. MTL-algebras:

The concept of a MTL-algebras is a generalization of the concept of Q/OS/BCH/BM/BCK(BCI)-algebras in 2012, by Zhan and Dudek W.A. see,

Definition 4.2.14.1:

By a commutative, integral and bounded residuated lattice we shall mean a lattice $L = (L; \leq, \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ containing the least element (0) and the largest element (1 ≠ 0), and endowed with two binary operation (\otimes) (called product) and (\rightarrow) (called residuum) such that: for all $x, y, z \in L$,

- (1) \otimes is associative, commutative and isotone ,
- (2) $x \otimes 1 = x$
- (3) the Galois correspondence holds, that is, $x \otimes y \leq z$ if and only if $y \leq z$

Proposition 4.2.14.2:

In a commutative, integral and bounded residuated lattice, the following are true : for all $x, y, z \in L$,

- (1) $x \leq y$ if and only if $x \rightarrow y = 1$.
- (2) $0 \rightarrow x = x, 1 \rightarrow x = x, x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow x) = 1$,
- (3) $y \leq (y \rightarrow x) \rightarrow x$,
- (4) $x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z) = (x \otimes y) \rightarrow z = y \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z)$,
- (5) $x \rightarrow y \leq (z \rightarrow x) \rightarrow (z \rightarrow y), x \rightarrow y \leq (y \rightarrow z) \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z)$.

Proposition 4.2.14.3:

A MTL-algebra is a commutative, integral and bounded residuated lattice $L = (L; \leq, \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ satisfying the pre-linearity equation:

$$(x \rightarrow y) \vee (y \rightarrow x) = 1$$

In a MTL-algebra, the following are true:

- (1) $x \rightarrow (y \vee z) = (x \rightarrow y) \vee (x \rightarrow z)$
- (2) $x \otimes y \leq x \wedge y$,
- (3) $x' = x''', x \leq x'', x' \otimes x = 0$,
- (4) if $x \vee x' = 1$, then $x \wedge x' = 0$, where $x' = x \rightarrow 0$

Throughout this paper, L is a MTL-algebra unless otherwise specified.

4.2.15 HS-algebras:

In 2011, Lee S.M. and Kim K.H., introduced the notion of HS-algebras. the HS-algebra is a characterized and we obtained some properties of HS-algebras.

Definition 4.2.15.1:

Let $(X; \cdot, *, 0)$ be a set with two binary operation (\cdot) , $(*)$ and a constant (0) . Then $(X; \cdot, *, 0)$ is called a HS-algebra if it satisfies the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$

- (1) $(X; \cdot)$ is a semigroup ,
- (2) $(X; *)$ is a Hilbert-algebra ,
- (3) $x \cdot (y * z) = (x \cdot y) * (x \cdot z)$ and $(x * y) \cdot z = (x \cdot z) * (y \cdot z)$.

Example 4.2.15.2:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ and (\cdot) be defined by :

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	2	3
2	0	1	0	3
3	0	1	2	0

\cdot	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	0	1	0	1
2	0	0	2	2
3	0	1	2	3

Then $(X; *, \cdot, 0)$ is a HS-algebra .

4.2.16. SA-algebras :

In 2015 AL-Budarub A.T.H., introduce the notion of SA-algebras ,define its ideal and investigate some of its properties.

Definition 4.2.16.1:

The algebraic system $(X; +, -, 0)$ with two binary operations $(+)$ and $(-)$ and constant (0) is called **SA-algebra**, if it satisfies the following properties :for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- $(SA_1) x - x = 0,$
- $(SA_2) x - 0 = x,$
- $(SA_3) (x - y) - z = x - (z + y),$
- $(SA_4) (x + y) - (x + z) = y - z.$

In X we can define a binary relation (\leq) by $x - y = 0$ if and only if $x \leq y$:

Example 4.2.16.2:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set and the operations $(+), (-)$ are defined by the following tables:

+	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	2	3	0

2	2	3	0	1
3	3	0	1	2

Then $(X; +, -, 0)$ is a SA-algebra .

Lemma 4.2.16.3:

Let $(X; +, -, 0)$ be a SA-algebra. Then the following hold :for any $x, y, z \in X$,

1. $x = -(0 - x) = 0 - (-x) = -(-x)$,
2. $x + y = y + x$,
3. $x - y = -y + x$,
4. $0 - x = -x$,
5. $0 + 0 = 0, 0 - 0 = 0$,
6. $-(x - y) = -x + y$ and $-(x + y) = -x - y$,
7. $((x - z) + (z - y)) = x - y$ and $((x - z) - (y - z)) = x - y$.

Proposition 4.2.16.4:

Let $(G; \cdot, e)$ be a commutative group .If we define $(x + y) = xy, (x - y) = xy^{-1}, 0=e$, for any $x, y \in G$ then $(G; +, -, 0)$ is a SA-algebra.

Proposition 4.2.16.5:

Let S be a set .If we define $x + y = x, x - y = x$, and $0 \in S$, then $(S; +, -, 0)$ is a SA-algebra.

Remark 4.2.16.6:

SA-algebra \leftrightarrow β -algebra $+[(x + y) - (x + z) = y - z]$.

Definition 4.2.16.7:

Let X be a SA -algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X . S is called a **SA-subalgebra** of X if, $x, y \in S$.

-	0	1	2	3
0	0	3	2	1
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	1	0	3
3	3	2	1	0

nonempty subset of $x + y \in S$, whenever

Definition 4.2.16.8:

A nonempty subset I of SA-algebra X of X if it satisfies :for $x, y, z \in X$,

- (I₁) $0 \in I$,
- (I₂) $(x + z) \in I$ and $(y - z) \in I$ imply $(x + y) \in I$.

Example 4.2.16.9:

Let $(Z_6; +_6, -_6, \bar{0})$ be a set and the operations $(+_6), (-_6)$ are defined by the following tables:

+	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{5}$
$\bar{0}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{5}$
$\bar{1}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{0}$
$\bar{2}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{1}$
$\bar{3}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{2}$
$\bar{4}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{3}$
$\bar{5}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}$

-	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{5}$
$\bar{0}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{1}$
$\bar{1}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{2}$
$\bar{2}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{3}$
$\bar{3}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{4}$
$\bar{4}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{5}$

$\bar{5}$	$\bar{5}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{1}$	$\bar{0}$
-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------

Then $(Z_6; +_6, -_6, \bar{0})$ is a SA-algebra .It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{\bar{0}, \bar{3}\} = \langle \bar{3} \rangle$ and $I_2 = \{\bar{1}, \bar{2}, \bar{3}\} = \langle \bar{2} \rangle$ are SA-ideal of $(Z_6; +_6, -_6, \bar{0})$.

Proposition 4.2.16.10:

Every SA-ideal of SA-algebra X is SA-subalgebra of X.

Note that 4.2.16.11: The converse of Proposition (1.53.10) is not true as shows in the following example:

+	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	2	3	0
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	0	1	2

-	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

It is easy to show that $(X; +, -, 0)$ is a SA-algebra . $S = \{0, 2\}$ is a SA-subalgebra of X but S is not SA-algebra of X since $3+3=2 \in S$ and $2-3=0 \in S$ but $3+2=1 \notin S$.

Proposition 4.2.16.12:

Let I be a SA-ideal of SA-algebra X, then for all $x, y \in X, x \leq y, y \in I$ imply $x \in I$.

Corollary 4.2.16.13:

Let I be a SA-ideal of SA-algebra X, For any $x \in I$, we have $-x \in I$.

Definition 4.2.16.14:

Let $(X; +, -, 0)$ be a SA-algebra, a fuzzy subset of X is called a **fuzzy SA-subalgebra** of X if it ,for all $x, y \in X, \mu(x + y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

Definition 4.2.16.15:

Let $(X; +, -, 0)$ be a SA-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is called a fuzzy SA-ideal with degree (λ, κ) of X if it satisfies :for all $x, y, z \in X$ and λ, κ is members of $(0, 1]$,

$(FI_1) \mu(0) \geq \lambda \mu(x)$,

$(FI_2) \mu(x + y) \geq \kappa \min\{\mu(x + z), \mu(y - z)\}$.

Example 4.2.16.16:

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following tables:

+	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	2	3	0
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	0	1	2

-	0	1	2	3
0	0	3	2	1
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	1	0	3
3	3	2	1	0

then $(X; +, -, 0)$ is a SA-algebra

Define a fuzzy subset by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.7 & \text{if } x \in \{0,1\} \\ 0.3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

$I_1 = \{0,1\}$ is a SA-ideal of X. Routing calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy SA-ideal with degree $(\frac{4}{7}, \frac{4}{7})$ of X.

4.2.17. ψ -algebras:

The notion of ψ -algebras was formulated first in 2016 by Areej Tawfeeq Hameed. introduce the notion of ψ -algebra which is a good generalization of some algebraic structures such as the medial (BCI\BCH-algebras), ..

Definition 4.2.17.1: An ψ -algebra is a nonempty set X with a constant (0), which is an algebra $(X; \oplus, *, 0)$ with two binary operations (\oplus) and ($*$) and constant (0), such that for all $x, y, z \in X$, satisfies the following properties:

$$(\psi_1) \quad x * x = 0$$

$$(\psi_2) \quad x * 0 = x,$$

$$(\psi_3) \quad (x \oplus y) * z = (x * z) \oplus y.$$

For brevity we shall call X a ψ -algebra unless otherwise specified .

In X we can define a binary relation (\leq) by : $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Example 4.2.17.2: Let \mathbb{Z} be the set of all integers and $n\mathbb{Z} = \{nz \mid z \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. Then $(\mathbb{Z}; +, -, 0)$ and $(n\mathbb{Z}; +, -, 0)$ are both ψ -algebras with usual the addition and the subtraction operations. Also, $(\mathbb{R}; +, -, 0)$ and $(\mathbb{C}; +, -, 0)$ are both

ψ -algebras where R is the set of all real numbers , C is the set of all complex numbers with usual the addition and the subtraction operations.

Example 4.2.17.3: Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a set with operations given by the following tables:

\oplus	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	1	0	4	0	3
2	2	4	0	1	2
3	3	0	1	0	1
4	4	3	2	1	0

$*$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	4	0	0	0
3	3	0	1	0	0
4	4	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; \oplus, *, 0)$ is a ξ -algebra.

Lemma 4.2.17.4: Let $(X; \oplus, *, 0)$ be a ψ -algebra. Then for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(L_1) \quad x \oplus y = x * (0 * y).$$

$$(L_2) \quad x = 0 * (0 * x), \quad x * y = 0 * (y * x) \text{ and } x * y = (0 * y) \oplus x$$

$$(L_3) \quad x \oplus y = y \oplus x,$$

$$(L_4) \quad (x \oplus y) * (x \oplus z) = y * z, \text{ and } (x * z) * (y * z) = (x * y)$$

$$(L_5) \quad (0 * (x * y)) = (0 * x) \oplus y \text{ and } 0 * (x \oplus y) = (0 * x) \oplus (0 * y),$$

$$(L_6) \quad (x * y) * z = x * (z \oplus y).$$

Proposition 4.2.17.5: Let $(X; \oplus, *, 0)$ be a ψ -algebra. Then the following hold: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(a_1) \quad x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0, \text{ imply } x = y,$$

$$(a_2) \quad x \oplus y = x * (0 * y),$$

$$(a_3) \quad x * y = x \oplus (0 * y),$$

$$(a_4) \quad (x * y) * z = (x * z) * y,$$

$$(a_5) \quad (x * y) * x = 0 * y,$$

$$(a_6) \quad 0 * (x * y) = y * x,$$

$$(a_7) \quad 0 * x = 0 \text{ implies that } x = 0,$$

$$(a_8) \quad x = (x * 0) * 0,$$

$$(a_9) \quad z * x = z * y \text{ implies that } 0 * x = 0 * y.$$

Proposition 4.2.17.6: Let $(X; \oplus, *, 0)$ be a ψ -algebra. Then the following hold: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(b_1) \quad x * y \leq z \text{ imply } x * z \leq y,$$

$$(b_2) \quad x \leq y \text{ implies that } z \oplus y \leq z \oplus x,$$

$$(b_3) \quad x \leq y \text{ implies } x * z \leq y * z,$$

$$(b_4) \quad x \leq y \text{ and } y \leq z \text{ imply } x \leq z.$$

Proposition 4.2.17.7: Let $(X; \oplus, *, 0)$ be a ψ -algebra and (\leq) be a relation on X . Then

(X, \leq) is a partially ordered set.

Proof:

Let X be a ψ -algebra and let $x, y, z \in X$, since $x * x = 0$, $x \leq x$.

Suppose that $x \leq y$ and $y \leq x$, then $x * y = 0 = y * x$ and $x = y$ (by (a_1)).

Suppose that $x \leq y$ and $y \leq z$, then by (b_4) , $x \leq z$. Thus (X, \leq) is a partially ordered set.

Proposition 4.2.17.8: $(X; \oplus, *, 0_X)$ and $(Y; \oplus, *, 0_Y)$ are ψ -algebras, where X is a group derived ψ -algebra and Y is a left ψ -algebra. Let $(x_1, y_1) \oplus (x_2, y_2) = (x_1 \oplus x_2, y_1 \oplus y_2)$ and $(x_1, y_1) * (x_2, y_2) = (x_1 * x_2, y_1 * y_2)$, for any $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in X \times Y$. Then $(X \times Y; \oplus, *, (0_X, 0_Y))$ is a ψ -algebra.

Proof:

Let $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), (x_3, y_3) \in X \times Y$, then

$$1- \quad (x_1, y_1) * (x_1, y_1) = (x_1 * x_1, y_1 * y_1) = (0_X, 0_Y),$$

$$2- \quad (x_1, y_1) * (0_X, 0_Y) = (x_1 * 0_X, y_1 * 0_Y) = (x_1, y_1),$$

$$3- \quad ((x_1, y_1) \oplus (x_2, y_2)) * (x_3, y_3) = ((x_1 \oplus x_2), (y_1 \oplus y_2)) * (x_3, y_3) \\ = ((x_1 \oplus x_2) * x_3, (y_1 \oplus y_2) * y_3) = ((x_1 * x_3) \oplus x_2, (y_1 * y_3) \oplus y_2)$$

$= ((x_1, y_1) * (x_3, y_3)) \oplus (x_2, y_2)$.Hence $(X \times Y; \oplus, *, (0_X, 0_Y))$ is a ψ -algebra. \square

Definition 4.2.17.9: Let X be a ψ -algebra and S be a nonempty set of X . S is called a ψ -sub-algebra of X if $x \oplus y \in S$, $x * y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$.

Definition 4.2.17.10: A nonempty subset I of a ψ -algebra X is called a ψ -ideal of X if it satisfies:
for $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(I_1) 0 \in I,$$

$$(I_2) (x \oplus y) * z \in I \text{ and } y \in I \text{ imply } (x * z) \in I$$

Example 4.2.17.11: Let $(Z_6; \oplus_6, *_6, 0)$ be a set with the following tables:

\oplus_6	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	0	3	4	5	0
2	2	3	0	5	0	1
3	3	4	5	0	1	2
4	4	5	0	1	0	3
5	5	0	1	2	3	0

$*_6$	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	5	4	3	2	1
1	1	0	5	4	3	2
2	2	1	0	5	4	3
3	3	2	1	0	5	4
4	4	3	2	1	0	5
5	5	4	3	2	1	0

Then

$(Z_6; \oplus_6, *_6, 0)$ is a ψ -algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, \bar{3}\} = \langle \bar{3} \rangle$ and

$I_2 = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{4}\} = \langle \bar{2} \rangle$ are ψ -ideals of $(Z_6; \oplus_6, *_6, 0)$.

SECTION THREE

4.3. Some Types of Algebras with some operation

In this section, we will provide you with the internationally agreed terms for the generation of all types of algebraic that are independent of each other.

A specific number consists of a certain type of algebraic species .

1	$x * x = 0,$
2	$x * 0 = x,$
3	$x * 0 = 0,$
4	$0 * x = x,$
5	$0 * x = 0,$
6	$x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \text{ imply } x = y,$
7	$x * (y * z) = 0 \Rightarrow y * (x * z) = 0 .$
8	$x * y = y * x .$
9	$x * (y * z) = y * (x * z) .$
10	$(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$
11	$x * (y * z) = (x * y) * z .$
12	$((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0,$
13	$((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0,$
14	$(x * y) * ((y * z) * (x * z)) = 0,$
15	$(x * z) * (x * y) = y * z .$
16	$(x * y) * (x * z) = y * z .$
17	$(x * y) * z = (x * z) * (y * z) .$
18	$x * (y * z) = (x * y) * (x * z) .$
19	$x * (x * y) = (x * y) * (x * y) .$
20	$x * (y * x) = 0$
21	$x * (y * x) = x,$
22	$x * (y * x) = y$
23	$x * (x * y) = y * (y * x)$
24	$(x * y) * y = (y * x) * x$
25	$0 * (x * y) = y * x .$
26	$(x * (x * y)) * y = 0,$
27	$(x * y) * (0 * y) = x .$
28	$(x * y) * x = 0 * y$
29	$(x * y) * z = x * (z * (0 * y)) .$
30	$(x * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * (x * z)) = 0,$
31	$((x * y) * z) * ((x * z) * y) = (z * y) * x,$

32	$((x * y) * z) * ((x * z) * y) * ((z * y) * x) = 0,$
33	$x * (x * (y * (y * x))) = y * (y * (x * (x * y))).$
34	$x * y = 0$ implies that $x = y,$
35	$((x * y) * (x * z)) * (y * z) = 0 .$

The relation of some types algebras

Now, we will present a diagram showing how to connect between the types of algebras and how one can get from one species to another.

- 1- $BCI_1 + BCI_3 + BCI_4 + BCI_5 + (x * 0 = x) \approx$ BCC-algebra .
- 2- $BCI_3 + BCI_4 + BCI_5 \approx$ d-algebra .
- 3- $BCI_3 + BCI_4 + (x * 0 = x) \approx$ BH-algebra .
- 4- $BCI_1 +$ d-algebra $+ (x * 0 = x) \approx$ BCC-algebra .
- 5- $BCI_1 +$ d-algebra $+ (x * (x * y)) * y = 0 \approx$ BCK-algebra.

Remark :

$x * x = 0, x * 0 = x$ ----- (*)

6- (*) + $[x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ implies that $x = y]$ \approx BH-algebra .

7- (*) + $[(x * y) * (0 * y) = x]$ \approx BG-algebra .

8- (*) + $[(x * y) * z = x * (z * (0 * y))]$ \approx B-algebra .

Remark :

$x * x = 0, 0 * x = 0$ ---- (**)

9- (**) + $[(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y]$ \approx Q-algebra .

10- (**) + $[x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ implies that $x = y]$ \approx d-algebra .

Remark :

11- Q-algebra + $[(x * z) * (x * y) = y * z]$ \approx QS-algebra .

12- KUS -algebra is dual of QS -algebra .

11- β -algebra + $[(x + y) * (x + z) = y * z]$ \approx SA-algebra .

The following diagrams illustrate the relationship between algebras

Now, we will present a diagram showing how to connect between the types of algebras and how one can get from one species to another.

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$+ [x*y = 0 \text{ and } y*x=0 \text{ implies that } x=y] \approx \mathbf{d\text{-algebra}}$

$+ [(x*y)*z=(x*z)*y] \approx \mathbf{Q\text{-algebra}}$

Prof. Dr. Areej Tawfeeq Hameed

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